

Year 2 Annual Report (PUBLIC)

(1 May 2024—30 Apr 2025)

THIS REPORT HAS BEEN EDITED TO REMOVE CONFIDENTIAL INFORMATION

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1. Progress against core objectives

The Open Book Futures (OBF) project team works collaboratively across 7 work packages (WPs). Below, we highlight examples of some of the ways in which we have pursued our project's 5 core objectives in Year 2. (NB. Many of the things summarised here are elaborated on further later in the report.)

Objective 1: Enhance the impact of Copim initiatives

The **Open Book Collective (OBC, WP2)** has become an impactful and vital revenue source for OA publishers and service providers, and a trusted way for libraries to financially support fee-free OA book publishing.¹ The OBC now has over 80 financial supporters from the UK, EU, US, Canada, Australia and New Zealand, and the registered charity is on-track to reach financial sustainability by the end of this grant period. Since the OBC's launch in early 2023, its supporters have committed over £1 million in revenue, almost three quarters of which was received during the life of the OBF project.² Importantly, this revenue is having a major impact on the publishers and service providers that the OBC supports. For example, thanks to the funds provided by the OBC, several publishers (including both smaller scholar-led publishers like **Mattering Press**, **mediastudies.press** and **African Minds**, as well as larger university presses, like **University of London Press**) have been empowered to hire new staff to build OA publishing capacity. **Opening the Future (OtF, WP3)** also reached an important milestone in Year 2 of the project: over £500K raised for its two presses (Liverpool University Press and CEU Press), thanks to subscriptions from over 100 libraries.³ To date, OtF revenue has provided funding for over 70 OA books (around half of which have now been published).⁴ OtF is having an

¹ <https://openbookcollective.org/>. Reports and posts published by OBC are available at <https://openbookcollective.pubpub.org/news>.

² A list of supporters is available on the OBC website: https://openbookcollective.org/cms/fixe_d_page/supporters/

³ <https://www.openingthefuture.net/>. Reports and posts published by OtF are available at <https://copim.pubpub.org/opening-the-future> and <https://www.openingthefuture.net/news/>.

⁴ Statistics from: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15189000>.

“immeasurable” positive impact on authors, who have been enabled to publish their work OA without the barrier of a processing charge.⁵

Objective 2: Bridge the infrastructure gap

Thoth Open Metadata (WP4) is now enabling over 60 publishers to access vital book supply infrastructures: ensuring that OA books are discoverable and accessible across an array of platforms, and bridging major infrastructure gaps.⁶ For example, Thoth has developed a plug-in to PKP's Open Monograph Press (OMP), successfully beta-testing it with presses in South Africa, Scotland, Austria and the Netherlands, and releasing it openly on GitHub.⁷ OMP is widely used by presses, and Thoth's new plug-in allows those presses to significantly streamline their workflows and enhance the discoverability of their publications by integrating directly with Thoth's metadata management system and its dissemination and archiving services. Thoth developed several other service integrations in Year 2, including strengthening dissemination links with several major aggregator platforms (JSTOR, Project MUSE, EBSCOhost, ProQuest and Clarivate/ExLibris).⁸

Objective 3: Incubate & financially support OA initiatives

In Year 2 of OBF, the **Open Book Collective (OBC, WP2)** announced the first 3 recipients of its Collective Development Fund (CDF), awarding £37,500 across 3 projects.⁹ Each project will build capacity to increase the quantity, quality and diversity of OA books, with particular emphasis on initiatives based in the Global South. For example, one of the CDF's

⁵ C. McGann, Grady, T., & Hopkins, K. (2025). “Opening the Future, Author Profile: Daniel Silva”. *Copim*. <https://copim.pubpub.org/pub/empire-found>.

⁶ <https://thoth.pub/about/about-us>. Reports and posts published by Thoth are available at <https://copim.pubpub.org/thoth>. Full publisher catalogue metadata can be accessed on Thoth's website (<https://thoth.pub/publishers>), with the caveat that not all publishers using Thoth already have book data available in the catalogue. Individual book title data can be accessed via <https://thoth.pub/books>.

⁷ The Thoth OMP-plugin is available at <https://github.com/thoth-pub/thoth-omp-plugin>. For more information on the plug-in, see <https://thoth.pub/solutions/integrations>.

⁸ See these recent presentations for an overview of Thoth services and integrations: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14674033> and <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13987020>.

⁹ Open Book Collective (2024). “OBC Collective Development Fund Grant Programme: 2024 Call & Guidance”. *OBC Information Hub*. <https://openbookcollective.pubpub.org/pub/obc-collective-development-fund-grant-programme-2024-call-guidance>.

grant recipients will use the financial support to establish the first OA university press in Zimbabwe.¹⁰ The OBC announced a second call for CDF applications in January 2025.¹¹ Six applications (all from LMICs) have been sent for external review, and the OBC expects to be able to allocate all the remaining project-allocated CDF funds (c. £57,000) in 2025. Further CDF calls will follow annually once the OBF project concludes. Post-project, the CDF will continue thanks to funds provided by OBC's publisher and service provider members, using portions of the revenue they receive from their supporters.¹² The OBC forecasts that it will be able to issue annual calls of around £30,000 post-project, drawing in part on the over £45,000 already accrued to the CDF from its members to date. In this way, our project is building a resource that will incubate and financially support OA initiatives many years into the future.¹³

The **Experimental Publishing Group (WP6)** has worked closely with its 3 Experimental Publishing pilot projects in Year 2. Each pilot is receiving a grant of £15,000, and is receiving mentorship and guidance from WP6 and the wider OBF project team. The pilot projects are being carefully documented through reports and outreach workshops, and this documentation is helping to incubate and inspire greater experimentation with the form and format of the scholarly book.¹⁴

¹⁰ J. Fathallah (2024). "Announcing OBC's Second Collective Development Fund Award: Enhancing Open Access Book Publishing at Chinhoyi University of Technology Library". *OBC Information Hub*. <https://openbookcollective.pubpub.org/pub/announcing-obcs-second-collective-development-fund-award-enhancing-open-access-book-publishing-at-chinhoyi-university-of-technology-library>.

For information on the other CDF recipients, see J. Fathallah (2024). "Announcing OBC's First Collective Development Fund award: Fostering Academic Self-Reliance in Nigeria through Open Access Books". *OBC Information Hub*. <https://openbookcollective.pubpub.org/pub/announcing-obcs-first-collective-development-fund-award-fostering-academic-self-reliance-in-nigeria-through-open-access-books>; and J. Fathallah (2025). "Announcing OBC's Third Collective Development Fund Award: The Community Publishing Garden". *OBC Information Hub*. <https://openbookcollective.pubpub.org/pub/announcing-obcs-third-collective-development-fund-awardthe-community-publishing-garden>.

¹¹ J. Fathallah (2025). "OBC Collective Development Fund Grant Programme: 2025 Call & Guidance". *OBC Information Hub*. <https://openbookcollective.pubpub.org/pub/obc-collective-development-fund-grant-programme-2025-call--guidance>.

¹² See https://openbookcollective.org/cms/fixd_page/funding_model/.

¹³ Drawing on OBC's most recent accounts, up to 30 April 2025. See also J. Deville (2025). "Reporting: 2025 and into the future". *OBC Information Hub*. <https://openbookcollective.pubpub.org/pub/reporting-2025-into-the-future>.

¹⁴ See <https://copim.pubpub.org/experimental-publishing-group>.

Objective 4: Enhance engagement with the wider OA publishing ecosystem

Opening the Future (OtF, WP3) led the initial launch of the “Copim Compass” Info Hub site in Year 2, sharing a range of toolkits and information designed to engage publishers already active within, or considering joining, the OA publishing ecosystem.¹⁵ Initial resources available on Copim Compass comprehensively document OtF’s collective funding model, providing presses with the information and insights needed to successfully fund their frontlist OA books equitably, sustainably and affordably.¹⁶ The Copim Compass site also includes a curated list of resources, signposting and summarising existing online guides to OA book publishing.¹⁷ An extensive scoping report (conducted and published in Year 2 of the project), and reviewed by project partners in the UK and US, identified a clear need for this “guide of guides”.¹⁸ In Year 3, Copim Compass will continue to grow, by offering authors, presses and libraries tools to help them engage with, navigate and support a brighter future for OA book publishing, including “success story” case studies.¹⁹ Our **Accessibility Work Package (WP5)** is also developing a knowledge base and tools to help publishers adapt their workflows to meet and exceed accessibility standards, these will be launched on Copim Compass in Year 3 of the project.

The project team has also been leading on fostering exchange between like-minded infrastructures, to more closely collaborate on establishing an open ecosystem for OA books. This recently culminated in the inception of an OPERAS Working Group dedicated to Open Infrastructures. The WG is now jointly coordinated by the Open Book Collective and Thoth Open Metadata and brings together more than 30 representatives from a global network of infrastructures active in the

¹⁵ See <https://compass.copim.ac.uk/>.

¹⁶ See <https://compass.copim.ac.uk/books/06-opening-the-future-introduction-and-description>.

¹⁷ See <https://compass.copim.ac.uk/books/02-open-access-book-publishing-a-comprehensive-overview-of-resources>.

¹⁸ K. Hopkins & Hughes, A. (2024). “Open Book Futures InfoHub scoping report”.

Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13842916>.

¹⁹ See <https://compass.copim.ac.uk/books/03-author-success-stories> and <https://compass.copim.ac.uk/books/04-library-success-stories>.

wider OA books publishing landscape.²⁰ In addition, the Open Book Collective co-leads the OPERAS Business Models WG, which together with the Open Access Books Network WG (co-led by Copim’s Lucy Barnes), are the three constituent parts of the OPERAS OA Books Special Interest Group.

Objective 5: Foster bibliodiversity

In December 2024, the OBF team published a co-authored piece documenting our perspective on Bibliodiversity, and the various ways in which we are working to support it.²¹ The **Experimental Publishing Group (WP6)** has been active in Year 2, working with publishers, authors and open-source platform providers to foster and encourage practices of experimentation and reuse: an important part of ensuring diversity in the form and format of OA books, and realising the creative potential of authors, publishers and their works. A series of Experimental Book Publishing in Practice seminars (delivered as webinars and shared afterwards as recordings) offered valuable practical advice on the tools, platforms and software available to support the publication of experimental books.²² In Year 2, WP6 also published multiple documentation posts, prepared in collaboration with the project’s 3 Experimental Publishing Pilots.²³

Objective 6: Support emerging OA books policy guidance

The project’s **Archiving & Digital Preservation Work Package (WP7)** is engaged in scoping the funding, technical and administrative needs of a National Libraries archiving network, as well as enhanced archiving workflows for the preservation of PhD theses. In Year 2, WP7 planned and initiated a series of guided workshop consultations with colleagues

²⁰ T. Steiner, Barnes, L., Fathallah, J., Findanis, J., Gatti, R., Deville, J., Sanders, K., Higman, R., Stern, N., & Stone, G. (2025). “Seeding for a not-for-profit community-led OA books ecosystem”. *Copim*. <https://doi.org/10.21428/785a6451.d35141ca>.

²¹ J. Adema, Barnes, L., Deville, J., Fathallah, J., Gatti, R., Grady, T., Hopkins, K., Hughes, A., McGann, C., Sanders, K., & Steiner, T. (2024). The Copim perspective on Bibliodiversity. *Copim*. <https://doi.org/10.21428/785a6451.86a892a7>.

²² See https://compendium.copim.ac.uk/practice_seminars.

²³ See <https://copim.pubpub.org/experimental-publishing-group>.

at National Libraries, whilst also undertaking extensive research into the workflows surrounding PhD thesis archiving.²⁴ This research is building towards the publication of evidenced policy guidance and recommendations, which will be published in Year 3 of the project. This is a key area in which the OBF project is supporting emerging OA books policy: placing a spotlight on ensuring the long-term preservation and accessibility of OA books and PhD theses.

Within **WP4 (Thoth Open Metadata)**, the team is working hard to implement changes to Thoth's metadata model to accommodate accessibility and archiving-specific information. Thoth is also looking to implement additional metadata fields as well as changes to metadata exports such as ONIX 3.1.2 that cater to incoming legislation and related reporting needs as mandated by the European Union, such as the EU's new General Product Safety Regulation (GPSR), EU Deforestation Act, and Accessibility Act legislations.

2. "Please provide a summary of how your project has delivered wider benefits beyond success criteria. For example, achieving outcomes not originally planned for."

In this report we detail many ways in which we've achieved successes that exceed our initial plans. In Year 2, we exceeded several annual revenue and member/user growth targets at both OBC and Thoth. For example, Thoth ended the year with twice as many publishers using its service than initially targeted (64 users, against a target of 30), and three times as many signed up for fee-paying services (20 users, against a target of 5).

Our work is directly impacting the development of other OA financial models on a global scale. A highlight this year was the launch of Open Journals Collective (OJC). OJC brings some of the key principles of the OBC's financial & governance model to OA journals.²⁵ The OBF project team supported the OJC's development by convening a workshop in London (Jan 2025), and Rupert Gatti (OBC Board Member and project lead at Open Book Publishers) is one of

²⁴ See M. Barnes (2025). "Scoping PhD Theses: Some initial reflections". *Copim*. <https://doi.org/10.21428/785a6451.d98f9a16> and M. Barnes (2024). "The OBF National Libraries Network: a summary of our first year". *Copim*. <https://doi.org/10.21428/785a6451.dd03d609>.

²⁵ C. Edwards (2025). "Academic libraries cannot afford to carry on with transformative agreements". *LSE Impact*. <https://blogs.lse.ac.uk/impactofsocialsciences/2025/03/31/academic-libraries-cannot-afford-to-carry-on-with-transformative-agreements/>.

three OJC founding Directors. The OJC was launched at UKSG 2025, with Caroline Edwards introducing the model at a panel convened by the OBF project.²⁶ As we discussed in our Year 1 reporting, Copim's OtF revenue model has also been cited as a reference point in the formation of De Gruyter's UPLO (an OA eBook initiative), with De Gruyter acknowledging that UPLO "leverages insights gained" from OtF.²⁷

The scale of our outreach has also significantly extended beyond what we anticipated. This includes far deeper engagement in an African context. In Year 2, we were invited to lead a 2-day workshop at the Diamond Open Access Summit in Cape Town, which was attended by participants from over 10 African countries. It was an honour to contribute to this major event, which has set the stage for discussions about OA publishing in the Global South for years to come.²⁸ In collaboration with African partners, the OBF project team are co-leading a network-mapping project, to help record and connect OA book initiatives and stakeholders on the African continent.²⁹ Two of the OBC's Collective Development Fund grants are currently supporting fledgling OA initiatives in Zimbabwe and Nigeria, and we anticipate that further Development Fund grants will be awarded to Global South initiatives in Year 3 of the project.³⁰ Our project's Experimental Publishing Group (WP6) is also funding a pilot project co-led by African Minds, the Research Data Share Collective and the Platform for Experimental Collaborative Ethnography, which will "build a 'database as book' to support an emergent collective of critical STS scholars in Kenya".³¹

The importance of the OBF project and Copim's research has also been recognised by external stakeholders. In 2024, a research report published by the Copim team in 2020 was cited in a "Report to the U.S. Congress on Financing Mechanisms for Open Access Publishing

²⁶ J. Deville, Grady, T., Edwards, C., Gatti, R., & Stern, N. (2025). "It's nice, but is it sustainable?' Rethinking sustainability for Diamond open access infrastructures & funding models". UKSG 2025. *Zenodo*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15189001>.

²⁷ See <https://www.degruyter.com/publishing/paradigm-publishing-services-university-press-library-embarks-on-a-sustainable-open-access-initiative-for-university-press-monographs>; <https://uplopen.com/about>. While we have concerns about UPLOpen's governance, including the fact that it is controlled by a non-profit foundation created by the large commercial publisher, De Gruyter Brill, it nonetheless shows the influence of our work on the sector.

²⁸ "Open Monograph Publishing: A workshop at the 2nd Global Summit on Diamond OA" (2024). *OBC Information Hub*. <https://doi.org/10.21428/41ca814e.02291384>.

²⁹ J. Fathallah (2025). "Reflections on Open Monograph Publishing: A workshop at the 2nd Global Summit on Diamond OA". *OBC Information Hub*. <https://doi.org/10.21428/41ca814e.b9ef0e6b>.

³⁰ J. Fathallah (2024). "Announcing OBC's Second Collective Development Fund Award: Enhancing Open Access Book Publishing at Chinhoyi University of Technology Library". *OBC Information Hub*. <https://openbookcollective.pubpub.org/pub/announcing-obcs-second-collective-development-fund-award-enhancing-open-access-book-publishing-at-chinhoyi-university-of-technology-library> and J. Fathallah (2024). "Announcing OBC's First Collective Development Fund award: Fostering Academic Self-Reliance in Nigeria through Open Access Books". *OBC Information Hub*. <https://openbookcollective.pubpub.org/pub/announcing-obcs-first-collective-development-fund-award-fostering-academic-self-reliance-in-nigeria-through-open-access-books>.

³¹ J. Adema (2024). "Launch of Experimental Book Publishing Pilot Project 'Database as Book'." *Copim*. <https://copim.pubpub.org/pub/database-book-launch>.

of Federally Funded Research”.³² For policy-makers, our research offers a reliable source of information on Diamond revenue models and values-driven, community led OA publishing. Indeed, our work was highlighted in a major independent report commissioned by Research England’s UKRI, which included the following summary of our impact on the field:

Amongst [Copim’s] many outputs are recommendations for how to set up a sustainable governance structure that ensures editorial independence, diverse participation, and sustainable financing without the threat of a commercial buyout (Hart, Adema & COPIM 2022). The COPIM project also developed two highly influential collective funding models: Opening the Future (Eve, Pinter, Poznanski et al 2022), and The Open Book Collective.³³

Tahia Zaidi (UKRI) cited the work of Open Book Futures at the PALOMERA Conference (Oct 2024).³⁴

Something that frequently surfaces in this report is our team’s ability to build, grow and foster collaboration at a scale significantly beyond what we imagined in our initial project planning. Our outreach and service-development is increasingly conducted through partnerships, motivated by a desire to “approach interested stakeholders in a more concerted fashion” and to realise “the powerful potential of [...] an interoperable, interconnected network”.³⁵ This year, for example, we coordinated a successful, joint proposal to establish an Open Infrastructures for OA Books Working Group within OPERAS, which held its inaugural meeting in March 2025 (with 20 international registered attendees).³⁶ In the recent “State of Open Infrastructure Report”, published by Invest in Open Infrastructures (IOI), OBC and Thoth were cited as exemplifying that “interconnectivity between infrastructures is dense”. IOI’s poll

³² “Updated Report to the U.S. Congress on Financing Mechanisms for Open Access Publishing of Federally Funded Research” (2024). *bidenwhitehouse.archives.gov*. <https://bidenwhitehouse.archives.gov/wp-content/uploads/2024/06/2024-Report-to-Appropriations-Committee-on-Scholarly-Publishing-and-Public-Access-Implementation.pdf>.

³³ L. Estelle, Jago, D., Jones, R., Laakso, M., Snijder, R., & Wise, A. (2025). “Supporting learned society, subject association, and smaller specialist publishers to transition to open access book publishing (SPA OPS 4.0 project)”. *Zenodo*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14679068>. The report includes several other references to the project and our initiatives.

³⁴ The PALOMERA conference was recorded, and Tahia’s comments are at 1 hour 32 minutes (https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=qhUdmDdsd_Y).

³⁵ Kumu map: <https://kumu.io/flavoursofopen/oa-books-landscape-overview>. Account of workshops and network mapping: T. Steiner, Barnes, L., Fathallah, J., Findanis, J., Gatti, R., Deville, J., Sanders, K., Higman, R., Stern, N., & Stone, G. (2025). “Seeding for a not-for-profit community-led OA books ecosystem”. *Copim*. <https://doi.org/10.21428/785a6451.d35141ca>.

³⁶ T. Steiner, Barnes, L., Stern, N., Stone, G., Gatti, R., Proudman, V., & Shuttleworth, K. (2024). “Inception of an OPERAS Open Infrastructures for OA Books Working Group (1.0)”. *Zenodo*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15166501>.

found that when an infrastructure uses Open Book Collective, they are also likely to use Thoth, OAPEN Library, Open Monograph Press, DOAB and others.³⁷ Thus, our focus on interoperability and partnerships is working, and we look forward to unlocking new successes and opportunities via collaborations in Year 3 of the project.

3. “Please provide an update on the sustainability of the project post-funding or on the legacy of the project if this is not applicable.”

Exceeding targets on the road to self-sustainability

In addition to the grant funding received through the OBF project, Thoth (WP4) has received over £100K in revenue since the OBF project began in 2023. This figure means that Thoth has already exceeded its initial target of raising £65K by the end of Year 3. Thoth also exceeded its Year 2 target for the number of publishers using its services by over 100%: over 60 publishers, based around the world, now use the platform to manage their metadata.³⁸ A vital component of ensuring Thoth’s sustainability post-project is Thoth Plus: a range of added-value services charged according to a banded pricing structure.³⁹ Year 2 of the project saw Thoth Plus become a viable new revenue stream for Thoth. More than 20 publishers have signed up to date, exceeding Thoth’s initial ambitions for the model. Similarly, and to establish a second source of funding, Thoth has been working with university libraries who recognise the social value Thoth is providing within the scholarly publishing ecosystem and who choose to help sustain its operations via participation in the OBC funding package.

In Year 2 of the project (1 May 2024-30 April 2025), the OBC (WP2) contracted revenue of over £700K, exceeding its Year 2 target by over 16%. The OBC also exceeded its Year 2 target for increasing its publisher/service provider members. New service provider and publisher members welcomed in Year 2 were the Public Knowledge Project (PKP), LSE Press, Verlag Barbara Budrich and Sidestone.⁴⁰

³⁷ “2025 State of Open Infrastructure Report” (2025). <https://investinopen.org/state-of-open-infrastructure-2025/sooi-vital-open-infrastructures-in-a-volatile-moment-2025/>.

³⁸ All publisher metadata can be accessed on Thoth’s website (<https://thoth.pub/publishers>), with the caveat that not all publishers using Thoth already have book data available in the catalogue.

³⁹ See <https://thoth.pub/pricing>.

⁴⁰ See <https://openbookcollective.pubpub.org/pub/the-open-book-collective-welcomes-pkp>; <https://openbookcollective.pubpub.org/pub/lse-press-joins-the-open-book-collective>; <https://openbookcollective.pubpub.org/pub/verlag-barbara-budrich-press-joins-the-open-book-collective>; and <https://openbookcollective.pubpub.org/pub/ye52vnsy>.

When preparing our deliverables for the Open Book Futures project, we set ourselves ambitious annual growth targets for the OBC and Thoth, with the aim of both reaching financial self-sustainability by the end of the Open Book Futures project. Despite a challenging financial climate for HE institutions in the UK and beyond,⁴¹ both Thoth and OBC managed to exceed their growth targets for Year 2, meaning that both are on track for sustainability post-project.

Enhancing our websites and systems to guarantee the legacy of the project

We made several improvements to the OBC's website in Year 2: working with developers to scope and develop a new CRM system for managing back-end administration (to be launched later this year), and introducing a public-facing multilingual interface (the first language—German—is set to launch soon). These enhancements to the OBC online platform are vital for the long-term sustainability of the OBC. The OBC's growth post-funding will require new Publisher and Service Provider members, as well as supporting institutions, from outside the anglophone world, and this outreach work will be better supported by the new site.

Thoth is also continually updating and enhancing the services it offers.⁴² In Year 2, Thoth also focused on establishing and building partnerships with organisations and infrastructures in the OA book supply chain, laying strong foundations for collaboration and integration in Year 3 and beyond. For example, both the OBC and Thoth became members of OPERAS, and Thoth is in discussions with the organisation about delivering title-level usage data via the OPERAS metrics service. Thoth's cooperations with OPERAS and other infrastructures, organisations, and consortia such as the Netherlands University Presses and SciELO Livros will allow it to continue to deliver exciting new services and integrations post-project.

Planning for the future

In February 2025, the project's Experimental Publishing Group (WP6) published a report scoping the long-term governance of its Experimental Publishing Compendium (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14802272>).⁴³ WP6 has already begun to implement the governance structures discussed in the report: convening a new Compendium Advisory

⁴¹ BBC News (November 2024). "University cash crisis to get worse despite tuition fee rise, BBC told", <https://www.bbc.co.uk/news/articles/c14lv7e61d3o>.

⁴² See these recent presentations for an overview of Thoth services and integrations: <https://zenodo.org/records/14674033> and <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13987020>.

⁴³ J. Adema (2025), "Developing a Governance Model for the Experimental Publishing Compendium", *Zenodo*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14802273>

Community and Editorial Oversight Group, who will soon meet to discuss a drafted Editorial Policy, Terms of Engagement and Code of Conduct.

OtF (WP3), also used Year 2 to make plans for the future, conducting a SWOT analysis of its revenue model, which will be shared with colleagues within the project and externally to garner feedback on OtF's long-term future. In Year 3, OtF will produce a final full evaluation of its model, and put in place measures to ensure its continuation and legacy post-funding (several options are currently being assessed). In April, the WP also co-organised a collaborative workshop at the UKSG conference, in which the panellists discussed the topic: "It's Nice, but is it sustainable? Rethinking sustainability for Diamond open access infrastructures and funding models".⁴⁴ Events like this are part of OtF's strategy to work with the OA community to find a suitable long-term "home" for the model.

In Year 2, both Thoth & OBC hired external consultants to provide independent evaluations of their services. In both cases, the consultants were specifically invited to assess the long-term future of both initiatives, and to offer advice and recommendations on sustainability. The recommendations from these reports have been or will be shared publicly, and both Thoth and OBC are developing action plans for applying the advice received.⁴⁵ In both cases, the reports were positive about the outlook for both initiatives.

4. "How are you disseminating learning from your project to the wider HE sector and others who might benefit from your insights? Please provide examples which illustrate how your project has had influence on other providers?"

Example 1. Equitable & sustainable funding for OA books

The work of the Open Book Collective (WP2) exemplifies how our project is tangibly benefitting the wider HE sector by providing a vital, sustainable revenue stream for Open Access publishers and service providers. This benefits HE institutions, academics and the wider public, by ensuring that there are affordable, reputable and effective routes for authors to publish and disseminate their research Open Access, and a trusted way for libraries and other institutions to financially support, and help to shape, a brighter future for scholarly communication.

⁴⁴ Slides available: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15189001>

⁴⁵ Thoth's mid-term evaluation report, prepared by Imming Impact and TrendLab: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15131149>. The OBC will share findings from its evaluation report (prepared by Research Consulting) in a forthcoming report to be published in *LSE Impact*.

The OBC's online platform allows libraries and other institutions to subscribe to "Supporter Programmes" and become financial supporters of the OBC's "Member" organisations (which must all meet strict eligibility criteria).⁴⁶ In Year 2, the OBC's Members increased by 4, so its membership now includes 13 publishers and 3 service providers.⁴⁷ Many of these Members would be too small or under-resourced to assume the administrative burden of running a subscription supporter programme for themselves. The OBC's platform also allows these small publishers and initiatives to work together to gain funding. Members can seek support as part of packages, for example the "University Press Package", which is an international grouping of 4 university presses (Leuven University Press, LSE Press, University of London Press, University of Westminster Press).⁴⁸ The Members, as well as the 80+ institutions financially supporting them via the OBC, can take part in the OBC's community governance structures, giving these stakeholders a rare "seat at the table" when it comes to shaping the future of research publishing.

The money the OBC is transferring to its OA Publisher & Service Provider Members is having a major, beneficial influence on how these organisations operate and provide services to authors and readers. Often, the kinds of presses that are OBC members do not have the resources to fully support their OA publishing ambitions. However, several of the OBC's publisher Members, including both smaller scholar-led publishers and larger university presses, have reported being able to hire new staff members thanks to the reliable revenue stream the OBC has granted them: giving them a hitherto unknown level of security and operational strength.

For example, in March 2024, **Mattering Press** (a publisher of OA books within relational research on science, technology and society) hired its first ever employee: a Publishing Project Manager, who has had a transformative impact on the press's production workflows. Mattering Press reports: "We simply would not have had the financial security [to hire the Publishing Project Manager] without the new income stream from the Open Book Collective".⁴⁹ In March 2025, **mediastudies.press** also announced that it had hired its first Publishing Project Manager, with the aim of streamlining its workflows and aiding "the volunteer co-directors in the press's planned five-book-a-year production schedule".⁵⁰ The press noted that it was "grateful

⁴⁶ For more information on supporters see: https://www.openbookcollective.org/cms/fixd_page/supporters/. For more information on eligibility criteria see: https://openbookcollective.org/cms/fixd_page/why_support_oa.

⁴⁷ See a full list here: <https://openbookcollective.org/packages/inititatives/>.

⁴⁸ <https://openbookcollective.org/view/collections/13/>.

⁴⁹ <https://www.matteringpress.org/blog/annual-report-april-6th-2023-april-5th-2024>.

⁵⁰ <https://www.mediastudies.press/pub/2025-03-ghtena-announcement/release/2>.

to the Open Book Collective, whose funding through the ScholarLed Package [...] made [the] hiring possible”.

In a presentation delivered at the UKSG conference in April 2025, **University of London Press** also reported that the OBC’s funding was giving the press the “ability to hire [a] fixed term Editorial Assistant to support growth and training events” and an “EDI internship” to support their accessibility work.⁵¹ In an interview with the OBC, **African Minds Press** (an OA, not-for-profit, publisher of scholarly social science books, predominantly authored by African academics) reported that the “OBC has allowed us to appoint a first, permanent staff member”.⁵² The revenue stream provided by the OBC, gave the press “the breathing space to allow us the confidence to appoint someone and say, ‘we’re committed to your salary’”. African Minds explained that this is crucial in their local context, where “the publishing industry in South Africa is small in terms of scholarly publishing. [...] So, if we can find individuals who are committed to scholarly publishing, and we can look after them, that’s the really, really key thing”.

All four of these examples evidence the tangible influence the Open Book Futures project is having on providers. Members of the team have promoted the OBC via conferences, webinars, exhibition stands, meetings and email campaigns, gaining new library and consortium support via an active presence at events including UKSG, LIBER and Charleston.⁵³ The OBC team also handles the administrative and governance work involved in making the platform a success: working, for example, to register new subscribers, handle subscription renewals, prepare and report on finances, support and assess applications from potential new Members, and manage the Collective’s robust governance structure. This work is translating into enormous benefits for OBC’s members: ensuring that community-led, OA presses and providers can stabilise and grow their operations.

This positive impact on publishers, also has a wider positive impact on academic authors and their institutions. The reliable revenue supplied by the OBC is a catalyst for positive change at publishers, allowing them to move away from relying on author fees, and to publish more OA books per year: giving authors more opportunities to publish OA without the barrier of expensive fees. For example, **White Horse Press** (an independent academic publisher specialising in

⁵¹ <https://bsky.app/profile/joedeville.bsky.social/post/3llrbrislyd2o>.

⁵² Unpublished interview with African Mind Press staff member. Shared with permission.

⁵³ A. Hughes, Deville, J., Grady, T., Gatti, R., Steiner, T., Barnes, L., & Fitzpatrick, J. (2025). “Reflections from UKSG 2025”. *Copim*. <https://copim.pubpub.org/pub/reflections-from-uksg-2025>; K. Sanders (2024). “LIBER 2024, libraries, and support for sustainable Diamond OA”. *OBC Information Hub*. <https://openbookcollective.pubpub.org/pub/liber-2024>; L. Onalee Snyder & Grady, T. (2025). “A Reflection on 2024 Charleston Conference”. *Copim*. <https://copim.pubpub.org/pub/a-reflection-on-2024-charleston-conference>.

environmental humanities and social sciences) discussed the positive impacts of joining the OBC in a recent Annual Report:

Since joining OBC, we have seen a steady accumulation of subscriber support, with revenue coming in at a level that has made a direct impact on our ability to publish OA books. [...] we have a very healthy frontlist for 2025 – and thanks in large part to OBC support, our confirmed frontlist is currently 100% open access.[...] Looking ahead, as of March 2025 we have allocated £17,500 of OBC revenue towards three books currently in production, which would otherwise have to be published gated. We expect all these books to be published in FY25/26.⁵⁴

Thanks to OBC funding, authors without access to institutional funding for book processing charges, are able to find a route to Open Access publication at publishers like White Horse Press. This is vital for scholars based at under-funded institutions, and for ECRs who often lack access to institutional funding at all.

Opening the Future (WP3) is also helping to fund new OA publications equitably. The model is being used to fund new OA frontlist titles at **CEU Press** and **Liverpool University Press** (with plans in motion to expand this to 3 further presses before the end of the project). Over 100 libraries subscribe to OtF packages, granting them permanent access to collections of closed backlist titles at CEUP or LUP. These library subscriptions then directly fund the publication of the press's OA frontlist. In this way, OtF is a model that allows presses like CEUP and LUP to move towards OA incrementally, and it's an affordable way for libraries to build a more equitable publishing future. Since its inception, OtF has already raised over £500K for the presses it supports, providing funding for over 70 OA books (around half of which have been published, with the other half due to be published in the coming years). For the authors of these books, it means that there is a route available for BPC-free publication, at a prestigious press, which won't cost them or their institution a fee, and which allows their work to be read around the world without a cost-barrier for readers.

Peter Watson (Teaching Fellow at University of Leeds) is one example of an author whose book was published OA thanks to OtF. *Football and Nation Building in Colombia (2010-2018)* (Liverpool University Press, 2022) is Watson's first monograph, and he recognises the

⁵⁴ "The White Horse Press, Report 2024/2025: The Open Book Collective. March 2025" (2025). https://whpress.co.uk/Documents/OBCreport_2025-03-28.pdf.

benefits of having been able to share his research, fee-free, with an international audience thanks to OtF:

Readers in Latin America [...] can access the book open access which they would not have been able to do if not for Opening the Future. I feel my readership has therefore increased, and my 'presence' in the field became much more evident as a consequence, both to academics and students. [...]

As a result of not having to buy individual copies and be[ing] easily downloadable, the book has been included on a number of university reading lists across the globe (in the UK, the USA, Australia and in some South American countries, I believe) [...]. In this way, it has become a key text in discussing aspects of sporting nationalism and political use of football in South America and globally. I doubt this would have been the case if it was not open access.⁵⁵

According to OAPEN usage statistics (kindly shared with us by Liverpool University Press), Watson's book has already been viewed 3,000 times. Thanks to this experience, the author is now an advocate for the advantages of publishing OA, and his story provides a case study illustrating the positive, BPC-free methods that are available for authors. This year the project published interviews with several other authors who published OA thanks to OtF funding, and we are planning to publish more of these in Year 3.⁵⁶

Authors at CEUP have also acknowledged the benefits of participating in a mode of Open Access publication that is free of fees for them, their institution and their readers. When asked, "How has Open Access affected the reception of your book?", author Tomasz Kamusella (reader in modern history at the University of St Andrews), notes that:

It's influenced the reception of my book [Words in Space and Time: A Historical Atlas of Language Politics in Modern Central Europe (2021)] immensely when it comes to the number of people who are accessing it and who are using it for teaching [...] students have started using it and some are coming back to me with certain questions about the issues in the book. So, yeah, it's been quite a success!⁵⁷

⁵⁵ C. McGann, Grady, T., & Hopkins, K. (2025). "Opening the Future, Author Profile: Peter Watson". *Copim*. <https://copim.pubpub.org/pub/football-and-nation-building>.

⁵⁶ See also: C. McGann, Grady, T., & Hopkins, K. (2025). "Opening the Future, Author Profile: Mario Graña Taborelli". *Copim*. <https://copim.pubpub.org/pub/jurisdictional-battlefields> and C. McGann, Grady, T., & Hopkins, K. (2025). "Opening the Future, Author Profile: Daniel Silva". *Copim*. <https://copim.pubpub.org/pub/empire-found>.

⁵⁷ <https://x.com/CEUPress/status/1778380208623497519>.

Kamusella's book has been described by critics as "a very erudite, highly thought-provoking and pleasingly quirky book";⁵⁸ "the product of extensive work and [...] a fantastic read" that "will influence seminar teaching";⁵⁹ and a "treasure trove" that "should help scholars and curious readers".⁶⁰ The Open Book Futures project is proud to have helped this, and many other acclaimed and valuable works, to reach both scholars and "curious readers" around the world through OA publication. On the OAPEN platform, Kamusella's text has been downloaded over 1,300 times.

The Open Book Futures project is demonstrating that sustainable and equitable funding models for OA books work, and can have a major, positive impact on the HE sector. Our project is readying the field for future OA monograph mandates, which will demand more financially viable models. We're also working to move the needle on attitudes towards OA publishing: giving funders, publishers, authors and institutions positive case studies and narratives to share. As one author, whose book was published OA thanks to funding provided by OtF attests:

*Many students and colleagues have approached me to congratulate me for publishing Open Access. It has not deterred many from actually buying a physical copy of the book [...] I would totally recommend Open Access publishing. [...] Keep up the good work!*⁶¹

Example 2: Fostering bibliodiversity

A further way in which our project has disseminated learning to the wider HE sector, and had a beneficial benefit on others, is through fostering bibliodiversity. Whilst biodiversity allows ecosystems to survive and thrive, bibliodiversity is necessary to ensure a healthy publishing ecosystem that serves writers and readers. This bibliodiversity requires a diversity of publishers and publishing practices. As OBF team members Lucy Barnes and Rupert Gatti articulate:

diversity of publishers is hugely important to the monograph ecosystem – it provides for a diversity of specialisation, editorial positions, publishing objectives and (as we have

⁵⁸ F. King (2023). "Book Review: Words in Space and Time: Historical Atlas of Language Politics in Modern Central Europe by Tomasz Kamusella". *European History Quarterly*, 53(4), 717-719. <https://doi.org/10.1177/02656914231199945k>

⁵⁹ J. Koranyi (2023). "Review of Kamusella, Tomasz, *Words in Space and Time: A Historical Atlas of Language Politics in Modern Central Europe*". *H-German, H-Net Reviews*. <http://www.h-net.org/reviews/showrev.php?id=58829>.

⁶⁰ M. Mandić (2022). "Review of *Words in Space and Time: Historical Atlas of Language Politics in Modern Central Europe*, by T. Kamusella". *The Hungarian Historical Review*, 11(2), 481–484. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/27297217>.

⁶¹ C. McGann, Grady, T., & Hopkins, K. (2025). "Opening the Future, Author Profile: Mario Graña Taborelli". *Copim*. <https://copim.pubpub.org/pub/jurisdictional-battlefields>.

*witnessed with OA publishing) a fertile bed for innovation in publishing practices and outputs.*⁶²

As we have discussed above, Open Book Futures is working to financially support diverse, small publishers to guarantee a biodiverse future. Additionally, the project is committed to fostering a “fertile bed for innovation in publishing practices and outputs” by making sure that authors and presses are aware of, and able to utilise, the opportunities for experimentation and creativity enabled by OA book publishing.

In Year 1 of the OBF project, our **Experimental Publishing Group (WP6)** launched the **Experimental Publishing Compendium**, a valuable

*guide and reference for scholars, publishers, developers, librarians, and designers who want to challenge, push, and redefine the shape, form, and rationale of scholarly books. The compendium gathers and links tools, examples of experimental books, and experimental publishing practices with a focus on free and open-source software, platforms, and digital publishing tools that presses and authors can either use freely or can adapt to their research and publishing workflows.*⁶³

In Year 2, the Compendium has continued to expand, with WP6 adding 23 new tools, 9 new books and 2 new experimental publishing practices. One of the new “practices” added to the site this year was “Designing”.⁶⁴ The Compendium’s users now have access to this detailed guide to the role designing plays, and can play, in experimental book publishing and long-form digital projects, where “design is not reduced to aesthetics but an integral part of the story”. Alongside a wide-ranging theoretical discussion, the Compendium’s new entry also offers practical guidance. Practitioners are offered a carefully curated list of exemplar publications and open-source tools for designing their own experimental books and multimodal, dynamic digital works. The entry for designing also offers a helpful list of “considerations” to keep in mind, including a reminder to examine “how design decisions affect preservation from the get-go”. Updates to the Compendium—including this new post on “Designing”—were not a deliverable mandated in the initial OBF project bid, but WP6 recognise the value of volunteering time and effort to maintain and expand the resource.

⁶² L. Barnes and Gatti, R. (2019). “Biodiversity in Practice: Developing Community-Owned, Open Infrastructures to Unleash Open Access Publishing”. *ELPUB 2019 23rd edition of the International Conference on Electronic Publishing*: 3, [10.4000/proceedings.elpub.2019.21](https://doi.org/10.4000/proceedings.elpub.2019.21).

⁶³ J. Adema (2023). “Official Launch of the Experimental Publishing Compendium”. *Copim*.

<https://copim.pubpub.org/pub/compendium-launch>.

⁶⁴ <https://compendium.copim.ac.uk/practices/58>.

In addition to the Compendium, the Experimental Publishing Group has been disseminating research and advice on experimental publishing via workshops and seminars. In Year 2 of the project, the work package convened a series of “Experimental Publishing in Practice” seminars, which brought together authors and publishers with software and tool providers. The online seminars functioned as a valuable showcase for the open-source tools and platforms Manifold and Hypothes.is.⁶⁵ The project team understands that it can be daunting to engage in experimental publishing, and often authors aren’t aware of the opportunities available. The “Experimental Publishing in Practice” seminars therefore offered a supportive space to learn and ask questions, and the events were recorded and added to the Compendium for future consultation (cumulatively, the sessions had 100 registered attendees, and the recordings have been viewed over 150 times).⁶⁶ In addition to these seminars organised by WP6, the team also attended many external events in Year 2 as keynote speakers, panelists and presenters, for example sharing the project’s research and expertise at Oxford Forum of Open Scholarship 2025, the Global Summit on Diamond Open Access in Cape Town, and the 11th quadrennial joint conference of EASST and 4S.

The direct influence the project is having on practitioners is further evidenced by our 3 Experimental Publishing Pilots. At the end of Year 1 these pilot projects launched, and in Year 2 the Experimental Publishing Group (WP6) has been actively supporting the pilots to produce their own experimental publications and document the process. This work is evidenced by a series of reports and blog posts, which document the pilots’ progress whilst acting as lasting guides and inspiration to future creators.⁶⁷ To highlight one example here: one of the pilot projects is the ***Deep Maps: Blue Humanities*** project, which involves writing and designing a book with **Juncture**, a digital publishing tool developed by JSTOR Labs for visual essaying.⁶⁸ In addition to developing an experimental writing practice, *Deep Maps* also explores integrating an innovative open peer review process using GitHub (a platform designed for sharing and managing software coding). This experiment in open peer review is being recorded through documentation posts, which both record the practicalities of this process (for example sharing the instructions for replacing the traditional GitHub README file for software with a REVIEWME file) and examine more theoretical concerns, for example how to navigate the fact that GitHub users must log “issues” with code(/texts), but “the term ‘issue’ has unfortunate derogatory

⁶⁵ See https://compendium.copim.ac.uk/practice_seminars.

⁶⁶ See https://archive.org/details/Experimental_Publishing_Seminar_01 and https://archive.org/details/Experimental_Publishing_Seminar_02.

⁶⁷ See full list here: <https://copim.pubpub.org/experimental-publishing-group>.

⁶⁸ J. McHardy (2024). “Launch of Experimental Book Publishing Pilot Project ‘Deep Maps: Blue Humanities’”. *Copim*. <https://copim.pubpub.org/pub/launching-deep-maps>.

implications in the context of a peer review process”.⁶⁹ Reviewer guidelines and a code of conduct will be published in Year 3 to serve as examples for other projects interested in pursuing a similar model. In May 2025, the project will also host a hybrid event in Den Haag – “Markdown, Deep Dive”— which will be based, in part, on the *Deep Maps* pilot.

The *Deep Maps* pilot project is just one example of the way the Experimental Publishing Group is growing a community of experimental book publishing practice: a community through which bibliodiversity is fostered through sharing ideas and practical expertise. And it is important to note that this work is building on research conducted under the first COPIM project, drawing on guidelines and advice gathered under the COPIM pilot projects and documented in the Experimental Publishing Compendium.⁷⁰ In this way, the project is assembling a rich wealth of knowledge and expertise in innovative publishing, whilst our team both serves the academic community and learns from it.

5. “What networks and/or approaches are you currently utilising for dissemination? Are there further ways in which you plan to connect with others to share insights from your project?”

Social media

In Year 2 of the Open Book Futures project, we doubled our followers on Copim’s **LinkedIn** account through organic posting alone, and continued to grow our community on **Mastodon**.⁷¹ We also made the decision to cease posting on X (formerly Twitter) and opened a Copim **Bluesky** account.⁷² Like many others, our decision to leave X in 2024 was motivated by both ethical and practical reasons. The site has rapidly become a source of disinformation, racism and prejudice that we no longer felt comfortable being part of, and it is owned by a man helping to dismantle and defund academic research in the US. Moreover, X’s algorithm deprioritises links, thus making it unsuitable for sharing posts to events, blog posts and books (one of the primary ways in which we use social media). We now have over 1,400 followers on Bluesky, nearing the count we had on X before our departure. This fast-growing platform has proven invaluable for sharing our research and connecting with a broad community of academics, librarians, and publishers. Many of our work packages have their own growing social media

⁶⁹ S. Bowie, J. Louis Smith, and J. McHardy (2025). “Deep Maps: Experimenting with Peer Review.” *Copim*. <https://copim.pubpub.org/pub/deep-maps-peer-review>.

⁷⁰ See, for example, J. Adema (2023). “Experimenting with Workflows for Open Peer Review”. *Copim*. <https://doi.org/10.21428/785a6451.b86d0b83> and <https://compendium.copim.ac.uk/practices/63>.

⁷¹ <https://www.linkedin.com/company/100244286/admin/feed/posts/> and <https://hcommons.social/@copim>.

⁷² <https://bsky.app/profile/copim.bsky.social>.

accounts, which will continue to be used post-project: for example, the OBC’s Bluesky account has 1.2K followers, OtF’s has over 790, whilst Thoth’s has over 250.⁷³ In Year 3, we are hoping to develop our social media presence further and explore tools to make scheduling multiple posts and syncing posts across different platforms more efficient.

The project uses social media to engage with a community of academics, librarians, publishers, and infrastructure providers, respond to developments in the field, highlight new publications from the project and our partners, and promote upcoming events. For example, we used Copim’s social media accounts to promote the project’s hybrid event, “**Crisis in Higher Education and the Future of Diamond Open Access**” (19 September 2024), hosted at

Crisis in Higher Education event
(photography by [Catriona Gray](#))

Graphic shared on social media to promote the event

LSE.⁷⁴ Our outreach campaign resulted in the event’s webpage being our most visited PubPub post in Year 2, with over 1,800 views.⁷⁵ This translated into a well-attended event (with c. 250 registered to attend online, and c.70 in person). As we aim to do for all the outreach events we organise or attend, we made the presentation slides available to view and download on Zenodo (the slides from the “Crisis in Higher Education” event have collectively been downloaded over 160 times) and recordings with edited Closed Caption transcriptions were uploaded to both YouTube and Internet Archive (the videos from “Crisis in Higher Education” have collectively been viewed over 200 times).⁷⁶ Finally, we published a blog post summarising the LSE event’s talks, answering questions we were unable to address on the night, and reflecting on the discussion and common links between the panel’s presentations.⁷⁷ Many useful

⁷³ <https://bsky.app/profile/openbookcollective.bsky.social>, <https://bsky.app/profile/openingthefuture.bsky.social>, <https://bsky.app/profile/thoth-metadata.bsky.social>. Several of these initiatives also have accounts on Mastodon and LinkedIn.

⁷⁴ An example social media post advertising the event, with a custom designed graphic: <https://bsky.app/profile/copim.bsky.social/post/3l3arpa6shv2x>.

⁷⁵ Copim Community. (2024). “Crisis in higher education and the future of Diamond open access”. *Copim*. <https://copim.pubpub.org/pub/futureofdiamond>.

⁷⁶ Copim Community (2024). “Catch up with: ‘Crisis in higher education and the future of Diamond open access’”. *Copim*. <https://copim.pubpub.org/pub/catch-up-future-of-diamond>.

⁷⁷ See above.

conversations and partnerships began or were strengthened through the event, for example staff from the Francis Crick Institute attended, and the institute later became a supporting members of the OBC.⁷⁸

The LSE event exemplifies the careful way in which the project's outreach team maximises the impact of the events we organise and attend: widening participation through creative and active online promotion, increasing access through hybrid hosting, and then allowing asynchronous engagement by releasing materials, recordings and published reflections after the event. In Year 3 of the project, we hope to employ these strategies when hosting a 2-day hybrid conference in London, which will bring together various stakeholders to discuss the future of OA books, as we look ahead to life after the Open Book Futures project.

⁷⁸ "The Open Book Collective Welcomes the Francis Crick Institute Library". (2025). *OBC Information Hub*. <https://openbookcollective.pubpub.org/pub/the-open-book-collective-welcomes-the-francis-crick-institute-library>.

Exhibition stands, posters, presentations, workshops and webinars

ACRL

UKSG

Charleston

In Year 2, the Open Book Futures team participated as organisers, delegates, panelists and presenters at over 70 events. A full list of these is made public on our PubPub site and in the appendix to this report.⁷⁹ These conferences, webinars and workshops allowed us to connect with networks around the world: reaching academics, librarians and publishers in the UK, Europe, Africa, US and Latin America. In Year 2, exhibition stands have proved a particularly successful method for disseminating our research and connecting with stakeholders. The project (often in collaboration with a partner) has hosted exhibition stands at **Frankfurt Book Fair**, **Guadalajara International Book Fair**, **Charleston Conference (USA)**, **ACRL** and **UKSG**. At these major events in our field, the project's exhibition space functioned as an important networking space: a hub where members of different organisations involved in OA publishing and open infrastructures met and exchanged ideas. Our exhibition stands and tables were also a place for OA advocates (and sceptics!) to learn more, to pick up leaflets and merchandise, and to ask for advice on their own projects.

Through exhibition stands, we disseminated our research, engaged with key audience groups and increased our work's visibility in the field. Moreover, many important in-person conversations began and progressed at these events: leading directly to new subscriptions from libraries, important progress on consortia deals, and applications from potential new member presses for OBC and OtF. For example, at Frankfurt Book Fair, Thoth met **Mohr Siebeck**, a medium-sized German publisher active in Legal Studies. During conversations in Frankfurt, the Thoth team demonstrated the benefits of signing up to the Thoth Plus dissemination service. An agreement was signed in mid-December, and Thoth is currently working to get Mohr Siebeck's catalogue ingested ready to start dissemination of their OA books soon.

⁷⁹ L. Barnes (2023). "Open Book Futures: Diary of events". *Copim*. <https://copim.pubpub.org/pub/open-book-futures-outreach>.

Poster presentations, conference contributions and webinars allowed the project team to share our research and advocate for more equitable OA book publishing. Importantly, this outreach work has also been an opportunity to collaborate and work with other partners. For example, in September 2024, members of the project team attended the **Paris Conference on Open Research Information**, and delivered a presentation entitled: “Leveraging the power of open research information to foster open collaboration towards an equitable not-for-profit ecosystem for Open Access books”. The presentation was co-authored and showcased the work of multiple infrastructures (OBC, DOAB, OAPEN, Thoth and PKP), highlighting the ways these organisations are collaborating to improve OA book publishing. The slides for this presentation are available to download from Zenodo, where they have been viewed over 1,250 times, and downloaded over 200 times.⁸⁰

In a further collaborative outreach effort, the project coordinated a joint poster presentation—“No open access without open infrastructure”—which was award-winning when delivered at **Open-Access-Tage** in September 2024.⁸¹ The poster was produced in collaboration with “five not-for-profit infrastructures with shared values for OA books”, and the project team translated the poster into four languages (English, Spanish, German and Brazilian-Portuguese) to enhance its dissemination. The poster has been viewed 1,200+ times on Zenodo and been downloaded 350+ times: one of the most popular items we made available under a CC-BY License on Zenodo this year. We edited the poster design to produce a run of flyers which were first distributed at the UKSG conference and that will be used in Year 3 of the project as well.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12263353>

Publications

In Year 2, we published over 60 PubPub posts, and clocked up over 60,000 page views (24,000 more than in Year 1).⁸² Our second most read post on the Copim PubPub in Year 2 was “Building assessment criteria for collection development policies: a community resource”.⁸³ This post wasn’t a planned deliverable for the project, but was instead written in response to an

⁸⁰ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13823880>.

⁸¹ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12263353>.

⁸² PubPub’s method of collecting these statistics changed in April 2024, which may explain some of this increase.

⁸³ A. Hughes, Barnes, L., Grady, T., & Hopkins, K. (2024). “Building assessment criteria for collection development policies: a community resource”. *Copim*. <https://doi.org/10.21428/785a6451.b7f99f49>.

emerging need for guidance in this area. As the authors describe in their introduction to the post:

At a 2023 webinar co-organised by Jisc and the Open Access Books Network (OABN), there was particular interest in an evaluation template used by the University of St. Andrews (USTAN) to assess and manage their read-and-publish deals. [...] Fast-forward to 2024 when Jisc and the OABN held a follow-up workshop to surface practical tips for libraries to consider when evaluating collective funding models for open access books and developing their own institutional policies. The themes that emerged from these discussions form the basis of the ‘model text’ and suggestions below. We hope that libraries will take what they need from this community resource and use it to create their own assessment rubrics.

The high viewing and downloading figures the post has garnered since publication suggest that the “model text” has struck a chord with our audience. In this way, this publication exemplifies the way the project listens to its stakeholders and responds to their needs: creating the resources and publishing the advice and research that librarians, publishers and academics are requesting.

The project has also published papers outside of our PubPub documentation site, often in response to developments in the OA landscape and feedback from the networks we engage with. This year, Janneke Adema published a journal article discussing the combinatorial books pilot developed under the COPIM project, which has now grown into a book series at OHP.⁸⁴ Tom Grady, Elaine Sykes and Martin Eve, published an article in *UKSG Journal*, in which they argue that new UKRI and REF OA books policies now make it more important than ever to support collective, non-BPC funding models.⁸⁵ The piece (read over 2,000 times in its first 2 months) was formulated following a well-attended and much-praised breakout session on the subject at the UKSG conference in 2024; a session which Grady and Skyes were then invited to deliver again as a UKSG webinar in October 2024 and then again at the campus of the University of York in 2025.⁸⁶ Over 350 people registered to attend the online webinar. Again, this is an example of how our most effective dissemination emerges from connections to

⁸⁴ J. Adema (2024). “Experimental Publishing as Collective Struggle. Providing Imaginaries for Posthumanist Knowledge Production”. Special Issue *Publishing After Progress* guest-edited by R. Kiesewetter. *Culture Machine*. Vol. 23. <https://culturemachine.net/vol-23-publishing-after-progress/adema-experimental-publishing-collective-struggle/>.

⁸⁵ T. Grady, Sykes, E. and Eve, M.P. (2025) “How can we achieve sustainable funding for open access books?”, *Insights: the UKSG journal*, 38(1), p. 4. <https://doi.org/10.1629/uksg.673>.

⁸⁶ Event page for webinar: <https://www.uksg.org/events/webinar-getting-out-from-the-back-of-the-sofa/>.

networks of stakeholders, and in response to the issues and themes that are of interest to those working in the field.

In Year 3 of the project, we will launch a new documentation site, which will use WordPress rather than **Knowledge Futures' PubPub platform**. This decision was prompted by a change in policy at PubPub's host organisation (Knowledge Futures), which will see the introduction of an expensive yearly hosting fee. We articulated many of our concerns with this change in a blog post, which Knowledge Futures acknowledged as a thoughtful and helpful critique in some of their own communications with users, and which was highlighted by attendees at the ROAC conference in Cambridge (April 2025) as a significant intervention on the topic.⁸⁷ In the absence of a workaround at Knowledge Futures, we decided to develop an open-source **WordPress** theme, which will allow us to continue publishing documentation posts on a new site without PubPub's new annual hosting fees. We will be sharing the WordPress theme on GitHub, documenting our migration, and updating the community on our decision via a new blog post, which will be published early in Year 3 of the project.

Copim Compass

In Year 2 of the project, we launched **Copim Compass**, an online information hub that will become an increasingly important platform for us to record and disseminate our team's expertise.⁸⁸ We plan for the site to grow to host a suite of toolkits and resources advocating for, and advising on, equitable, community-led open access publishing. One of the site's first major contributions is a toolkit produced by **Opening the Future (WP3)**.⁸⁹ Using the toolkit's resources, a publisher could implement and run the Opening the Future model at their own press. The toolkit is arranged into a series of easily digestible sections, offering a comprehensive guide to the entire set-up process, as well as the requirements of maintaining and growing the model. We have also included testimonials from the publishers currently using Opening the Future, and have shared documentation of costs and potential revenue. This toolkit is an important resource for presses interested in funding their OA frontlist equitably. It is also an important manifestation of our project's commitment to making OA book publishing more transparent, open and trust-worthy. Copim Compass is a way for us to share and document our knowledge and practical experience to the benefit of the wider publishing ecosystem.

⁸⁷ J. Adema, Barnes, L., Bowie, S., McGann, C., & Steiner, T. (2024). "Copim's thoughts on the changes announced at PubPub". *Copim*. <https://doi.org/10.21428/785a6451.c64e3c31>. See <https://www.knowledgefutures.org/updates/platform-update-sept-24/> for one citation of our post.

⁸⁸ <https://compass.copim.ac.uk/>.

⁸⁹ <https://compass.copim.ac.uk/books/06-opening-the-future-introduction-and-description>.

To inform the development of Copim Compass, we conducted an initial scoping survey, in which we analysed existing online information on OA publishing, and the various websites and guides targeting scholars, librarians and publishers. This extensive scoping report received feedback from several of our partners (including **SPARC EU** and **Lyrasis**), and has been published on Zenodo, where it has been periodically updated to include new resources and downloaded over 300 times.⁹⁰ Our scoping research revealed that a valuable contribution to the field would be a “guide of guides”: a curated list of the many valuable resources and sources that offer advice on publishing OA books. We also identified a need for a curated list of case studies from authors, libraries and publishers, which could offer ‘real world’ examples of OA book publishing and its benefits. At the end of Year 2, we launched these exciting new features, and are highlighting them through a targeted outreach campaign on social media and via mailing lists.⁹¹ We also highlighted Copim Compass in a recent interview with Research Professional News, which we hope will result in an article highlighting some of our project’s work.

In Year 3, Copim Compass will also become home to an Accessibility tool and knowledge base, designed to help publishers assess their maturity when it comes to accessibility, adapt their workflows to meet and exceed standards, and evidence their compliance and/or “planned route to compliance” in the ways stakeholders require. Our **Accessibility Work Package [WP5]**, launched in Year 2, has held a series of one-to-one knowledge-exchange consultations with 7 small- to medium-sized publishers, with further meetings planned for Year 3. Thanks to a “snow-balling” approach, each consultation has been informed by the previous interview, as our researchers build a more comprehensive understanding of the workflows and challenges facing small publishers when it comes to OA ebook accessibility. WP5 is finalising an interim blog post summarising some of the initial findings from these consultations.⁹² And, in Year 3, WP5 will release a knowledge base of guidance for publishers, alongside publisher-focused tools to assist with self-assessment, maturity modelling and workflow adaptation. The project team will be supporting a selection of small publishers to implement the guidance and tools at their presses. By the end of the project,

⁹⁰ K. Hopkins & Hughes, A. (2024). “Open Book Futures InfoHub scoping report”. *Zenodo*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13842916>.

⁹¹ See <https://compass.copim.ac.uk/books/02-open-access-book-publishing-a-comprehensive-overview-of-resources>; <https://compass.copim.ac.uk/books/03-author-success-stories>; and <https://compass.copim.ac.uk/books/04-library-success-stories>.

⁹² J. Fitzpatrick & Findanis, J. (2025). “Accessibility standard implementation and OA publishers”. *Copim*. <https://copim.pubpub.org/pub/accessibility-publishers>

we will have significantly increased the ability for publishers to create accessible OA ebooks, ensuring that “open access” books are open to as many readers as possible.

African OA network building

In Year 2 of the project, we have continued to disseminate our research to international audiences, connecting with networks of scholars, librarians and publishers in Europe, the USA and Latin America. As we noted in our Year 1 report, the team is also committed to helping to connect and support OA book networks in Africa. The Open Book Futures team continued this work in Year 2 of the project. In December 2024, we co-hosted a workshop at the **2nd Global Summit on Diamond OA at Cape Town University**. The 2-day workshop, organised in partnership with the **Association of African Universities**, was entitled: “Open Monograph Publishing: Towards Sustainable Open Access Book Publishing in the Global South Context”. The workshop was designed to be highly collaborative, with contributions from members of **African Minds, Experimental Publishing Group (WP6), the Directory of Open Access Books/OAPEN, Lancaster University, the Open Book Collective, Open Book Publishers, the Public Knowledge Project, punctum books, Thoth Open Metadata, University of Cape Town Libraries and University of Cape Town Press**. The programme also included presentations from librarians and academics based at **Addis Ababa University, Chinhoyi University of Technology, Ghana University and University of the Western Cape**, who each shared their own experiences of developing OA policies. Full details of the workshop, including all slides, were made available on our website, so that those unable to attend could still share in the resources.⁹³

The Cape Town workshop was an important opportunity for the project to make connections, disseminate our research, and learn more about OA publishing in Africa. It was attended by delegates from a wide variety of countries, including Angola, Botswana, Ethiopia, Ghana, Nigeria, Senegal, South Africa, Tunisia, Zambia and Zimbabwe. In this way, it was an event that enabled librarians, publishers and scholars working within African contexts to meet, network and collaborate. A need for more of these opportunities was highlighted at a previous workshop that the project co-organised at the University of Cape Town in February 2024.⁹⁴ At this earlier workshop, attendees expressed a desire for greater collaboration and skill-sharing within the African continent, and it was noted that there is currently no map or resource

⁹³ Open Book Collective (2024). “Open Monograph Publishing: A workshop at the 2nd Global Summit on Diamond OA”. *OBC Information Hub*. <https://doi.org/10.21428/41ca814e.02291384>.

⁹⁴ J. Fathallah & Deville, J. (2024). “Towards Sustainable Open Access Book Publishing in the African Context: Workshop Programme, Slides & Resources”. *OBC Information Hub*. <https://doi.org/10.21428/41ca814e.c8fbbc53>.

recording the various OA book initiatives and stakeholders in Africa, which leads to uncoordinated working and labour duplication. Since that event, members of the Open Book Futures team have been exploring how to support this mapping work, and have begun gathering initial data. The workshop in December 2024 allowed us to take that work further, and many participants were keen to help and join a working group to support the endeavour. An inaugural meeting of this African OA Books working group was held in April 2025, and the project team will continue to support this network-building into Year 3 of the project. Members of the project team also helped contacts in Africa to submit a funding bid to a recent Invest in Open Infrastructures grant call, which we expect to learn the outcome of in Year 3.

6. “Please provide a case study for your project that highlights the impact of your project.”

Getting OA books “out there in the world”

Early on in Year 2 of the project, the **Open Book Collective (WP2)** published an interview with the author Matthew Cheney.⁹⁵ Cheney’s book, *About That Life: Barry Lopez and the Art of Community* (2023) was published by one of the OBC’s Members, **punctum books** (an independent queer- and scholar-led, community-formed, and peer-reviewed OA publisher, which is also one of the project’s consortium members). In the interview, Cheney notes that he was initially skeptical about OA book publishing, but that his experience of publishing with punctum helped to change his mind:

Few of us in academia are going to get rich off our writing, but we ought to be able to experience a supportive publishing process that will offer the world access to our work. Sadly, that’s not the norm ... except with folks like punctum.

In the interview, Cheney particularly highlights the beneficial exposure that comes from publishing OA, and the increased readership and visibility he had noticed:

The most wonderful thing about the reception of About That Life is that the book is clearly out there in the world. People have told me they’ve recommended it to students or assigned pieces in class, people who are interested in a variety of subjects have found it via keyword searches, people who have no connection to academia have looked

⁹⁵ L. Onalee Snyder (2024). “Leveraging the strengths of teaching-first institutions to support OA book publishing: An interview with Matthew Cheney”. *Copim*. <https://copim.pubpub.org/pub/leveraging-the-strengths-of-teaching-first-institutions-to-support-oa-book-publishing-an-interview-with-matthew-cheney>.

at it. This is not true of any of the work I've had stuck behind paywalls or sold for ridiculous cover prices.

Publishing open access gives authors like Cheney an unparalleled opportunity get their research “out there in the world”, in a way that benefits them, their institution, students, academics and the wider public. In this case study, we'd like to highlight some of the ways our project is having an impact by making sure OA books get “out there in the world” in the most effective way, and that they **stay** “out there” and available to readers for as long as possible.

The key to making sure that OA works are discoverable “via keyword searches”, and in library catalogues and ebook platforms, is good metadata and access to dissemination routes. Improving OA book metadata and dissemination is a major way in which the Open Book Futures project is having a direct beneficial impact on authors, publishers and readers. **Thoth Open Metadata (WP4)** is now empowering over 60 publishers to generate crucial high-quality metadata records for the books and chapters they publish and disseminate to readers. Thoth's publishers are located around the world, including in Argentina, Austria, Canada, Cuba, Germany, Mexico, South Africa, Spain and the USA. These publishers are supported by the Thoth platform to create high-quality metadata records, formatted to meet multiple industry specifications, thereby ensuring compatibility and interoperability across different systems and platforms. Here, it is worth mentioning that the funds received via library support are crucial to supporting bibliodiversity in open access book publishing, by enabling Thoth to provide dissemination services for publishers from less-advantaged regions that are not able to cover the service fees. The provision of Thoth's services is helping to improve the visibility of publishers' valuable contributions to the scholarly records. This is particularly relevant for publishers and researchers from less-advantaged regions that risk remaining unnoticed due to not having the means to fully participate in an ecosystem that is dominated by aggregators and protocols often run by companies from the Global North.

High-quality metadata means that a book like Cheney's, published at punctum—a publisher using Thoth—has the potential to be disseminated to more than a dozen platforms, including **EBSCO Host, Project MUSE, OAPEN, Google Books** and **JSTOR**, where it can then be discovered and accessed by readers.⁹⁶ On OAPEN's platform alone, Cheney's book has been downloaded over 200 times.⁹⁷ As co-director of punctum, Vincent van Gerven Oei, noted recently, there are serious challenges involved in extrapolating meaningful usage metrics

⁹⁶ <https://thoth.pub/books/ca2f9ad1-a5fd-45b6-a662-4991cf1767a3>.

⁹⁷ <https://www.jstor.org/stable/jj.2354008> and <https://library.oapen.org/handle/20.500.12657/62262>.

from ebook platforms, and “making open access ebook usage data both interoperable and interpretable still has a long way to go”.⁹⁸ However, as van Gerven Oei reports, visualisation of usage data is something Thoth is actively working on in collaboration with OPERAS. In Year 3 of the project, and beyond, Thoth will be exploring how best to offer publisher reports and website widgets that will give authors like Cheney accurate figures that evidence the fact that their OA book is “out there in the world”: metrics that we know are important for publishers and academics when making a case for OA and their own impact on the field.

Importantly, the Open Book Futures team is also working to make sure that the OA books published by authors are “out there” for as long as possible, meaning that they are securely archived and available for future generations of researchers. The project’s **Archiving and Preservation working group [WP7]** are contributing to efforts to ensure long-term preservation of open access content, this has included the creation of new archiving criteria targeted specifically for open access content, supplementing existing criteria which focused on restricted access content.⁹⁹ In partnership with Thoth, WP7 has launched the **Thoth Open Archiving Network [TOAN]**, a vital safeguard that allows publishers to automatically archive their publications in multiple repository locations, thereby filling a major gap in preservation infrastructure and significantly simplifying publisher workloads.¹⁰⁰ Thanks to its inclusion in TOAN, Cheney’s book, for example, is now archived in the Internet Archive and Cambridge University Library’s Dspace repository, as part of a pilot study.¹⁰¹

We have recently published a new blog post documenting some of the complex work involved in building this collaboration with Cambridge University Library.¹⁰² In Year 3, we will publish a further report on some of the unforeseen benefits of this repository pilot. This work on Dspace/SWORD has helped Thoth to integrate better with OAPEN (who also use Dspace) and Thoth is aiming to reutilise the code developed for api delivery to DSpace and Figshare repositories to introduce a customised content delivery service for university libraries. Work on the pilots also brought to light some bugs within the protocols and software, which WP7 has now fixed. Fixing these bugs, documenting the development process, and sharing the resulting

⁹⁸ V. W. J. van Gerven Oei (2025). “An Update on punctum books Usage Data: Interoperability, Interpretability, and AI”. *Punctum Books*. <https://doi.org/10.21428/ae6a44a6.52f495bc>.

⁹⁹ For more detail see, R. Higman, Cole, G., Gatti, R., Arias, J., Steiner, T., Stokes, P., Wheatley, P., Barnes, M., & McGann, C. (2025). “Putting the ‘Open’ in ‘Thoth Open Archiving Network’”. *Copim*. <https://doi.org/10.21428/785a6451.76e96572>.

¹⁰⁰ <https://thoth.pub/solutions/archiving>.

¹⁰¹ <https://archive.org/details/ca2f9ad1-a5fd-45b6-a662-4991cf1767a3> and <https://thoth-arch.lib.cam.ac.uk/items/a2361c42-3e49-4c75-9c17-92a2fad048ee>.

¹⁰² R. Higman & Martínez-García, A. (2025). “Archiving with Cambridge University Library”. *Copim*. <https://copim.pub/pub/archiving-cambridge-university-library>.

code, has clear benefits for the community of present and future users of Dspace and SWORD protocol, demonstrating the benefits of open-source licensing.

In Year 3 of the project, WP7 and Thoth will continue to develop and enhance TOAN, making sure that principles of openness are integral to every aspect of its preservation workflows. As the project team explain, “many existing archiving solutions are often geared towards handling copyrighted items, and therefore do not make content openly available until this is deemed necessary”.¹⁰³ However, TOAN will centre its efforts around making archived content that is also fully public from point of deposit (increasing dissemination and visibility of born OA works like Cheney’s). The TOAN team will also look to record checksums within Thoth’s metadata schema, allowing open and easy verification of content, and the network’s documentation will be clear about how content is checked and maintained. This gives authors a rare level of security: knowing that their work is being archived and protected in a sustainable, effective and verifiable way, which in turn will give them the confidence that they are meeting the preservation requirements frequently set out in grant funding and OA publishing mandates.

In Year 2, Thoth also continued to develop their white-label website solution, which is a further way in which our project is having a beneficial impact on publishers, authors and readers by helping OA books to get “out there”. Thoth’s white-label, reusable website template is based on Strapi CMS, making it perfect for interoperability and easy scalability. It’s an ideal solution for open access book publishers, consortia or other organisations managing open access book catalogues. Some of the many positive impacts from switching to the white-label solution include gaining an advanced integrated catalogue search with customizable filters, an enhanced user experience (with in-built landing pages for book and chapters alike), and metrics widget integration, allowing readers, authors and publishers to easily see usage statistics for a work.¹⁰⁴

In Year 2 of the project, Thoth supported **NUPs [Dutch University Presses]** to pilot the white-label solution for its website and OA book catalogue. NUPs is a consortium of 6 open access academic publishers, and—thanks to Thoth—its website now hosts a catalogue of books published by its members.¹⁰⁵ Users can explore the available books and download metadata records in multiple formats, enabling dissemination and integration with myriad platforms. This new experimental consortial catalogue has been so successful that NUPs have now applied to their national funder for a grant to support more infrastructure work, citing the

¹⁰³ R. Higman, Cole, G., Gatti, R., Arias, J., Steiner, T., Stokes, P., Wheatley, P., Barnes, M., & McGann, C. (2025). “Putting the ‘Open’ in ‘Thoth Open Archiving Network’”. *Copim*. <https://doi.org/10.21428/785a6451.76e96572>.

¹⁰⁴ R. Higman & Martínez-García, A. (2025). “Archiving with Cambridge University Library”. *Copim*. <https://copim.pubpub.org/pub/archiving-cambridge-university-library>.

¹⁰⁵ <https://nups.thoth.pub/>.

catalogue as a first step in the process. In Year 3, we hope that a successful outcome of this grant application will enable more collaboration between Thoth and the NUPs. Thoth are also in discussion with other consortia and organisations to host website and catalogue solutions, including with the German university publishers working group of **AG Universitätsverlage**, and **SciELO Books**. A variety of individual presses have also expressed interest, for example **mediastudies.press** noted in its Annual Report that “given developments at Knowledge Futures, the PubPub maker, we are considering a move away from the platform, to a white-label site offered by Thoth”..¹⁰⁶

This summary of recent work at Thoth helps to exemplify how our project is innovating and collaborating in order to get OA long-form research “out there in the world” for the benefit of readers, authors and their institutions. To illustrate this further, we asked one of Thoth’s users [Scottish Universities Press] to share more about the impact Thoth has had on the way they work...

A publisher’s perspective: Scottish Universities Press and Thoth Open Metadata

The OBF project team asked Dominique Walker to tell us more about how Thoth is working with Scottish Universities Press (SUP):

Scottish Universities Press (SUP) is a new fully open access press that is managed by 20 academic libraries across Scotland and Northern Ireland, through the Scottish Confederation of University and Research Libraries (SCURL). SUP launched in October 2024 and to date we have published two books, Conversations with Tim Ingold and Digital editing and publishing in the twenty-first century..¹⁰⁷ The metadata for both titles has been distributed through Thoth..¹⁰⁸

As a library-led press, discoverability and high-quality metadata were a priority for us from the start. While our member libraries help us create MARC records, we did not have any technical expertise when it comes to other metadata types, such as ONIX. We also wanted to make sure that our books were available on the platforms our authors would expect, and to ensure that the open access book reached as wide an audience as possible. We only have 2 FTE working on the Press, so another challenge we faced was

¹⁰⁶ Mediastudies.press (2024). “2024 Annual Report”. <https://msp-docs.org/annual-reports/2024+Annual+Report>.

¹⁰⁷ <https://books.sup.ac.uk/sup/catalog/book/sup-9781917341028> & <https://books.sup.ac.uk/sup/catalog/book/sup-9781917341073>.

¹⁰⁸ <https://thoth.pub/books/bcfa11f4-b749-40a0-b91e-6b67b7c8e0b4> & <https://thoth.pub/books/d99764cf-2d40-4722-8cea-ff791e822633>.

the amount of time it would take to manage our metadata, creating different formats and submitting to lots of different platforms in lots of different ways!

We first heard of Thoth at a workshop back in 2022 in the very early days of setting up the press. As a not-for-profit press we were immediately interested as Thoth is also not-for-profit with a similar ethos around openness. We subsequently signed up to start using the free version of Thoth in October 2023 as we worked on our first book.

Entering the data was very straightforward and the system is really intuitive. Any teething problems were quickly sorted, for example when I downloaded the ONIX record for the first time the product availability was set to 'Code 99 - contact supplier' which caused issues with submitting the data to BDS. When I reported this, it was amended almost immediately, meaning I could quickly download the ONIX record for our first book and send it across to Nielsen and BDS, without having to fill out individual forms or create spreadsheets.

We quickly decided to sign up to Thoth Plus once launched. It was an easy decision for us, the cost was very reasonable for the amount of time it would save, plus it included other benefits such as Crossref and OAPEN membership. The onboarding experience was very straightforward, with clear documentation and great support from Thoth staff, Hannah and Toby.

There are clear benefits for our workflow. We only need to enter the data once and when I make the book 'active' the data is immediately sent to Crossref and the DOIs resolve almost straight away. Thoth staff then start working on distributing the book in the background while SUP staff can get on with other tasks.

There are also benefits for our authors. As one of the authors of Conversations with Tim Ingold, Diego Maria Malara, pointed out in a recent blog post, 'It is one thing to publish the work; quite another thing to ensure that the public beyond the narrow academic community is even aware of the work's existence and can engage with it.'¹⁰⁹

Lastly, we have been providing feedback on the new Thoth plugin for OMP. This tool will eventually mean that I simply enter the data for an SUP book into OMP and the data is carried across to Thoth and distributed on our behalf, saving even more time.

¹⁰⁹ "Breaking down borders between academia and the rest of the world: A conversation with Tim Ingold and his co-authors", <https://www.sup.ac.uk/news/tim-ingold-blog-post>.

Our experience of working with Thoth has been incredibly positive, the team are very supportive and keen to improve the system for the benefit of the whole scholarly community.

7. “Please provide any lessons learnt, feedback for Research England, or other key information which is not already covered by the information in this report.”

Since the OBF project began, there have been several major developments in OA book policy in the UK. In Jan 2024, UKRI launched an OA books mandate for its grant recipients, and in Aug 2024 it was announced that “an open access requirement for submission of longform outputs will be in place for the next [REF] assessment exercise, with implementation from 1 January 2029”.¹¹⁰ These new mandates have had, and will continue to have, a significant impact on the UK’s HE sector and the publishing industry. These policy decisions also have an impact around the world: nations develop their own OA policies by monitoring and referencing those in place elsewhere, and the globalised workflows and networks involved in academia and publishing mean that UK-based decisions have consequences for the entire book supply chain and HE sector. These new mandates have turned the spotlight on OA books in the UK, and have highlighted the many inequities, infrastructure gaps and author concerns that urgently require redress. More than ever before, academics, librarians and publishers stand to benefit from the insights and experience that the OBF project team has been building over the past 5 years.

The project team stands ready to assist funders and policy-makers with the design and implementation of OA mandates, and is eager to be a valuable asset when communicating with stakeholders. We have been doing some of this work already. Work package lead, Janneke Adema, shared her knowledge of experimental and community-led OA publishing with a study commissioned by UKRI. Adema’s enthusiastic advocacy for publishing OA was published as a case study for other academics, helping to assuage some fears about the new UKRI funder mandate for OA monographs by promoting the possibilities of OA publication and highlighting the equitable, community-led routes to publication available.¹¹¹ Other members of the team were also consulted as part of UKRI’s study, sharing insights into the equitable and community-led models for OA book publishing showcased by the OBF project. The project’s work was

¹¹⁰ See <https://www.ukri.org/news/update-on-ukri-open-access-policy-and-fund-for-books/> and <https://2029.ref.ac.uk/news/early-decisions-made-on-ref-2029-open-access-policy/>.

¹¹¹ UK Research and Innovation. (2025). “Researchers’ experience of publishing academic books open access”. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13944972>.

highlighted several times in the study’s key reports.¹¹² For example, the report noted that “Further integration of Thoth in the supply chain would be beneficial” and publishers seeking to transition to OA were advised to “consider using the Thoth platform, which is optimized for OA”. Publishers were also directed towards “the Open Book Collective, which is a platform for bringing libraries and publishers together”, as well as Copim’s extensive work on developing “recommendations for how to set up a sustainable governance structure that ensures editorial independence, diverse participation, and sustainable financing without the threat of a commercial buyout”.

The Open Book Futures team are often invited to speak and comment on the issues raised by new OA mandates in the UK, and have—through extensive research and practical, hands-on experience—developed a deep understanding of what is needed to ready the sector. We mention this work here by way of invitation. We would welcome the opportunity to work with Research England, UKRI, Arcadia, and any other funders and policy-makers in the UK or abroad, on their OA mandates.

8. Year 2 expenditure and forecasted expenditure in Year 3

Following the Year 1 funding report, the project management team amended the project’s Year 2 & Year 3 budgets to incorporate under/over-spend from Year 1, and to accommodate virements across budget categories and partner budgets. This reconfigured budget was approved by the funders in the Summer of 2024, and is reflected in the financial reporting supplied as part of this Year 2 report.

Overall, the reconfigured budget is meeting the needs of the project, and we spent 86% of our total Year 2 budget, and are forecasting only a small amount of underspend in Year 3. The project plans to use much of the Year 2 underspend in Year 3 to support work in our final year. However, to ensure that we are using the budget in ways that are most beneficial for meeting and exceeding our targets, we will be preparing a further virements proposal for the funders to review in June 2025.

Staff

Percentage of Year 2 Budget spent: 95%

¹¹² “Supporting learned society, subject association, and smaller specialist publishers to transition to open access book publishing (SPA OPS 4.0 project)”. <https://zenodo.org/records/14679068?> and “How to Begin the OA Transition: a guide for smaller and specialist publishers”. <https://zenodo.org/records/14679095>.

Events & Travel

Percentage of Year 2 budget spent: Events (60%) + Travel (73%)

Consultancy

Percentage of Year 2 Budget spent: 55%

Equipment

Percentage of Year 2 Budget spent: 93%

9. Appendix

9.1 Grant progress: success criteria & schedule

	Year 1	Year 2	Year 3
Total number of Success criteria	24	31	21
Total completed	52		
Total "In progress-delayed"	5		

Work package	Success criteria	Success criteria description	Target completion date	Status	Actual outcome
WP2: Open Book Collective					
Year 1					
2. OBC	(A2.1) Increase OBC revenue	(D2.1a) £250,000 revenue generated in Year 1	May-24	Completed	Success criteria exceeded by ca. 25%+. By the end of Apr 2024, the OBC's contracted subscription revenue was ca. GBP 316,000, from 61 supporting institutions.
2. OBC	See above	(D2.1b) At least 3 new publisher/service provider sign-ups (Year 1)	May-24	Completed	3 new publishers signed-up: University of Westminster Press, Leuven University Press and University of London Press all launched on the OBC on 5 Feb 2024. See press release: "Three university presses join the Open Book Collective". (Feb 2024). <i>OBC Information Hub</i> . https://doi.org/10.21428/41ca814e.3fc4b79b See A2.6 (a Year 2 success criteria) for details of further sign-ups already in progress.
2. OBC	(A2.2) At least 2 library outreach	(D2.2) At least 2 library outreach events	May-24	Completed	Success criteria exceeded, with multiple outreach events completed in Year 1, including:

<p>events organised in the UK (with JISC, RLUK, SCURL) and US (with Lyrisis), promoting OBC work</p>	<p>completed and documented</p>	<p>Library Outreach Event 1 (UK) Title: Open Access Week 2023: Open Access Books: Panel Discussion. Date: 26 Oct 2023 Location: online Participating organisations: Organised by University of Derby & University of Essex. No. of participants: 40 Recording: "Open Access Week 2023 - Open Access books: Panel discussion". (Jan 2024). DerbyUni Library. <i>YouTube</i>. https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=k4YiVSqfIRY (45+ views) Further documentation of event: Deville, J., Sanders, K., & Corazza, F. (Feb 2024). "What a difference a year makes: An update on the Open Book Collective's activities over the past 12 months". <i>OBC Information Hub</i>. https://doi.org/10.21428/41ca814e.3db1e0a1</p> <p>Library Outreach Event 2 (UK) Title: Copim Community exhibition stand, evening social event & paper presentations Date: 8-10 Apr 2024 Location: UKSG 2024, Glasgow Further documentation of event: See X thread for a record of Copim Community's participation: https://x.com/Copim_community/status/1773318375239754211 <u>Planned follow up: Tom Grady & Elaine Sykes have been invited to deliver their very successful presentation again, as a recorded webinar hosted by UKSG.</u></p> <p>Library Outreach Event 3 (US) Title: Open Book Collective: Collective Paths Toward an Open and Sustainable Ecosystem for Monographs Date: 12 Dec 2023 Location: CNI conference, Washington Participating organisations: University of California, Santa Barbara No. of participants: 50 Recording: "Open Book Collective: Collective paths toward an open and sustainable ecosystem for monographs". (Jan 2024). CNI: Coalition for Networked Information. <i>YouTube</i>. https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=obWzE2_uNk8 (80+ views) Further documentation of event: Deville, J., Sanders, K., & Corazza, F. (Feb 2024). "What a difference a year makes: An update on the Open</p>
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					<p>Book Collective's activities over the past 12 months". <i>OBC Information Hub</i>. https://doi.org/10.21428/41ca814e.3db1e0a1</p> <p>Library Outreach Event 4 (US) Title: Presence at the Charleston Conference (in-person and online) Presentation title: A community-led future for OA books: How can new OA infrastructures enable libraries to support "scaling small" in scholarly publishing? Poster title: Closing the Knowledge Gap: Improving Open Access Knowledge Sharing between Publishers, Authors, and Libraries Date: 27 Nov 2023 (presentation); 6 Nov-1 Dec 2023 (poster) Location: Charleston Conference Participating organisations: University of California, Santa Barbara No. of participants: 88 (for online presentation) Recording: "A community-led future for OA books". (Apr 2024). CharlestonConference. <i>YouTube</i>. https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=kMstZahjPus (4 views) Further documentation of event: Deville, J., Sanders, K., & Corazza, F. (Feb 2024). "What a difference a year makes: An update on the Open Book Collective's activities over the past 12 months". <i>OBC Information Hub</i>. https://doi.org/10.21428/41ca814e.3db1e0a1</p>
2. OBC	(A2.3) 2 publisher workshops (inc. 1 with OBC members) scoping requirements for OBC Information Hub (with WP3, Lyrasis & OPERAS) & CRM, multilingual interface, grant allocation pilot	(D2.3a) Multilingual platform interface (draft) and spec document for CRM	May-24	Completed	<p>WP met with software engineers (DeltaQ) in Dec 2023 and agreed a plan for development next steps, including work on CRM and other platform features. Specifications for interface enhancements have been informed by consultation with publishers, including via the workshops with publishers detailed below. Publisher workshops co-organised with Lyrasis & OPERAS planned for Year 2.</p> <p>Publisher Workshop 1 Title: OBC Information Hub and Collective Development Fund scoping workshop Date: 22 Jan 2024 Location: online Participating organisations: punctum, White Horse Press, Mattering Press, African Minds, Westminster University Press, University of London Press, Leuven University Press, DOAB/OAPEN, Thoth, OBP, meson press, mediastudies.press No. of participants: 15 Report on event: Fathallah, J., & Deville, J. (Mar 2024). "Collective</p>

					<p>Development Fund Grant Programme: Scoping update". <i>OBC Information Hub</i>. https://doi.org/10.21428/41ca814e.f748da11</p> <p>Publisher Workshop 2 Title: Evaluating evaluation criteria for OA book publishers: An exploratory workshop Date: 18 Apr 2024 Location: Online Participating organisations: Project Muse, OpenEdition, Open Book Collective, SciELO, DOAB, JSTOR, Thoth, African Platform for Open Scholarship, AG Universitätsverlage, University of Georgia Press, Fulcrum No. of participants: 20 Further details: This workshop will help to inform the resources around evaluation criteria that will feature on the project's Information Hub. An article was published using data gathered at the workshop: Joe Deville, Jordy Findanis and Niels Stern, "How Should We Evaluate Open Access Book Publishing" https://katinamagazine.org/content/article/open-knowledge/2024/how-should-we-evaluate-open-access-book-publishing.</p>
2. OBC	See above	(D2.3b) Interim blog post on grant allocation & management procedures	May-24	Completed	<p>Blog post on grant allocation & management procedures has been published: Fathallah, J. (Jan 2024). "First Collective Development Funding Call to Open in Apr 2024". <i>OBC Information Hub</i>. https://doi.org/10.21428/41ca814e.495490c0</p> <p>Call for grant applications launched in Apr 2024 (ahead of schedule, see A2.10 below) and has been viewed nearly 3000 times. Spanish & Portuguese versions also published: "OBC Collective Development Fund Grant Programme: 2024 Call & Guidance". (Apr 2024) <i>OBC Information Hub</i>. https://openbookcollective.pubpub.org/pub/obc-collective-development-fund-grant-programme-2024-call-guidance</p> <p>Grant allocation & management procedures have passed through internal feedback processes. This work has been supported in particular by the US-based non-profit Invest in Open Infrastructures, which has run a similar grant management programme. Feedback has also been sought and received from SPARC EU, who have joined the project as a consultant (via the OBC, in line with the original grant proposal).</p> <p>The WP also launched a scoping survey to help inform the grant</p>

					<p>allocation & management procedures. This survey was available in both English and Spanish, and closed at the end of Feb 2024: Fathallah, J. (Nov 2023). "Open Book Collective Development Fund: Scoping Survey". <i>OBC Information Hub</i>. https://doi.org/10.21428/41ca814e.e5f289c6</p> <p>In addition, WP2 collaborated with WP6 on parallel grant funding programme, which will award 3 grants funds to experimental publishing pilot projects: collaborating on specific grant allocation/management procedures.</p>
2. OBC	(A2.4) 1 workshop on the financial, governance, and communication challenges associated with supporting OA infrastructures in diverse contexts (with DOAB & SPARC Europe)	(D2.4) Interim blog post on OA infrastructures scoping work	May-24	Completed	<p>Blog post on OA infrastructures scoping work published: Fathallah, J., & Deville, J. (Mar 2024). "Collective Development Fund Grant Programme: Scoping Update". <i>OBC Information Hub</i>. https://doi.org/10.21428/41ca814e.f748da11</p> <p>Workshop was held in Nov 2023 (see details below), supplemented by insights from OBC publisher members workshop (see A2.3).</p> <p>Workshop 1 Title: Workshop to inform the OBC Development Fund Grant Date: 29 Nov 2023 Location: online Participating organisations: African Platform for Open Scholarship (formerly Continental Platform), Digital, Preservation Coalition, Invest in Open Infrastructures, Knowledge Futures, OpenEdition/Language Science Press, Public Knowledge Project, SPARC EU No. of participants: 13 Report on event: Fathallah, J., & Deville, J. (Mar 2024). "Collective Development Fund Grant Programme: Scoping Update". <i>OBC Information Hub</i>. https://doi.org/10.21428/41ca814e.f748da11</p>
2. OBC	(A2.5) 3 international workshops including in the EU (with OPERAS & SPARC EU) & rest of the world (RoW) (with the	(D2.5a) New outreach targets identified in Europe and RoW	May-24	Completed	<p>New outreach targets in Europe & RoW have been identified and approached. The OBC now has 61 supporters. New supporters have included Heinrich Heine University Düsseldorf; KB, National Library of the Netherlands; McMaster University Libraries; Rowan University Libraries; University of Waikato Library; and Zentralbibliothek Zürich. If permission is granted, new supporters are announced via press releases on the OBC news blog: https://openbookcollective.pubpub.org/news</p> <p>Outreach work has also involved organising international workshops</p>

	<p>African Continental Platform and SciELO) scoping opportunities/barriers to consortial funding models</p>			<p>scoping opportunities/barriers to funding OA around the world. One workshop was held in Jul, in collaboration with SciELO (an organisation that supports OA publishing in Latin America) and a second workshop took place in Feb in Cape Town in collaboration with University of Cape Town Library/UCT Press/African Platform for Open Scholarship. A third workshop was held with Southern Women Academics Network. See workshop details below.</p> <p>International Workshop 1 Title: Open Book Futures: Working together to Build Community-owned Infrastructures for OA books to its members Date: 14 Jul 2023 Location: online Participating organisations: SciELO, Thoth, OtF No. of participants: c.60 Event page: https://25.scielo.org/en/seminars/copim/ Slides: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8142775 Further documentation: Deville, J., Sanders, K., & Corazza, F. (Feb 2024). "What a difference a year makes: An update on the Open Book Collective's activities over the past 12 months". <i>OBC Information Hub</i>. https://doi.org/10.21428/41ca814e.3db1e0a1</p> <p>International Workshop 2 Title: Open Access and Global South Scholars: Needs, Experiences, Barriers Date: 11/01/2024 Location: Online Participating organisations: Southern Women Academics Network No. of participants: 10 Report on event: Fathallah, J. (Feb 2024). "Open Access and Global South Scholars: Needs, Experiences, Barriers. Workshop Report." <i>OBC Information Hub</i>. https://doi.org/10.21428/41ca814e.b423d75c</p> <p>International Workshop 3 Title: 'Towards Sustainable Open Access Book Publishing in the African Context' Date: 7–9 Feb 2024 Location: Cape Town Participating organisations: African Platform for Open Scholarship (formerly Continental Platform), Association of African Universities,</p>
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2. OBC	(A2.5) See above	(D2.5b) Interim blog post on EU/RoW library landscape scoping work	May-24	Completed	<p>Report published: Fathallah, J., & Deville, J. (Mar 2024). "Reflections on 'Towards Sustainable Open Access Book Publishing in the African Context', a workshop at the University of Cape Town". <i>OBC Information Hub</i>. https://doi.org/10.21428/41ca814e.6fa8c7df</p>
Year 2					
2. OBC	(A2.6) Continue to increase OBC revenue	(D2.6a) At least 3 new publisher and service provider sign-ups (Year 2)	May-25	Completed	<p>1. PKP confirmed as a new member of the OBC (Oct 2024): joining 2 other service provider members. "Public Knowledge Project Joins the OBC". (2024). <i>OBC Information Hub</i>. https://openbookcollective.pubpub.org/pub/the-open-book-collective-welcomes-pkp</p> <p>2. LSE Press confirmed as a new member of the OBC (Dec 2024). "LSE Press Joins the Open Book Collective". (2024). <i>OBC Information Hub</i>. https://openbookcollective.pubpub.org/pub/lse-press-joins-the-open-book-collective</p> <p>3. Barbara Budrich Press confirmed as a new member of the OBC (Feb 2025). "Verlag Barbara Budrich Joins the Open Book Collective". (2025). <i>OBC Information Hub</i>. https://openbookcollective.pubpub.org/pub/verlag-barbara-budrich-press-joins-the-open-book-collective</p> <p>4. Sidestone confirmed as a new member of the OBC (Apr 2025). "Sidestone Press Joins the Open Book Collective". (2025). <i>OBC Information Hub</i>. https://openbookcollective.pubpub.org/pub/ye52vnsy</p>

2. OBC	(A2.6) See above	(D2.6b) £600,000 revenue generated in Year 2	May-25	Completed	Since start of year 2, OBC's contracted revenue is £707,846 Total number of supporting members = 85 [Figures correct on: 16 April 2025]
2. OBC	(A2.7) 5 workshops (1 UK, 2 US, 1 EU, 1 RoW) for librarians (supported by Jisc, SCURL, RLUK, SPARC Europe, OPERAS)	(D2.7) 1 report on barriers to consortial funding from libraries & supporting OA infrastructures in diverse contexts	May-25	Completed	<p>1 X report on barriers to consortial funding & supporting OA in diverse contexts Fathallah, J. (2025). "Update on Forthcoming Report: Barriers and Experience with Collective Funding Models in European Contexts". <i>OBC Information Hub</i>. https://openbookcollective.pubpub.org/pub/update-on-forthcoming-report</p> <p>The above, is an initial, interim report, focussing on illustrative findings in the Netherlands. A longer report (forthcoming) will examine barriers present in a range of case study countries: Germany, Sweden, Finland, the Netherlands and France. The OBC has conducted interviews with librarians working in these national contexts, and these will inform the longer report due to be published in Year 3.</p> <p><u>Workshop 1 (UK):</u> Title: "The Crisis in Higher Education and the Future of Diamond Open Access" Date: 19 September 2024 Location: London Participating organisations: LSE Press, Open Library of Humanities No. of participants: Circa 250 (60-70 in person, rest online) Event page: Copim Community (2024). "Crisis in higher education and the future of Diamond open access". <i>Copim</i>. https://copim.pubpub.org/pub/futureofdiamond Recordings/slides/event report: Copim Community (2024). "Catch up with: 'Crisis in higher education and the future of Diamond open access'". <i>Copim</i>. https://copim.pubpub.org/pub/catch-up-future-of-diamond</p> <p><u>Workshop 2 (EU)</u> Title: "Evaluating and Assessing Diamond Open Access Book Initiatives: Challenges and Opportunities" (LIBER Pre-Conference Workshop)</p>

				<p>Date: 2 July 2024 Location: Cyprus Participating organisations: OBC, DOAB/OAPEN No. of participants: 20+ in attendance Event page: https://liberconference.eu/workshop-10-evaluating-and-assessing-diamond-open-access-book-initiatives-challenges-and-opportunities/ Report on event: Sanders, K. (2024). "LIBER 2024, libraries, and support for sustainable Diamond OA". OBC Information Hub. https://openbookcollective.pubpub.org/pub/liber-2024</p> <p><u>Workshop 3 (US)</u> Title: Bridging Altruism to Strategy in OA Book Publishing – How Libraries Can Close Funding Gaps to Support a Bibliodiverse Global Shared Collection Date: 1 May 2024 Location: Online Participating organisations: OBC & Lyrasis No. of participants: 15 Event page: https://copim.pubpub.org/pub/workshop-bridging-altruism-to-strategy-in-oa-book-publishing Report: Adema, J., Barnes, L., Deville, J., Fathallah, J., Gatti, R., Grady, T., Hopkins, K., Hughes, A., McGann, C., Sanders, K., & Steiner, T. (2024). "The Copim perspective on Bibliodiversity". <i>Copim</i>. https://doi.org/10.21428/785a6451.86a892a7 Slides: Annie Johnson, "Towards an Open Access Strategy for Books" <https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.11202986> ; Harrison W. Inefuku, "Open Access Book Publishing" <https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.11202885> ; Ellen Dubinsky, "OA at UA Libraries" <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11202827> ; Joe Deville, "Bridging Altruism to Strategy in Open Access Book Publishing" <https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.11202754> ; Sara Chomyc, "University of Alberta Library & Open Access Monographs" <https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.11202590></p> <p><u>Workshop 4 (US)</u> Title: Whose Future Is It? Practical Strategies for Supporting Community-led Open Access Book Publishing Date: November 2024 Location: Charleston Conference, Charleston</p>
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				<p>Participating organisations: punctum books, OBC (via Lidia Uziel, UCSB), CUNY, Queens College Graduate School of Library and Information Studies</p> <p>No. of participants: 70</p> <p>Further documentation of event: Onalee Snyder, L. & T. Grady (2025). "A Reflection on 2024 Charleston Conference". <i>Copim</i>. https://copim.pubpub.org/pub/a-reflection-on-2024-charleston-conference</p> <p>Workshop 5 (RoW)</p> <p>Title: Open monograph publishing workshop, at the 2nd Global Summit on Diamond Open Access</p> <p>Date: 9-10 December 2024</p> <p>Location: Cape Town, South Africa</p> <p>Participating organisations: Association of African Universities, African Minds, Coventry University, the Directory of Open Access Books/OAPEN, Lancaster University, the Open Book Collective, Open Book Publishers, the Public Knowledge Project, punctum books, Thoth Open Metadata, University of Cape Town Libraries, and University of Cape Town Press.</p> <p>No. of participants: 60</p> <p>Event page with slides:</p> <p>"Open Monograph Publishing: A workshop at the 2nd Global Summit on Diamond OA". (2024). OBC Information Hub. https://openbookcollective.pubpub.org/pub/open-mongraph-publishing-workshop-at-the-2nd-global-summit-on-diamond-oa</p> <p>Further documentation of event: Fathallah, J. (2025). "Reflections on Open Monograph Publishing: A workshop at the 2nd Global Summit on Diamond OA". <i>OBC Information Hub</i>. https://doi.org/10.21428/41ca814e.b9ef0e6b</p>	
2. OBC	(A2.8) 1 new promotional online video produced	(D2.8) 1 video published	May-25	Completed	<p>Video produced and published on YouTube in April 2025: https://youtu.be/vc_MkR0d9bQ?si=5LaESznEEhN0nKtw</p> <p>Filming took place at the Charleston Conference and the Diamond OA Summit in Cape Town in December. The video will be embedded on the OBC homepage and shared via social media. It is set to be a useful resource for promoting the OBC, and advocating for community-led OA publishing more generally.</p>

2. OBC	(A2.9) CRM & advanced search for OBC platform finalised	(D2.9) CRM system, advanced platform search features, and a multilingual interface operational	May-25	In progress - delayed	<p>Throughout Year 2, developers have been actively working on these changes to the site, but workload has meant not all improvements will be live by 30 April 2025. All are on track for completion before the end of the project.</p> <p>CRM system: may not be fully functioning by end of Year 2, but work on track to be complete by end of Year 3.</p> <p>Advanced platform search features: there is a possibility OBC may be able to work with Thoth on this.</p> <p>Multilingual interface: is ready for launch. First language will be German. Translation underway. Technical functionality is very near complete. Press release will announce this site improvement.</p>
2. OBC	(A2.10) New call for OBC grant applications	(D2.10a) Grant allocation & management procedures published	May-25	Completed	<p>Call published on 16 Apr 2024: "OBC Collective Development Fund Grant Programme: 2024 Call & Guidance". (Apr 2024) <i>OBC Information Hub</i>. https://openbookcollective.pubpub.org/pub/obc-collective-development-fund-grant-programme-2024-call-guidance</p>
2. OBC	(A2.10) See above	(D2.10b) 1 OBC grant allocated, 1 new call announced	May-25	Completed	<p>Following meeting of OBC board in September 2024, 3 grants were provisionally awarded, totalling £37,500. Due diligence was completed and contracts issued and signed. Grants allocated as follows:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> <p>Fostering Academic Self-Reliance in Nigeria through Open Access Books</p> <p>For more information see: Fathallah, J. (2024). "Announcing OBC's First Collective Development Fund award: Fostering Academic Self-Reliance in Nigeria through Open Access Books". <i>OBC Information Hub</i>. https://openbookcollective.pubpub.org/pub/announcing-obcs-first-collective-development-fund-award-fostering-academic-self-reliance-in-nigeria-through-open-access-books</p> <p>Enhancing open-access book publishing at Chinhoyi University of Technology (CUT) Library</p> <p>For more information see: Fathallah, J. (2024). "Announcing OBC's Second Collective Development Fund Award: Enhancing Open Access Book Publishing at Chinhoyi University of Technology Library". <i>OBC Information Hub</i>. https://openbookcollective.pubpub.org/pub/announcing-obcs-</p>

					<p>second-collective-development-fund-award-enhancing-open-access-book-publishing-at-chinhoyi-university-of-technology-library</p> <p>3. The Community Publishing Garden: centring grassroots publishing initiatives in the open book publishing system For more information see: Fathallah, J. (2025). "Announcing OBC's third Collective Development Fund award: The Community Publishing Garden". <i>OBC Information Hub</i>. https://openbookcollective.pubpub.org/pub/announcing-obcs-third-collective-development-fund-awardthe-community-publishing-garden</p> <p>More information on the allocation process published here: Fathallah, J. (2024). "Collective Development Fund Update: Learning From Our First Assessment Process". <i>OBC Information Hub</i>. <https://openbookcollective.pubpub.org/pub/collective-development-fund-update-learning-from-our-first-assessment-process></p>
2. OBC	(A2.11) Interim evaluation of OBC, including impact of global outreach, completed	(D2.11) Interim evaluation report published & management plan updated	May-25	Completed	<p>Research Consulting were employed as external consultants to support an external appraisal of the OBC's work, impact, and sustainability. This work was completed by April 2025.</p> <p>The full report includes some sensitive financial information, which would not be suitable for publication. So, the OBC will instead publish a report summarising findings and reflecting on how the report will impact the charity's future plans. This is scheduled to be published in <i>LSE Impact</i> in Year 3.</p>
2. OBC	(A2.12) OBC Information Hub (with WP3) launched, in collaboration with Knowledge Futures (creators of PubPub, an open-source, end-to-end publishing platform for	(D2.12) OBC Information Hub launched	May-25	Completed	<p>Scoping report conducted to ascertain Info Hub requirements: Hopkins, K. and Hughes, A., "Open Book Futures InfoHub Scoping Report", https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13842915</p> <p>The information hub has been launched on BookStack and will continue to be expanded throughout year 3 of the project: https://copimcompass.copim.ac.uk/books</p> <p>Rather than being named the "OBC Information Hub" we have called the hub "Copim Compass". This change makes it clearer that the hub will not only include information from or about the OBC. More broadly conceived, the hub will be a cross-Copim initiative, sharing guides and resources created across the project. For example, the first materials</p>

	knowledge communities, which will be used to host the Information Hub).				available on the hub will be a guide to Opening the Future for presses seeking to transition to OA book publishing. <u>Rationale behind decision to host on BookStack rather than on PubPub:</u> In July 2024 Knowledge Futures announced their intention to introduce an annual fee of \$3,500 to use their publishing platform (https://www.knowledgefutures.org/updates/pubpub-platform/). The project team responded expressing concerns, and have been working with Knowledge Futures to find a solution (https://doi.org/10.21428/785a6451.c64e3c31). However, in the interests of time, and to guarantee the openness and long-term sustainability of the information hub, the project team have decided to launch this deliverable on an alternative platform, rather than Knowledge Futures's PubPub, the Hub uses Book Stack: a simple, open-source, self-hosted, easy-to-use platform for organising and storing information.
Year 3					
2. OBC	(A2.13) Further increase OBC revenue	(D2.13a) £1,000,000 revenue generated in Year 3	May-26	Not started	
2. OBC	(A2.13) See above	(D2.13b) At least 3 new publisher/service provider sign-ups (Year 3)	May-26	In progress	Applications received from 5 new publisher/service providers.
2. OBC	(A2.14) 6 library outreach events (1 UK, 1 US, 3 EU, 1 RoW; supported by Jisc, SCURL, RLUK, SPARC Europe, OPERAS,	(D2.14) 300+ libraries briefed	May-26	In progress	

	African Continental Platform, SciELO)				
2. OBC	(A2.15) Further call for OBC grant applications announced	(D2.15) 2 OBC grants allocated	May-26	In progress	<p>Further call for OBC grant applications announced in January 2025: Fathallah, J. (2025). "OBC Collective Development Fund Grant Programme: 2025 Call & Guidance". OBC Information Hub. https://openbookcollective.pubpub.org/pub/obc-collective-development-fund-grant-programme-2025-call--guidance</p> <p>Call was also published in 3 additional languages:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Portuguese [https://openbookcollective.pubpub.org/pub/obc-collective-development-fund-grant-program-2025-call-for-proposals-and-guidance] • French [https://openbookcollective.pubpub.org/pub/programme-de-subventions-du-fonds-de-developpement-collectif-de-lobc--appel-et-conseils-pour-2025] • Spanish [https://openbookcollective.pubpub.org/pub/cbo-collective-development-fund-grant-program-call-and-guidance-2025] <p>6 applications sent to reviewers in March 2025.</p>
2. OBC	(A2.16) Final full evaluation of OBC	(D2.16) 1 final performance evaluation report	May-26	Not started	
WP3: Opening the Future					
Year 1					
3. OtF	(A3.1) Direct outreach to at least 5 presses about shifting to the presses to	(D3.1) Discussions initiated with 3 presses about adopting the OtFRM	May-24	Completed	A report on OtF's direct outreach work in Year 1 is available here: Hopkins, K. (Apr 2024). "Engaging with New Presses: Growing the Opening the Future Programme and Community". <i>Copim</i> . https://copim.pubpub.org/pub/y1nzugp1

	engage with OtFRM				
3. OtF	(A3.2) Work with Jisc and Lyris to scope options for embedding the OtFRM in third party processes	(D3.2) Interim blogpost on options for embedding OtFRM in partner workflows	May-24	Completed	Blogpost on options for embedding OtF in partner workflows is published here: Hopkins, K., & 3, W. P. (Apr 2024). "How Long is a Tangled Web of String?" <i>Copim</i> . https://copim.pubpub.org/pub/01mst8w2
3. OtF	(A3.3) 2 outreach events for publishers & libraries on OtFRM toolkits & workflows (supported by Jisc, SCURL, Lyris, SPARC Europe)	(D3.3) Reports via blogposts on updates on OtFRM toolkits & workflows	May-24	Completed	<p>Reports on updates to OtF toolkits and workflows:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Hopkins, K. (Apr 2024). "Improving Workflows and Updating Infrastructure at Opening the Future". <i>Copim</i>. https://copim.pubpub.org/pub/t72gg6n9 • Hopkins, K., & WP3 (May 2024). "Opening the Future seeks Library Advisory Board Members". <i>Copim</i>. https://copim.pubpub.org/pub/i9i9izvd • Grady, T. (Feb 2024). "New year update, Jan 2024". <i>Opening the Future</i>. https://www.openingthefuture.net/news/111/ • Grady, T. (Forthcoming, Summer 2024). "Getting Out From the Back of the Sofa: Sustainable Funding for Open Access Monographs Through Opening the Future and Other Collective Funding Models". <i>National Acquisitions Group</i>. • See also the various other updates posted here: https://www.openingthefuture.net/news/ <p>Outreach Workshop 1 Title: The Times They Are A' Changing: How Can We Fund Open Access Books Equitably and Sustainably Date: 1 Nov 2023 Location: Online Participating organisations: Project MUSE, CEU Press, California Digital Library No. of participants: 430+ attendees Recording: "Opening the Future Webinar: How Can We Fund Open Access Books Equitably and Sustainably". (Nov 2023) Project MUSE. <i>YouTube</i>. https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=fqDv80x2F8Y&t=4s (198 views)</p>

					<p>Documentation of event: Hopkins, K., & 3, W. P. (Jan 2024). "The Times They Are A'Changing: How Can We Fund Open Access Books Equitably and Sustainably". <i>Copim</i>. https://doi.org/10.21428/785a6451.4780fe88</p> <p>Outreach Workshop 2 Title: Getting Out From the Back of the Sofa: Sustainable Funding for Open Access Books Date: 9 Nov 2023 Location: Munin Conference, Tromsø campus of UiT The Arctic University of Norway No. of participants: 30 attendees Event page: https://site.uit.no/muninconf/program/ Abstract: https://septentrio.uit.no/index.php/SCS/article/view/7156 Documentation of event: https://zenodo.org/records/10226504</p>
3. OtF	(A3.4) Create specification and advert to recruit Outreach Coordinator	(D3.4) Outreach Coordinator position filled	May-24	Completed	Interviews for 'Scholarly Publishing Outreach Officer' were held on 17 Oct 2023, and a new colleague (Kira Hopkins) was appointed. Kira joined the team on 11 Dec 2023.
Year 2					
3. OtF	(A3.5) Begin transitioning revenue models of new presses to OtFRM	(D3.5) 3 new non-UK/US presses in transition	May-25	In progress - delayed	<p>Positive talks are underway with 2 presses, with a public announcement expected soon. Work will continue in Year 3 of the project, and we hope to have some presses in transition before the end of the OBF project.</p> <p>The WP has been in talks with 10+ presses since start of project. Many presses consulted have cited other priorities at this stage i.e.: operational issues and strategic priorities for them that are more pressing than transitioning to OA. For further detail on the challenges of transitioning from closed to open access, see: Grady, T., & Hopkins, K. (2024). "The Challenges of Transitioning from Closed to Open Access Books". <i>Copim</i>. https://doi.org/10.21428/785a6451.191c428b</p> <p>Record of other progress on this deliverable:</p>

- Implemented code updates to the website and back office functionality that will make onboarding new presses smoother and quicker.
- Negotiated and drafted a template contract between Birkbeck and A.N.Other Press which can be implemented quickly

Rationale behind delays to completing this deliverable:

Since May 2023, Work Package 3 (Opening the Future) has engaged in transition talks with over 10 presses. The WP has also pursued an active outreach campaign: organising and participating in 20+ high-profile events & webinars [see full list: <https://copim.pubpub.org/pub/open-book-futures-outreach>], launching a newsletter, and convening a Library Advisory Board. However, the current economic climate has made it hard for many publishers to commit to transition before April 2026. In October 2024, the WP published a report discussing the risks & challenges impacting successful completion of this deliverable. [<https://copim.pubpub.org/pub/challenges-of-transitioning-from-closed-to-open-access-books>]

We have made progress with several contacts, and hope to have positive news to announce early in Year 3.

However, it will be challenging to ensure that the new presses in transition by the end of the project are based outside the UK & US [as targeted in our initial deliverables]. WP3 has engaged with presses outside of these national contexts, but national particularities and other circumstances (including language barriers) have made it challenging for these presses to begin the transition process within the project's timeframe.

Whilst we regret that new Opening the Future presses are unlikely to all represent areas outside the Global North, it would still be an immense achievement to announce the transition of new presses, wherever located. We firmly believe that it is valuable to support publishers around the world who are seeking to transition to OA publishing via equitable, non-BPC models like Opening the Future. If we can support more presses to adopt the model (regardless of their location) it would be an important victory, particularly given the massive proliferation of non-BPC models and tough economic circumstances at HEI institutions (with knock-on impacts on publishers).

					<p>OtF has been heavily involved in outreach to new OA initiatives outside the UK/US, such as Open Books Hong Kong and FORM (an Arab / Gulf States OA initiative), offering knowledge and guidance about collective funding for books. The WP is in discussions with OBHK about how we may support their work, and with FORM about a possible webinar to their members. For further information on Copim’s work outside the Global North, see:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • “Thoth Latin American Publishers’ workshop, April 2024.” https://doi.org/10.21428/785a6451.1a61edad • “Implementing international metadata standards and requirements in Thoth: an update.” https://doi.org/10.21428/785a6451.8d96d21a • “Reflections on ‘Towards Sustainable Open Access Book Publishing in the African Context’, a workshop at the University of Cape Town.” https://doi.org/10.21428/41ca814e.6fa8c7df • “Open Monograph Publishing: A workshop at the 2nd Global Summit on Diamond OA”. https://openbookcollective.pubpub.org/pub/open-mongraph-publishing-workshop-at-the-2nd-global-summit-on-diamond-oa
3. OtF	(A3.6) 2 international workshops for publishers (scoping sustainability of OtFRM model) and librarians (scoping engagement strategies) (supported by SPARC Europe, OPERAS)	(D3.6) 1 report with OtFRM case studies published	May-25	Completed	<p>Report with OtFRM case studies published as part of Copim Compass: The WP divided this deliverable in two, publishing case studies from publishers using OtF & authors who have had books published thanks to OtF: Publishers: Title: “Comments from current users of Opening the Future” Author: Tom Grady, and staff at Central European University Press and Liverpool University Press, who have both been using the model since its inception in 2020. Link: https://compass.copim.ac.uk/books/06-opening-the-future-introduction-and-description/page/comments-from-current-users-of-opening-the-future See also: OtFRM Annual Report for 2024, highlighting successes at current presses, and discussions with Library Advisory Board: https://www.openingthefuture.net/news/140/ Authors:</p>

				<p>McGann, C., Grady, T., & Hopkins, K. (2025). "Opening the Future, Author Profile: Peter Watson". <i>Copim</i>. https://copim.pubpub.org/pub/football-and-nation-building</p> <p>McGann, C., Grady, T., & Hopkins, K. (2025). Opening the Future, Author Profile: Mario Graña Taborelli. <i>Copim</i>. https://copim.pubpub.org/pub/jurisdictional-battlefields</p> <p>McGann, C., Grady, T., & Hopkins, K. (n.d.). Opening the Future, Author Profile: Daniel Silva. <i>Copim</i>. https://copim.pubpub.org/pub/empire-found</p> <p>Workshop 1 Title: Copim Connects SCONUL libraries: practical strategies to support equitable OA book publishing Date: 25 Jan 2024 Location: Online webinar Participating organisations: SCONUL, Lancaster University, Coventry University, University of Sheffield, Salford University No. of participants: 350 Event page: https://www.sconul.ac.uk/event/copim-and-sconul-exploring-practical-problems-and-potential-strategies-to-fund-equitable-oa Recording: https://vimeo.com/906390958 Report on event: Hopkins, K. (2024). "Copim and SCONUL: exploring practical problems and potential strategies to fund equitable OA book publishing". <i>Copim</i>. https://doi.org/10.21428/785a6451.415492ea</p> <p>Workshop 2 Title: Beyond the BPC: Collective Funding Model Experimentation and Challenges in Accelerating Sustainable OA Monographs Date: 14 November 2024 (in person), 12 December 2024 (online) Location: Charleston Conference 2024 Participating organisations: ITHAKA/JSTOR, OtF, MIT Press, Lancaster University Library Slides: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14717134 Event page: https://www.charleston-hub.com/the-charleston-conference/welcome/2024-preliminary-program/ Report on event: Onalee Snyder, L. & T. Grady (2025). "A Reflection on 2024 Charleston Conference". <i>Copim</i>.</p>
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					https://copim.pubpub.org/pub/a-reflection-on-2024-charleston-conference
3. OtF	(A3.7) OBC Information Hub (with WP2) launched	(D3.7) Publisher Info/Advice Hub update	May-25	Completed	<p>February/March 2025 - Copim Compass Iteration 1 launched [https://copimcompass.copim.ac.uk/books]. Hub hosts an OtF Toolkit as its main content initially, but with areas for other WPs to upload content in Year 3 of the project. An initial soft comms push targeted specific recipients. A larger launch is planned for before the end of April with a full comms plan.</p> <p>A scoping report was conducted to ascertain Info Hub requirements: Hopkins, K. and Hughes, A., "Open Book Futures InfoHub Scoping Report", https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13842915</p>
Year 3					
3. OtF	(A3.8) 5 workshops on OtFRM revenue models for presses in different countries	(D3.8) New OtFRM Presses' transition to OA documented in Publisher Info/Advice Hub	May-26	In progress	
3. OtF	(A3.9) Final full evaluation of OtFRM	(D3.9) 3 new publishers joint OtFRM programme	May-26	In progress	
WP4: Thoth Open Metadata					
Year 1					
4. Thoth	A4.1 Increase Thoth revenue	D4.1 £10,000 revenue generated in Year 1	May-24	Completed	Success criteria exceeded by 250%. Thoth has generated more than GBP 35,000 in revenue via Open Book Collective subscriptions.

4. Thoth	A4.2 Increase publisher use of Thoth services	D4.2 15 publishers using Thoth services	May-24	Completed	<p>As of Apr 2024, there are 25 publishers using the Thoth platform. Of these, 19 have metadata ready to export from the new Thoth website: https://thoth.pub/publishers</p> <p>Thoth has worked with & onboarded a variety of new international presses in Year 1, including Latin American SciELO Books publishers (EDUFBA, EDITUS, EDUEPB) and L'Harmattan Open Access (a Hungarian subsidiary of L'Harmattan [France]).</p> <p>The new Thoth Plus services were launched on 16 Nov 2023 and the initial response has been very positive. Thoth are now working with 5 publishers (Mattering, WHP, adocs, punctum, OBP) to establish submission workflows to several platforms. A blog post discussing the new Thoth Plus services has been published on the project's PubPub site: Arias, J., Higman, R., Hillen, H., Gatti, R., van Gerven Oei, V. W. J., O'Connell, B., Ramalho, A., & Steiner, T. (2024). "Thoth Expands Team and Collaborations, Introduces New Services". <i>Copim</i>. https://doi.org/10.21428/785a6451.a2e47002</p>
4. Thoth	A4.3(a) 2 workshops for publishers scoping Thoth requirements services, including in non-anglophone contexts (supported by COKI, DOAB, OPERAS, PKP)	D4.3a Service integration landscape study published	May-24	Completed	<p>Service integration landscape study published here: Steiner, T. (n.d.). "A growing network of open infrastructures: federated services with Thoth". <i>Copim</i>. https://copim.pubpub.org/pub/growing-network-of-open-infrastructures-federated-services-with-thoth</p> <p>Publisher Workshop 1 Title: Thoth Publisher Scoping Workshop Date: 16 Nov 2023 Location: Online Participating organisations: ADOCS Verlag, Edinburgh Diamond, Lancaster University, LSE Press, Loughborough University Library, mediastudies.press, Mattering Press, meson press, Open Book Collective, Open Book Publishers, punctum books, SciELO Books, Scottish Universities Press, textem Verlag and University of Westminster Press No. of participants: 21 Report on event: Steiner, T., Arias, J., Gatti, R., Higman, R., Hillen, H., Ramalho, A., & van Gerven Oei, V. W. J. (Jan 2024). "Thoth Publishers Workshop 2023". <i>Copim</i>. https://doi.org/10.21428/785a6451.0daca04e</p> <p>Publisher Workshop 2 Title: Thoth Latin American Publishers' workshop</p>

					<p>Date: 11 Apr 2024 Location: online Participating organisations: SciELO Books, Editorial UNRN (Argentina), Editorial Flacso Ecuador, Editorial UR (Colombia) and EUNED (Costa Rica) Report on event: Ramalho, A., Arias, J., & Steiner, T. (May 2024). "Workshop do Thoth Latin American Publishers, abril de 2024 / Taller de editores latinoamericanos Thoth, abril de 2024 / Thoth Latin American Publishers' workshop, Apr 2024". <i>Copim</i>. https://doi.org/10.21428/785a6451.1a61edad</p>
4. Thoth	A4.3(b) See above	D4.3b 1 interim blog post on int'l metadata requirements	May-24	Completed	<p>Blog post published: Steiner, T. (May 2024). "Implementing international metadata standards and requirements in Thoth: an update". <i>Copim</i>. https://copim.pubpub.org/pub/implementing-international-metadata-standards-requirements-in-thoth</p>
4. Thoth	A4.3(c) See above	D4.3c New publisher services launched (automatic reference generation, DOI minting, book content distribution)	May-24	Completed	<p>Thoth Plus service model launched on 16 Nov 2023. A blog post discussing the new Thoth Plus services has been published on the project's PubPub site: van Gerven Oei, V. W. J., Steiner, T., Arias, J., Gatti, R., Hillen, H., Higman, R., & Ramalho, A. (2024). "Launching the Thoth Plus service model". <i>Copim</i>. https://doi.org/10.21428/785a6451.0e9234b1 For further discussion of new services, see also: Arias, J., Higman, R., Hillen, H., Gatti, R., van Gerven Oei, V. W. J., O'Connell, B., Ramalho, A., & Steiner, T. (2024). "Thoth Expands Team and Collaborations, Introduces New Services". <i>Copim</i>. https://doi.org/10.21428/785a6451.a2e47002 And Steiner, T., van Gerven Oei, V. W. J., Hillen, H., & O'Connell, B. (2024). "A growing network of open infrastructures and federated services with Thoth". <i>Copim</i>. https://doi.org/10.21428/785a6451.92d1c71e</p> <p>Major website update now live: https://thoth.pub . Further information available here: Hillen, H., & Arias, J. (2024). "Launch of the new Thoth Open Metadata website". <i>Copim</i>. https://doi.org/10.21428/785a6451.1e5f1d4c Video overview of features available here: https://youtu.be/HtD7GdPKdqq And changelog here: https://github.com/thoth-pub/thoth/blob/master/CHANGELOG.md</p>

					<p>Formalised collaborations have been made with various platforms, which will help to facilitate service integration & content distribution across these platforms, e.g.:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Thoth-OAPEN collaboration agreement signed, this enables Thoth to act as an umbrella for small publishers who would have difficulty joining OAPEN on their own. (https://oapen.org/article/8778704-oapen-and-thoth-open-metadata-sign-partnership-agreement) • DOAB Trusted Partner Network: Collaboration agreement in place. (https://doabooks.org/en/article/jstor-african-platform-for-open-scholarship-apos-fulcrum-and-thoth-open-metadata-join-doab-trusted-platform-network) • Thoth confirmed as an official Crossref sponsor: enabling help with DOI minting for smaller publishers. (https://thoth.pub/solutions/doi) • Agreement w. OCLC signed. • In exchange with Jisc Library Hub to facilitate Thoth integration with Jisc NBK. <p>Other advancements in services & new services in development include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Improvement to MARC records in response to feedback from metadata librarians (e.g. now include a dedicated note re. their CC0 license) • Early scoping work on OMP-Thoth plugin development begun. • Work on full ONIX export begun (as compared to platform specific ONIX outputs that only use a subset of the full data available in Thoth). • Early stages of Traffic Light System being implemented. • Major update of Thoth book catalogue. In conjunction with this, planning a new service to offer hosting of catalogue and white-label website, which will be of particular interest to consortia and national-level catalogues. • Linked to Thoth's Crossref sponsorship, Thoth are now able to offer Crossmark and Crossref Similarity Check services.
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Year 2					
4. Thoth	A4.4 Further increase Thoth revenue	D4.4 £25,000 revenue generated in Year 2	May-25	Completed	Thoth have exceeded this revenue goal thanks to funds generated via the OBC. Thoth have received £100K+ in revenue since the OBF project began. In Oct 2024, the first publishers were invoiced for Thoth Plus services, and this is another important revenue stream (for further info. see deliverable A4.5 below).
4. Thoth	A4.5 Further increase publisher use of Thoth services	D4.5a 30 publishers using Thoth services	May-25	Completed	<p>On 1st April 2025, Thoth catalogue consisted of 2,800+ books and more than 13,000 chapters. Thoth also exceeded their target number of publishers by over 100%: over 60 publishers are using now Thoth's services. All publisher metadata can be accessed on Thoth's website (https://thoth.pub/publishers), with the caveat that not all publishers using Thoth already have book data available in the catalogue. See below for a list of publishers using Thoth (List updated 16 April 2025):</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Adocs Publishing 2. African Minds 3. Bokförlaget Stolpe 4. Casemate Academic 5. Central European University Press 6. Digital Preservation Coalition 7. Ediciones de la Ergástula 8. Ediciones RISEI 9. Ediciones Universidad de Camagüey 10. Edinburgh Diamond 11. Editora da Universidade Estadual da Paraíba 12. Editora da Universidade Estadual de Feira de Santana 13. Editora da Universidade Federal de Bahia (EDUFBA) 14. Editora da Universidade Tecnológica Federal do Paraná 15. Editorial Ciencias Médicas 16. Editorial FLACSO Ecuador 17. Editorial Mar Caribe 18. Editorial Universidad Autónoma de Aguascalientes 19. Editorial Universidad del Rosario 20. Editorial Universitaria UTE 21. Editorial Universitat Politècnica de València 22. Editus - Editora da UESC

					<p>62. University of London Press 63. University of North Georgia Press 64. University of Westminster Press</p>
4. Thoth	A4.5 See above	D4.5b At least 5 new publishers use services/features developed in year 1	May-25	Completed	<p>Thoth have exceeded this target by 300%. 20 publishers have signed up for Thoth Plus services, with more applications under review.</p> <p>For a summary of Thoth Plus services see: https://thoth.pub/pricing.</p> <p>The revenue gained from Thoth Plus services will be important for Thoth's financial sustainability post-project. Sign-ups to Thoth Plus Package B have been higher than initially anticipated, which is a major success for the initiative.</p>
4. Thoth	A4.6 Mid-point evaluation with publishers using the service (survey)	D4.6 1 mid-point evaluation report & update to project management plan	May-25	Completed	<p>Imming, M., & Uyens, B. (2025). "Thoth Open Metadata: Copim Open Book Futures Mid-Term Review (1.0)". Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15131150</p> <p>The above is an independent report conducted by Imming Impact and Trendlab, reviewing Thoth Open Metadata's efforts to deliver on the goals defined as part of the company's participation in the Copim Open Book Futures project, its business model, catalogue of services and how Thoth is perceived by its key stakeholders.</p> <p>Moreover, it focuses on the Thoth Strategic Roadmap for the coming five years. Input for this review was three 3-hour workshops with the Thoth team (attended by ca. 8 pp each workshop), interviews with stakeholders and desk research.</p>
4. Thoth	A4.7 2 workshops to conclude research on international metadata requirements (supported by DOAB, OPERAS, COKI, PKP)	D4.7a 1 study of book metadata requirements in diverse national contexts	May-25	Completed	<p>1 study of book metadata requirements in diverse national context:</p> <p>Van Gerven Oei, V. W. J., Steiner, T., Hillen, H., & Higman, R. (2025). "Maybe Persistent but Certainly Not Unique: On the Proliferation of DOIs in Open Access Book Publishing". <i>Copim</i>. https://doi.org/10.21428/785a6451.fb6181fd</p> <p>A further study of book metadata requirements will be published in Year 3.</p>

				<p>Workshop 1 Title: Publishing Workshop: Accessibility, Archiving and Metadata (hosted in collaboration with WP 5 & 7) Date: 27 November 2024 Location: online Participating organisations: Ext: Open Press at the University of Sussex, University of London Press, Scottish Universities Press, LSE Press, Graz University Library Publishing, meson press, L'Harmattan Publishing House, University of Groningen Press, mediastudies.press, Mattering Press, TU Delft Open Publishing, Maastricht University Int.: Open Book Publishers, Loughborough University Library, Lancaster University Library, Thoth Open Metadata, punctum books, No. of participants: 30 Slides: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14620187 (Accessibility); https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14673216 (Archiving); https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14674033 (Open Metadata). Further documentation of event: Steiner, T., Fitzpatrick, J., Barnes, M., Hillen, H., & Gatti, R. (2025). "Accessibility, Archiving, and Open Metadata - A Copim Publishers' Workshop". <i>Copim</i>. https://doi.org/10.21428/785a6451.a1803fe6</p> <p>Workshop 2: Good Metadata practice workshop Title: Metadata Good Practice webinar Date: 20 March 2025 Location: online Participating organisations: Thoth, OIPA, OABN, (IOAP). Speakers: Graham Bell from EditEUR (to talk about ONIX), Jeff Edmunds from Penn State University Libraries (to talk about MARC). Contribution by Thoth colleagues re. general good practice regarding metadata creation and dissemination No. of participants: 250+ signups, 180 participants Slides: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15048076 Further documentation of event: Hillen, H., & Steiner, T. (2025). Good metadata practice for Open Access books. Copim. https://doi.org/10.21428/785a6451.ced96be1</p>	
4. Thoth	A4.7 See above	D4.7b New services for EU/RoW publishers and	May-25	In progress - delayed	In Year 2, development work at Thoth has focused on improving existing services and adding many new features to Thoth (see list below). However, the multilingual data schema & interface was not introduced in Year 2 – it will be launched before the end of Year 3. This

for librarians,
multilingual
interface

delay is due to re-prioritising workload in order to launch the features most required by users, and to work with the timelines and workload of partners.

New services for publishers & librarians:

See these recent presentations <https://zenodo.org/records/14674033> and <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13987020> for an overview of services on offer. Some of the key services developed in Year 2 include:

Crossref's Crossmark feature

(<https://thoth.pub/solutions/integrations#crossmark-integration>)

Implementation finalised in Sept 2024. Crossmark informs reader of the current status of an item, so that readers can be sure they are reading the most up-to-date version of a given document

Open Monographs Press / Thoth plugin

([https://thoth.pub/solutions/integrations#open-monographs-press-\(omp\)-integration](https://thoth.pub/solutions/integrations#open-monographs-press-(omp)-integration))

Plugin beta openly available as of Oct 2024 (<https://github.com/thoth-pub/thoth-omp-plugin>). Developed in partnership with Brazilian developer Lepidus. Beta-testing with: Scottish Universities Press / Edinburgh Diamond, Graz University Publishing, TU Delft, Groningen University Press & UJ Press. Plugin enables publishers to send metadata from PKP's Open Monographs Press (OMP) into Thoth.

Thoth Hosting services

(<https://thoth.pub/solutions/hosting>)

High-performance content hosting (PDFs, epub, html, etc. incl. book cover files) now fully implemented and being rolled out to all Plus publishers, streamlining dissemination and enabling Thoth to easily collect usage data.

Thoth's white-label website approach [using template based on Strapi CMS] now successfully implemented for Thoth's own website, and for Open Book Publishers and Dutch NUPs consortia catalogue.

Analytics and usage

(<https://thoth.pub/solutions/hosting#thoth-usage-statistics>)

Provision of privacy-respecting usage data for Thoth-hosted files. Integration with OPERAS Metrics to collect, process & aggregate usage data from Google Books, OAPEN & publishers' own website. Thoth has

					<p>plans to expand this to include JSTOR, Project MUSE, etc. Thoth is developing a user-friendly publisher dashboard designed to provide intuitive visualisations of usage statistics across an entire portfolio.</p> <p>Thoth Open Archiving Network (TOAN) https://thoth.pub/solutions/archiving#thoth-open-archiving-network TOAN offers publishers the option of automatically archiving their publications in multiple repository locations. 11 publishers subscribed to Thoth Plus are now included in TOAN workflows: Scottish Universities Press, Adocs, Bokförlaget Stolpe, Digital Preservation Society, L'Harmattan Open Access, Mattering Press, Media Studies Press, Paideia Publishing Services, White Horse Press, OBP, Punctum.</p> <p>Links to aggregator platforms In Year 2, Thoth have made progress with several aggregator platforms including JSTOR, Project MUSE, EBSCO, ProQuest and Clarivate/ExLibris (agreements signed and workflows established). Reached out to Scopus in Feb 2025, to add as a new platform</p> <p>Integration with other platforms Thoth engaged in conversations with Jisc, PKP/OMP, Pressbooks, Fulcrum/Michigan Publishing re: closer integration of Thoth data in these platforms.</p> <p>Dissemination to OAPEN's DSpace (via SWORD) Delayed due to OAPEN's change of hosting providers (now with CERN), but progress has resumed and in April 2025 implementation work began.</p> <p>Services for librarians A brain-storming workshop with a small number of metadata librarians held at the end of Oct 24. Library-facing open union catalogue idea being explored in earnest, and pitched to funders. Further conversations had with interested stakeholders during Jan/Feb 2025.</p>
Year 3					
4. Thoth	A4.8 Further increase Thoth revenue	D4.8 £65,000 revenue	May-26	Completed	Thoth has generated over £100k in revenue.

		generated in Year 3			
4. Thoth	A4.9 Further increase publisher use of Thoth services	D4.9 45 publishers use Thoth services	May-26	Completed	In April 2025, 60+ publishers were using Thoth (see above)
4. Thoth	A4.10 Development of new services, database features, service integrations, non-English user interfaces for Thoth finalised	D4.10 Open-Source code made available online via Github	May-26	In progress	
WP5: Accessibility					
Year 1					
5. Accessibility	(A5.1) 2 workshops scoping accessibility requirements and obstacles with libraries and publishers (1 UK/US/EU, 1 RoW)	(D5.1) Scoping report on global accessibility barriers	May-24	Completed	<p>1 Scoping report on global accessibility barriers Fitzpatrick, J. (2025). "Global Accessibility Barriers". <i>Copim</i>. https://copim.pubpub.org/pub/global-accessibility-barriers</p> <p>Workshop 1 of 2 Title: Publishing Workshop: Accessibility, Archiving and Metadata (hosted in collaboration with WP 5 & 7) Date: 27 November 2024 Location: online Participating organisations: Ext: Open Press at the University of Sussex, University of London Press, Scottish Universities Press, LSE Press, Graz University Library Publishing, meson press, L'Harmattan Publishing House, University of Groningen Press, mediastudies.press, Mattering Press, TU Delft Open Publishing, Maastricht University Int.: Open Book Publishers, Loughborough University Library, Lancaster University Library, Thoth Open Metadata, punctum books, No. of participants: 30</p>

Slides: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14620187> (Accessibility); <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14673216> (Archiving)
Report on workshop: Steiner, T., Fitzpatrick, J., Barnes, M., Hillen, H., & Gatti, R. (2025). "Accessibility, Archiving, and Open Metadata - A Copim Publishers' Workshop". *Copim*. <https://doi.org/10.21428/785a6451.a1803fe6>

Workshop 2 of 2: (Libraries)

Title: Beyond Paywalls: Librarians Re-imagining Open Access

Date: 20 March 2025

Location: online

Event page: <https://lancaster-uk.libcal.com/calendar/libraryevents/beyondpaywalls>

Slides: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15221690>

Recording: https://archive.org/details/beyond_paywalls

Report on workshop findings: Fitzpatrick, J. (2025). "Librarians and Open Accessibility". *Copim*. <https://copim.pubpub.org/pub/librarians-and-open-accessibility>

Notes: On 14 December 2024, the WP also received detailed feedback from librarians working at Lancaster University, Leeds University, Manchester University, the Open University, and the University of South Africa, as part of a dedicated meeting of the project's Advisory Board. On 25 September 2024, the Work Package also sought feedback on their work during a Copim Online Showcase, attended by 80+ members of the library and publishing community. The WP has also arranged one-to-one meetings with librarians working in open research, learning technologies and acquisitions.

Record of other work scoping accessibility and barriers:

- A draft briefing document summarising accessible ebook legislation in the UK, EU, US, and RoW.
- A draft briefing document summarising relevant standards.
- Updates to Thoth wiki to include metadata standards that handle accessibility. For example, <https://github.com/thoth-pub/thoth/wiki/DAISY>; <https://github.com/thoth-pub/thoth/wiki/ONIX-3.0>; and <https://github.com/thoth-pub/thoth/wiki/BIBFRAME-2.0>.

Note about change in timeline for WP5 deliverables:

					<p>Work on this work package was postponed from Year 1 to Year 2 due to lengthy recruitment delays [see narrative provided in Year 1 reporting]. In Sep 2024 (M17), our ‘Accessibility and Library Engagement Manager’ (based at Lancaster University) began work, on a full-time contract, and WP5 launched. [The role was initially costed at 0.5 FTE, and a different project partner]. In Year 2, the WP has been catching up on Year 1 deliverables and making good progress on Year 2 deliverables. We are confident that all project deliverables will be complete by end of Year 3 thanks to acceleration provided by having a full-time staff member, and support from other parts of the wider project team.</p>
5. Accessibility	(A5.2) Iterative improvement of the accessibility checker tool	(D5.2) Codebase made openly available	May-24	Completed	<p>1 X Blog post documenting progress on iterative improvement of accessibility resources Fitzpatrick, J. (2025). “Accessibility Tools and Resources”. <i>Copim</i>. https://copim.pubpub.org/pub/accessibility-tools-resources</p> <p>See also, open Zotero list: https://www.zotero.org/groups/5680172/obf_wp5_accessibility/library</p> <p>The first step for the development of tools to support OA book publishers was to scope existing tools. This work has been documented via a blog post and openly available Zotero list, and revealed a large number of existing solutions. Discussions with publishers (see A5.1 above) revealed that many small open access publishers simply don’t know where to start or how to navigate through the emerging legislative requirements on one hand and the array of solutions available in a structured and cost-efficient manner. Understanding upcoming legislation requirements is complicated, identifying what needs to be done, what could be done, and how to practically achieve any of those objectives were the primary difficulties small publishers were facing. To that end the WP team recognised that, rather than developing a single accessibility tool, publishers would benefit more from a broader suite of tools and guidance that will allow them to understand legislative requirements, self-identify accessibility objectives, assess their existing publications against those objectives and design pragmatic strategies for enhancing the accessibility of their publications to achieve their objectives. To that end, the WP is now developing a Knowledge Base, hosted on Copim Compass, which will offer valuable guidance and advice on standards and requirements, as well as the benefits and “easy wins” available for small presses, and tools designed to help</p>

publishers assess their own maturity when it comes to accessibility and guide publishers on next steps for enhancing their accessibility compliance - offering practical support with planning and implementing workflow changes. Furthermore, the WP's tools will support publishers to demonstrate their compliance, and/or their planned route to compliance: an important form of documentation that is increasingly a requirement for libraries and platforms. In Year 3, the WP will be supporting a selection of small publishers to implement the project's new guidance and tools at their presses.

After consultation with publishers, and scoping existing tools available, we are confident that focussing on supporting maturity modelling, adapting workflows, and demonstrating compliance, is the best way of achieving our overarching, initial objective for this work package: i.e.: "to deliver more readily accessible open scholarship" and to "support publishers meeting accessibility standards in their publications".

In the blog post cited above (<https://copim.pubpub.org/pub/accessibility-tools-resources>), WP5 highlights the existence of a number of useful, open-source accessibility checker tools (making the creation of a new, stand-alone software of limited value). As the blog post explains, many accessibility improvements and checks require non-automated checks, and there is a pressing need to help publishers to improve and adapt their workflows to enable accessibility.

On the technical side, the WP's development team is also working hard to implement changes to Thoth's metadata model to accommodate accessibility and archiving-specific information. For example, the Thoth wiki was updated to include metadata standards that handle accessibility. For example: <https://github.com/thoth-pub/thoth/wiki/DAISY>; <https://github.com/thoth-pub/thoth/wiki/ONIX-3.0>; and <https://github.com/thoth-pub/thoth/wiki/BIBFRAME-2.0>

In Year 3, Thoth will seek to implement additional metadata fields as well as changes to metadata exports such as ONIX 3.1.2 that cater to incoming legislation and related reporting needs as mandated by the European Union, such as the EU's new General Product Safety Regulation (GPSR), EU Deforestation Act, and Accessibility Act legislations.

					<p>Note about change in timeline for WP5 deliverables: See explanation above (in notes accompanying deliverable A5.1)</p>
Year 2					
5. Accessibility	(A5.3) 2 knowledge-exchange workshops with publishers on accessibility standards implementation	(D5.3a) 1 interim blog post on accessibility standard implementation	May-25	Completed	<p>Knowledge-exchange workshops with publishers Rather than holding 2 workshops with multiple publishers, the Work Package has held multiple knowledge-exchange consultations with several publishers individually, to learn more about their implementation of accessibility standards and their needs. In Year 2, consultation meetings have been held with 7 small- to medium-sized presses, with a further 5 planned. [Names of publishers redacted]</p> <p>Rather than hosting 2 large workshops with multiple publishers in attendance (who will each have different production workflows), WP5 has elected to begin by consulting with publishers more closely, and on an on-going, iterative basis. A series of one-to-one meetings, surveys and consultations is helping to guide the WP's development of resources for publishers. The consultation process will snowball: and by Year 3, the WP will be supporting at least 5 publishers to use the accessibility resources launched under the OBF project (see KPI D5.4 below).</p> <p>1 interim blog post on accessibility standard implementation at publishers Fitzpatrick, J., & Findanis, J. (2025). "Accessibility standard implementation and OA publishers". <i>Copim</i>. https://copim.pubpub.org/pub/accessibility-publishers</p> <p>The WP has kept detailed records of its consultations with publishers, however these minutes will not be shared publicly as they may contain confidential material. Instead, the WP has summarised the findings of its consultations in an interim blog post, which will be continually versioned and updated over the coming months.</p> <p>Note about change in timeline for WP5 deliverables: See explanation above (in notes accompanying deliverable A5.1)</p>

5. Accessibility	(A5.3) See above	(D5.3b) Guidance on accessibility standards implementation (online toolkit)	May-25	In progress - delayed	<p>A Knowledge Base, including multiple guidance documents and tool kits, is currently under-development, and is being informed by consultation with publishers and librarians (see KPI A5.1 & A5.3 above). The resulting materials have been drafted, and will be made available on the CopimCompass InfoHub early in Year 3. So far, the WP has developed guidance on: Open Accessibility, Legislation and Standards.</p> <p>Note about change in timeline for WP5 deliverables: See explanation above (in notes accompanying deliverable A5.1)</p>
Year 3					
5. Accessibility	(A5.4) Service/software to improve accessibility compliance released	(D5.4) 5 publishers using service tool	May-26	In progress	The WP team has begun developing an Accessibility Maturity Modelling tool enabling publishers to assess the accessibility of their existing publications, design strategies to improve accessibility and to monitor and record these improvements over time.
5. Accessibility	(A5.5) Promote service/software via at least 1 workshop and conference presentations	(D5.5) 1 workshop & conference presentations to present and promote service/software	May-26	Not started	
WP6: Experimental Publishing					
Year 1					
6. Experimental Publishing	(A6.1) 1 workshop scoping experimental publishing		May-24	Completed	Workshop took place on 15 Jan 2024 and took the form of a 'matchmaking workshop', bringing together applicants for the pilot projects with invited publishers, and platform/software providers (further details below). The work of WP6 on COPIM and OBF was also presented.

	futures with 5+ OA publishers				<p>Workshop details Title: Experimental Publishing Book Pilots Matchmaking Workshop Date: 15 Jan 2024, 3pm-6:45pm [GMT] Location: Online Participating organisations: authors and project teams (17 proposed pilot projects presenting), platforms and presses No. of participants: around 40 Report/written reflections on event: Adema, J. (Mar 2024). “Matchmaking Workshop Experimental Book Publishing Pilots”. <i>Copim</i>. https://copim.pubpub.org/pub/matchmaking</p>
6. Experimental Publishing	(A6.2) With WP2 develop processes to allocate funding for the WP6 pilots as part of the grant allocation pilot	(D6.2) 3 pilot projects on experimental publishing assessed through the grant allocation pilot and launched	May-24	Completed	<p>3 pilot projects on experimental publishing were launched in Apr 2024. Further details of each of the selected projects can be found in the following announcements posted on PubPub:</p> <p>Kiesewetter, R. (Apr 2024). “Launch of Experimental Book Publishing Pilot Project ‘Servpub – A Collective Infrastructure to Serve and Publish’”. <i>Copim</i>. https://copim.pubpub.org/pub/servpub-book-launch</p> <p>McHardy, J. (Apr 2024). “Launch of Experimental Book Publishing Pilot Project ‘Deep Maps: Blue Humanities’”. <i>Copim</i>. https://copim.pubpub.org/pub/launching-deep-maps</p> <p>Adema, J. (Apr 2024). “Launch of Experimental Book Publishing Pilot Project ‘Database as Book’”. <i>Copim</i>. https://copim.pubpub.org/pub/database-book-launch</p> <p>The call for applicants for these experimental book pilot projects closed on 22 Nov 2023: McHardy, J., Kiesewetter, R., Bowie, S., & Adema, J. (Oct 2023). “CALL FOR PROPOSALS: EXPERIMENTAL BOOK PILOT PROJECTS”. <i>Copim</i>. https://copim.pubpub.org/pub/expub-pilot-call The call was also accompanied by detailed additional guidance to support applicants: Adema, J. (2023). “Open Call for Experimental Publishing Pilots: Background Information to Support your Application”. <i>Copim</i>. https://copim.pubpub.org/pub/expub-pilot-faqs</p> <p>The opportunity was disseminated via a thorough outreach plan, and the call for applicants became the second most-viewed publication on the Copim PubPub site, with over 3,200 views. Thanks to the widespread promotion of the call, the work package received nearly 50 applications, and 22 of these passed an initial ‘key criteria’ check.</p>

					<p>Many of the projects that applied did not have full teams consisting of a press, an author or group of authors, and a technology provider (a requirement for submission of final proposals on 1 Feb), so the WP facilitated a matchmaking process with potential partners in the form of a workshop (see workshop described above). The WP also actively supported the proposed projects with their applications to ensure they met the eligibility criteria before full submission.</p> <p>Working together with WP2 the WP drafted assessment criteria and procedures and set up an assessment panel consisting of representatives of the WP6 team, the OBC Board of Stewards, and OBC members. Full submission of proposals was due 1 Feb and the assessment panel took place 12 Feb. 3 successful projects were selected, and subaward agreements were signed with the aid of CU and Lancaster legal teams. Successful pilots were also established on CU's finance systems to allow for them to be provided with funds.</p>
Year 2					
6. Experimental Publishing	(A6.3) 1 outreach event to promote Experimental Publishing Compendium to authors and publishers		May-25	Completed	<p>The Experimental Publishing Compendium was officially launched 1 Dec 2023 (after the launch of a beta version in Apr 2023). Since then, multiple outreach events and strategies have been used to promote the Compendium.</p> <p>In Year 2, the WP hosted two "Experimental Publishing in Practice Seminars":</p> <p>Experimental Publishing in Practice - Seminar 01: Manifold Date: 21 November 2024 Speakers: Terence Smyre (Manifold) and Matthew Gold (CUNY) with author Whitney Trettien (University of Pennsylvania) Organisers: Co-organised with post-Publishing strand at the CPC (Coventry University) Event page: https://compendium.copim.ac.uk/practice_seminars & https://copim.pubpub.org/pub/practiceseminars Recording: https://archive.org/details/Experimental_Publishing_Seminar_01</p> <p>Experimental Publishing in Practice - Seminar 02: Hypothes.is</p>

				<p>Date: 16 January 2025 Speakers: Remi Kalir (Duke University) with Sonja Visser (Hypothes.is) and Janneke Adema (Open Humanities Press) Organisers: Co-organised with post-Publishing strand at the CPC (Coventry University) Event page: https://compendium.copim.ac.uk/practice_seminars & https://copim.pubpub.org/pub/practiceseminars Recording: https://archive.org/details/Experimental_Publishing_Seminar_02</p> <p>WP6 also co-organised a workshop on archiving workflows for experimental monographs: Archiving Workflows for Experimental Monographs: an OBF Workshop Date: 3 March 2025 Location: Online Participating organisations: Joint workshop with WP6, and colleagues from British Library & Jisc. Attendees included several university-based presses and several scholar-led OA monograph presses at varying levels of size and experience. [Report on event's findings below]. Report on event: Barnes, M. (2025). "Archiving Workflows for Experimental Monographs: an OBF Workshop." <i>Copim</i>. https://doi.org/10.21428/785a6451.bc3b5a71</p> <p>The WP has also organised a forthcoming pilot project event (with a further two events planned for October & December): Markdown, dive deep: A hybrid online session exploring Markdown & publishing for deep mapping Date: 23 May 2025 Location: Online & Koninklijke Bibliotheek in Den Haag Organisers: Open Book Futures Experimental Publishing Group. Event page: McHardy, J. (2025). "Markdown, dive deep". <i>Copim</i>. https://copim.pubpub.org/pub/markdown-dive-deep</p> <p>WP6 was also invited to discuss the Compendium in meetings with Utrecht University Library, the Alan Turing Institute, Northumbria University Library, and at a workshop of the Multimodal Appreciation project (Berlin). WP6 also presented the Compendium at a roundtable on Experimenting with Academic Knowledge Production at 4S/EASST in Amsterdam in Jul 2024, and it was included at the Mattering Press</p>
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					<p>bookstand at the conference (https://x.com/matteringpress/status/1813594049955393769). The Compendium also featured in the cross-project poster presented at the OASAPA 2024 conference in Lisbon (https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13694568).</p> <p>In August 2024, Janneke Adema delivered a keynote presentation at the University of Copenhagen, which highlighted the compendium, and was entitled: 'Experimental Publishing as a Critical Praxis: Rethinking Distinctions between Research and Publishing' (Slides available: https://www.openreflections.org/?page_id=1709)</p> <p>WP6 has also participated in many more conferences and webinars in Year 1 and 2 of the project (see full list of events online [https://copim.pubpub.org/pub/open-book-futures-outreach] and in appendix of Year 2 report).</p> <p>Other outreach activity has included:</p> <p>Online promotion of compendium</p> <p>The launch of the Compendium was promoted with a blog post: Adema, J. (Dec 2023). "Official Launch of the Experimental Publishing Compendium". <i>Copim</i>. https://copim.pubpub.org/pub/compendium-launch</p> <p>Initial promotion of the launch also included mailing list announcements, and a festive 'calendar' of tweets/toots (one released every day throughout Dec 2023). A promotional video showcasing the Compendium was also published: Bowie, S. (2024). "A brief walkthrough of the Experimental Publishing Compendium". <i>Copim</i>. https://copim.pubpub.org/pub/compendium-video</p> <p>Nomination for the Digital Humanities Awards</p> <p>The compendium was nominated for the DH Awards 2023: Adema, J. (Mar 2024). "The Experimental Publishing Compendium Receives a Digital Humanities Awards 2023 Nomination". <i>Copim</i>. https://copim.pubpub.org/pub/dhawards.</p>
6. Experimental Publishing	(A6.4) Documentation methods for pilots developed	(D6.4) Open documentation of the pilots	May-25	Completed	<p>Documentation methods for pilots developed</p> <p>Each pilot project shared its open documentation methods in a blog post:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Adema, J. (2024). "Documenting Database as Book and Lively Community Archive". <i>Copim</i>. https://copim.pubpub.org/pub/documentingdatabase

2. Kiesewetter, R., & Bowie, S. (2024). "Documenting 'Servpub – A Collective Infrastructure to Serve and Publish". *Copim*.
<https://copim.pubpub.org/pub/pilot-project-documentation-servpub2>
3. Bowie, S., McHardy, J., & Smith, J. L. (2024). "Deep Maps: Monographs 'n' Markdown". *Copim*.
<https://doi.org/10.21428/785a6451.fd1f9fe1>

Open documentation of the pilots

Pilot project progress has been documented via regular blog posts:

Database as Book

1. Adema, J. (2024). "Launch of Experimental Book Publishing Pilot Project Database as Book". *Copim*.
<https://copim.pubpub.org/pub/database-book-launch>
2. Adema, J. (2024). "What is a Database Book?" *Copim*.
<https://copim.pubpub.org/pub/what-is-a-database-book>
3. Kiesewetter, R. (2025). "More Than a Moment: The Practice of Getting Together". *Copim*.
<https://copim.pubpub.org/pub/database-as-book-on-gathering>

DeepMaps

1. McHardy, J. (2024). "Launch of Experimental Book Publishing Pilot Project 'Deep Maps: Blue Humanities'". *Copim*.
<https://copim.pubpub.org/pub/launching-deep-maps>
2. McHardy, J. (2025). "Markdown, dive deep". *Copim*.
<https://copim.pubpub.org/pub/markdown-dive-deep>
3. Bowie, Simon, James Louis Smith, and Julien McHardy. (2025). "Deep Maps: Experimenting with Peer Review." *Copim*, March.
<https://copim.pubpub.org/pub/deep-maps-peer-review>.

ServPub

1. Kiesewetter, R. (2024). "Launch of Experimental Book Publishing Pilot Project 'Servpub – A Collective Infrastructure to Serve and Publish'". *Copim*.
<https://copim.pubpub.org/pub/servpub-book-launch>
2. Bowie, S. (2025). "Embodied and embedded publishing infrastructure on ServPub". *Copim*.
<https://doi.org/10.21428/785a6451.4b371366>

6. Experimental Publishing	(A6.5) Scoping of extended Compendium governance structure	(D6.5) Extended Compendium governance structure implemented	May-25	Completed	<p>In October 2024, the Experimental Publishing Group presented to the project's Advisory Board & asked for recommendations and advice on developing a governance structure for the Compendium. A report scoping governance structures was published in February 2025 (see below, Deliverable A6.5).</p> <p>Actions have been implemented to put governance structures in place.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Formation of an Editorial Oversight Group: • Formation of a Compendium Advisory Community • Preparation of Editorial Policy • Preparation of Terms of Engagement and Code of Conduct: <p>The new governance structures will be outlined in a blog post. The inaugural meetings of the Editorial Oversight Group and Advisory Community will be held in the first three months of Year 3.</p>
6. Experimental Publishing	(A6.5 continued) See above	(D6.6) Scoping report published	May-25	Completed	<p>Scoping report published on Zenodo & PubPub in February 2025:</p> <p>The Experimental Publishing Group (2025). "Developing a Governance Model for the Experimental Publishing Compendium - Scoping Report". <i>Copim</i>. https://copim.pubpub.org/pub/compendiumgovernancescoping</p> <p>Adema, J. (2025). "Developing a Governance Model for the Experimental Publishing Compendium". <i>Zenodo</i>. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14802273</p>
6. Experimental Publishing	(A6.6) Scoping of expansion and integration of the Compendium as OBC service		May-25	Completed	<p>In Year 2, WP6 scoped the expansion and integration of the Compendium as an OBC service. The WP prepared a draft white paper to present to the OBC management and Board in 2025.</p>
Year 3					
6. Experimental	(A6.7) Pilot projects concluded	(D6.7) 3 experimental books & 1 research article	May-26	In progress	<p>1 x Research Article</p> <p>Adema, J. (accepted/in press). "Promoting Interactions and Engagement with Scholarly Research: Speculations on the Role of the Librarian in Advancing Experimental Publishing", in A. Mfengu and J.</p>

Publishing					<p>Raju (eds.), <i>Advancing Social Justice Through Curriculum Realignment: Centering Scholarly Communication in LIS Curricula</i> (Capetown: University of Capetown Press, 2024)</p> <p>See also, this article reflecting on research and pilots developed under the COPIM (2019-2023) project:</p> <p>Janneke Adema (2024) 'Experimental Publishing as Collective Struggle. Providing Imaginaries for Posthumanist Knowledge Production', Special Issue <i>Publishing After Progress</i> guest-edited by Rebekka Kiesewetter. <i>Culture Machine</i>. Vol. 23. https://culturemachine.net/vol-23-publishing-after-progress/adema-experimental-publishing-collective-struggle/</p>
6. Experimental Publishing	(A6.8) Pilot projects fully integrated with other OBC services/tools	(D6.8) Full documentation of 3 Pilot projects	May-26	Not started	
6. Experimental Publishing	(A6.9) Development and expansion of ExPub Compendium finalised	(D6.9) 1 event with authors and publishers to promote ExPub Compendium	May-26	Not started	
WP7: Archiving & Digital Preservation					
Year 1					
7. Archiving & Digital Preservation	(A7.1) Increase number of repositories involved in the Thoth Archiving Network	(D7.1) At least 3 new UK/US repositories involved in Thoth Archiving Network	May-24	Completed	<p>Thoth Archiving Network now involves 4 UK/US repositories:</p> <p>1) Internet Archive – automated feed: https://archive.org/details/thoth-archiving-network</p> <p>2) Loughborough University, Fig Share – automated feed: https://repository.lboro.ac.uk/Thoth_Archiving_Network</p> <p>3) University of Cambridge, D-Space – https://thoth-arch.lib.cam.ac.uk/home</p> <p>4) Zenodo – pilot automated feed</p>

					<p>(https://sandbox.zenodo.org/communities/thoth/records?q=&l=list&p=1&s=10&sort=newest)</p> <p>Expanding this network has proved challenging: with each new repository demanding new processes, specifications and rounds of testing and reconfiguration. However, in its current form, the network now offers a secure and accessible option for OA presses seeking to archive their books for future readers.</p>
7. Archiving & Digital Preservation	(A7.2) Working with existing national library networks and the Digital Preservation Coalition, identify and engage with new national library stakeholders	(D7.2) At least 5 national libraries involved in discussion about requirements for OA books archiving/preservation	May-24	Completed	<p>WP7 founded the National Libraries Network, which currently has 6 members (Qatar National Library, [REDACTED], British Library, National Library of Scotland, National Library of the Netherlands and German National Library) who are invited to quarterly meetings. The WP is also in touch with other National Libraries who have expressed an interest in being involved, including Library and Archives Canada</p> <p>The network has been established to discuss the requirements and challenges of archiving/preserving OA books. Discussions take place during regular online meetings and asynchronously via a Teams space. Meetings were held in Sep 2023, Jan 2024 and Apr 2024.</p>
7. Archiving & Digital Preservation	(A7.3) 1 workshop scoping archiving challenges of small/scholar-led presses	(D7.3) White paper/report published on archiving challenges	May-24	Completed	<p><u>White paper/report on archiving challenges</u> Rather than 1 long report, WP7 have produced 2 reports highlighting different archiving challenges:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Barnes, M., & Cole, G. (2024). Metadata: Archiving challenges for small publishers series. <i>Copim</i>. https://doi.org/10.21428/785a6451.3041c8b7 2. Barnes, M., & Cole, G. (2024). Existing pathways to preservation: Archiving challenges for small publishers series. <i>Copim</i>. https://doi.org/10.21428/785a6451.a5d57088 <p>In addition, the WP has drafted a report on Legal Deposit practices within the European Research Area as part of a collaborative effort with PALOMERA (forthcoming).</p> <p><u>Workshop scoping archiving challenges for small/scholar-led presses</u> Title: Publishing Workshop: Accessibility, Archiving and Metadata (hosted in collaboration with WP 5 & 7) Date: 27 November 2024 Location: online Participating organisations: Ext: Open Press at the University of</p>

					<p>Sussex, University of London Press, Scottish Universities Press, LSE Press, Graz University Library Publishing, meson press, L'Harmattan Publishing House, University of Groningen Press, mediastudies.press, Mattering Press, TU Delft Open Publishing, Maastricht University Int.: Open Book Publishers, Loughborough University Library, Lancaster University Library, Thoth Open Metadata, punctum books,</p> <p>No. of participants: 30</p> <p>Slides: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14620187 (Accessibility); https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14673216 (Archiving)</p> <p>Further documentation of event: Steiner, T., Fitzpatrick, J., Barnes, M., Hillen, H., & Gatti, R. (2025). "Accessibility, Archiving, and Open Metadata - A Copim Publishers' Workshop". <i>Copim</i>. https://doi.org/10.21428/785a6451.a1803fe6</p> <p>Note on delay to this deliverable Completion of this success criteria was delayed due to other WP deliverables requiring greater time and resource than originally planned (see A7.1 above). Moreover, a period of extended staff absence due to illness has delayed progress further.</p>
Year 2					
7. Archiving & Digital Preservation	(A7.4) Further increase number of UK/US repositories in the preservation network	(D7.4a) At least 5 participating repositories	May-25	Completed	<p>Deliverable marked as 'Completed' as Archiving network has now grown to a desirable number of participating repositories, allowing WP7 to meet its core project objectives. This number of repositories is lower than initially targeted and we offer an explanation for this below.</p> <p>Thoth Open Archiving Network currently has 4 participating repositories:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Internet Archive – an automated feed: https://archive.org/details/thoth-archiving-network 2. Zenodo – pilot automated feed: https://sandbox.zenodo.org/communities/thoth/records?q=&l=list&p=1&s=10&sort=newest 3. Loughborough University, Fig Share – an automated feed: https://repository.lboro.ac.uk/Thoth_Archiving_Network 4. University of Cambridge, D-Space – piloting automated deposits: https://thoth-arch.lib.cam.ac.uk/home (See also: https://unlockingresearch-blog.lib.cam.ac.uk/?p=3992)

However, going forward, the Archiving Network will focus on 2 participating repositories only: Internet Archive and Zenodo. We believe that this is the best way for WP7 to meet its “overarching aim” (as set out in our initial project bid): “to provide a major contribution to efforts to ensure long term preservation of open access content, freely available not just to academics but also the wider public”.

Rationale behind enhancing and growing the Thoth Open Archiving Network in ways other than increasing the number of repositories :

In consultation with publishers, libraries and other stakeholders the WP undertook a thorough review of the needs and technical requirements for the development of an effective and efficient **open** archiving process for open access content. The concept of an open archive that emerged from this process is an innovative development that we believe will be an important outcome of the WP. By an open archive we mean not only the archiving of open access content, but also ensuring the archived content is openly accessible and that the whole archiving process itself is openly verifiable – including making public checksums, version control, and the processes by which these were checked/maintained etc. Existing archiving solutions make one or all of these components dark to users.

Important outcomes of the consultation and scoping process were:

- a. defining the technical requirements for an archiving process to be open – in the broad sense outlined above.
- b. Identifying effective and efficient mechanisms for achieving those requirements.

In addition to the technical requirement for open archiving we also identified additional desirable features for the open archiving of open access scholarly works, which included: strategies to ensure urls within titles, together with research material associated with the work, can be archived alongside the title itself; and the desirability that where possible archived content is also maintained within repository ecosystems outside the control of private or government controlled entities.

We now recognise that a viable open archiving network that satisfied all these requirements could be achieved via the coordinated archiving of content in two open general repositories (Internet Archive and Zenodo).

				<p>With these 2 participating repositories, the Thoth Open Archiving Network will allow publishers to automatically archive their publications in a robust way, thereby filling a significant gap in preservation infrastructure. The initiative will meet the needs of its users, by safeguarding publishers against the risk of complete loss of their catalogue, thereby supporting the long-term accessibility and preservation of scholarly works for readers: as set out in our initial project objectives.</p> <p>When the project bid was initially developed, WP7 aimed to expand the preservation network to 5 repositories in year 2 and 10 in year 3. However, following the extensive scoping & workshopping described above it has become clear that introducing open archiving objectives actually achieves a broader set of deliverables than would have been possible via the originally proposed network.</p> <p>The work involved in establishing the inclusion of just 4 repositories has been extensive and time-consuming, as each institution has particular collection requirements and technical specifications that require careful navigation. Moreover, research conducted by WP7 suggests that increasing the number of repositories further would not add sufficient value to justify the labour. Extra deposit locations would not greatly decrease the risk of file loss, and any small benefit is out-weighed by the time, labour and environmental costs involved in adding extra repositories.</p> <p>Our decision to focus on 2 generalist repositories – and to ultimately exclude the 2 university repositories we have worked with in Year 1 & Year 2 of the project—is a decision that has emerged from extensive research. Our findings suggest that, from an archiving perspective, university repositories do not offer an ideal solution, as individual universities are often unable to commit to offering open-ended and long-term archiving in their repositories. Moreover, our pilot has revealed that university repositories are not presently set up – either technically or managerially- to easily accept deposits from third parties via an api. Together, this means that the labour and cost needed to maintain and expand a network of repositories would be significant and ongoing. We will be reporting these findings in a forthcoming paper.</p> <p>Instead of expanding the number of repositories, the team is now focusing its efforts on increasing the services and protections offered by the network. Thus, the final product will do more than initially targeted, but with fewer repositories than initially envisaged. Importantly, as part of the process WP7 is creating the technical definition and needs for an</p>
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					open archiving solution - where not only is the content and metadata openly available, but so are the data and processes to ensure the validity of the content. In addition the code created to enable api deposits to Figshare and DSpace repositories is open source and can be reutilised for other purposes and by others. Thoth is already utilising this code for delivery to the OAPEN library (which is hosted on a DSpace repository) and will look to introduce a customised content delivery service to other similar repositories.
7. Archiving & Digital Preservation	(A7.4) See above	(D7.4b) Inclusion of at least 2 non-UK/US presses in repository archiving networks	May-25	Completed	<p>Target exceeded by 100%.</p> <p>In Year 2, four non-UK/US presses were enrolled in Thoth Open Archiving Network workflows, meaning that their works will now be preserved in the network:</p> <p>Adocs Bokförlaget Stolpe L'Harmattan Open Access Paideia Publishing Services</p> <p>More will be added as publishers sign up to Thoth Plus services.</p>
7. Archiving & Digital Preservation	(A7.5) Informal National Libraries' network with at least 5 members on OA books archiving established	(D7.5) Blog post on establishment of informal national libraries network	May-25	Completed	<p>National Libraries Network has 7 members:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Qatar National Library, 2. British Library, 3. National Library of Scotland, 4. National Library of the Netherlands 5. German National Library 6. Library and Archives Canada 7. A further institution has participated in conversations, but wishes to remain anonymous & does not wish to be listed as an official member of the NLN in public documentation. <p>Quarterly meetings were held throughout Year 1 & 2.</p> <p>Blog post on establishing the network Barnes, M. (2024). "The OBF National Libraries Network: a summary of our first year". <i>Copim</i>. https://doi.org/10.21428/785a6451.dd03d609</p>
7. Archiving & Digital Preservation	(A7.6) 1 workshop on archiving/preservation workflows for	(D7.6) Publication of 3 reports on experimental book archiving,	May-25	Completed	<p>Archiving Workflows for Experimental Monographs: an OBF Workshop Date: 3 March 2025 Location: Online Participating organisations: Joint workshop with WP6, and colleagues</p>

	smaller publishers & experimental books, supported by the Digital Preservation Coalition	PhD theses and 'link rot'			<p>from British Library & Jisc. Attendees included several university-based presses and several scholar-led OA monograph presses at varying levels of size and experience. [Report on event's findings below].</p> <p>Report 1: Experimental book archiving Barnes, M. (2025). "Archiving Workflows for Experimental Monographs: an OBF Workshop." <i>Copim</i>. https://doi.org/10.21428/785a6451.bc3b5a71</p> <p>Notes: In addition, a poster on "The challenges of archiving experimental and practice-based scholarly works" was also presented at "Born-Digital Collections, Archives and Memory" conference (2 April 2025). Link: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15221938</p> <p>Report 2: PhD Theses Thoth Open Archiving Network Higman, R., Cole, G., Gatti, R., Arias, J., Steiner, T., Stokes, P., Wheatley, P., Barnes, M., & McGann, C. (2025). "Putting the 'Open' in 'Thoth Open Archiving Network'". <i>Copim</i>. https://doi.org/10.21428/785a6451.76e96572</p> <p>Notes: In Year 2 & Year 3, WP7 is already publishing several reports on PhD theses: cf. D7.7 and D7.13, and these publications will comprehensively record and share the WP's research and recommendations on this topic. As such, the WP felt it would be more beneficial to publish a report on the Thoth Open Archiving Network in Year 2. As discussed in the rationale for D7.4a, the WP has conducted a lot of scoping and assessment work, and has many findings and reflections to share on the requirements and necessity of building an open archiving network.</p> <p>Report 3: Link rot Barnes, M., & Cole, G. (2024). "Link rot: Archiving challenges for small publishers series". <i>Copim</i>. https://doi.org/10.21428/785a6451.4ce69019</p>
7. Archiving & Digital Preservation	(A7.7) Scoping of PhD thesis archiving/preservation practices	(D7.7) Blog post on PhD thesis scoping work	May-25	Completed	<p>Blog post on PhD thesis scoping work: Barnes, M. (2025). "Scoping PhD Theses: Some initial reflections". <i>Copim</i>. https://doi.org/10.21428/785a6451.d98f9a16</p> <p>Notes: WP7 has held consultations with several libraries (the Bodleian Library, Oxford; Queens University, Belfast; Lancaster University Library) gathering information on their PhD thesis archiving and preservation practices. This research was compiled to form this initial</p>

					blog post, with further research shaping a report to be published in Year 3 (in fulfilment of D7.13).
7. Archiving & Digital Preservation	(A7.8) Addressing 'link rot' challenge inc. proposal to change PDF/A standard	(D7.8) Blog post or report on proposal to change PDF/A standard and link rot challenge	May-25	In progress - delayed	<p>Notes on delay to Year 2 deliverable</p> <p>This work on changes to PDF/A standards and the challenges of link rot requires input from the Digital Preservation Coalition, who will be acting as a consultant in the preparation of the blog post. Unfortunately, WP7's key contact at the DPC has been on secondment for several months in Year 2, delaying this deliverable. This work will now be prioritised in Year 3 of the project.</p> <p>Conversations have been had with DPC about scope and resource requirements.</p>
Year 3					
7. Archiving & Digital Preservation	(A7.9) Further increase the number of UK/US repositories in the preservation network	(D7.9a) 10 participating repositories	May-26	Not started	<p>Rather than increasing to 10 participating repositories, TOAN will be extended and improved by implementing open archiving features across the network, e.g. introduce public checksums.</p> <p>Cf. Higman, R., Cole, G., Gatti, R., Arias, J., Steiner, T., Stokes, P., Wheatley, P., Barnes, M., & McGann, C. (2025). "Putting the 'Open' in 'Thoth Open Archiving Network'". <i>Copim</i>. https://doi.org/10.21428/785a6451.76e96572</p>
7. Archiving & Digital Preservation	(A7.9) See above	(D7.9b) 1 report on funding, technical and administrative needs for a National Libraries archiving network	May-26	In progress	<p>WP7 has established a working methodology to present to the National Libraries, towards scoping the technical and administrative requirements that would be necessary to implement a theoretical "archiving network" among the National Libraries. A series of guided workshops is planned to consult with National Libraries. WP7 members have held the first of these workshops with colleagues at the British Library (held on 23 January 2025). This workshop was run as a pilot to test the methodology used (process mapping and workflows) but also to get the relevant information from British Library colleagues. We already have agreement in principle from two other national libraries to hold a similar workshop with them and will arrange details. The outcomes of these workshops will also feed into A/D7.11. This work will form a key part of a new RA's role (recruited April 2025)</p>
7. Archiving & Digital	(A7.10) Open Educational Resources	(D7.10) OER Training	May-26	In progress	<p>Scoping has begun and discussions are underway with the DPC, who will be helping to create these OERs.</p>

Preservation	(OER), including training materials for authors, publishers and libraries on archiving & preservation practices around PhD theses finalised	materials published			
7. Archiving & Digital Preservation	(A7.11) Recommendations for national and international policy makers finalised	(D7.11) 1 report on recommendations for national and international policy makers	May-26	Not started	
7. Archiving & Digital Preservation	(A7.12) Toolkit with recommendations & software for small presses finalised	(D7.12) Toolkit for small presses published	May-26	Not started	
7. Archiving & Digital Preservation	(A7.13) Research on archiving and preservation of PhD theses concluded	(D7.13) 1 report on archiving of PhD theses published	May-26	In progress	

9.3 Materials and open access

Bibliography of materials and papers produced (1 May 2023-30 April 2025), and statistics about their use where available. Nb. all usage figures are total views since publication, except for PubPub posts. PubPub introduced a new analytics system in March 2024, so figures for PubPub posts only include views from 1 March 2024—4 May 2025 (for views before 1 March 2024 see Year 1 report).

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9.4 Events organised and attended

This list documents the project team's contributions to external events (e.g. presentations at conferences) and events organised by the project (e.g. webinars and workshops). Wherever possible we make our slides available online (see 'Further details' column for links). An online, public version of this list is also available here: <https://copim.pubpub.org/pub/open-book-futures-outreach>

Date	Title of presentation/poster	Event	Presenter(s)/ participants	Further details
Q8 (February 2025—April 2025)				
16 Apr 2025	Building an Open Monographs Future: How the Library Community can help create a more equitable OA Ecosystem	RLUK Annual Conference	Kevin Sanders (w/ Sarah Thompson (York), Andrew Barker (Lancaster), Silke Davison (OAPEN), Ruth MacMullen (Bodl., Oxford), Bethany Logan (Sussex))	Event page: https://rlukconference.com/ Slides: N/A Notes: 30-40 attendees
10-11 Apr 2025		Radical Open Access III: From Openness to Social Justice Activism	Co-organisers of event: Janneke Adema, Rebekka Kiesewetter, Samuel Moore, Toby Steiner	Event page: https://radicaloa.postdigitalcultures.org/conferences/radicaloa3/ Slides: N/A
4 Apr 2025	The challenges of archiving experimental and practice-based scholarly works	Born-Digital Collections, Archives and Memory conference (London, UK)	Gareth Cole	Event page: https://www.sas.ac.uk/borndigital2025 https://easychair.org/smart-program/BDCAM25/index.html
3 Apr 2025	African OA Books Network: Inaugural meeting	Copim webinar	Organised by Rupert Gatti. Attended by c. 10 others	Event page: N/A Slides: N/A
2-5 Apr 2025	Open Book Collective Exhibition Stand	ACRL conference	Livy Snyder	Event page: https://www.ala.org/events/acrl-2025-conference

				Slides: N/A
31 Mar- 2 Apr 2025	Copim Community Exhibition Stand	UKSG		Event page: https://www.uksg.org/uksg-annual-conference-2025-programme/
31 Mar- 2 Apr 2025	It's Nice, but is it sustainable? Rethinking sustainability for Diamond open access infrastructures and funding models	UKSG	Joe Deville, Tom Grady, Caroline Edwards, Rupert Gatti, Niels Stern	Event page: https://www.uksg.org/uksg-annual-conference-2025-programme/ Slides: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15189001
26 Mar 2025	Creating Community-Owned Futures for Open Access Books by Scaling Small and Co-designing Governance	MetaGovernance Seminar	Janneke Adema	Event page: https://researchseminars.org/seminar/Metagov Slides: [tbc] Recording: https://archive.org/search.php?query=creator%3A%22Metagovernance%20Seminar%22
21 Mar 2025	No Open Access without Open Infrastructure. Five Open Infrastructures Supporting Diamond OA for Books	Swiss Diamond OA workshop (Bern, CH)	Jordy Findanis, Kira Hopkins, Toby Steiner	Event page: https://www.openscience.uzh.ch/en/scholarly-publishing-and-open-access/publishing-at-uzh/scholar-led-publishing/plato/News/DOA_WorkshopDay.html Slides: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15094205
20 Mar 2025	Beyond Paywalls: Librarians Re-imagining Open Access	Lancaster University Webinar	Jo Fitzpatrick	Event page: https://lancaster-uk.libcal.com/calendar/libraryevents/beyondpaywalls Slides: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15221690 Recording: https://archive.org/details/beyond_paywalls
20 Mar 2025	Metadata, standards and platforms for open access books: good metadata practice with Thoth	OABN & OIPA Good Metadata Practice webinar (online)	Hannah Hillen & Toby Steiner	Event page: https://oipauk.org/news-events-and-blog/events/ Slides: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15048076 See also: Graham Bell slides: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15168234

				Notes: 200+ registrations
19 Mar 2025	Building an Open Monographs Future	RLUK Conference	Kevin Sanders (+ Andrew Barker and Silke Davison)	Event page: https://site.pheedloop.com/event/RLUK25/schedule?date=2025-03-19 Slides: N/A
11 Mar 2025	Choosing Open Access for Books: Myths and Truths Beyond the BPC	Oxford Forum of Open Scholarship 2025 (OxFOS25)	Judith Fathallah	Event page: https://openaccess.ox.ac.uk/oxfos25 Slides: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15012232
10 Mar 2025	Why OtF Might Work For Your Press	Association of University Presses OA Committee meeting	Tom Grady & Kira Hopkins	Event page: N/A Slides: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15188924
7 Mar 2025	Unlocking Knowledge Through Open Access: The What, Why & How of OA for Books	Library Association of Ireland Open Scholarship Group	Tom Grady	Event page: https://www.eventbrite.ie/e/unlocking-knowledge-through-open-access-tickets-1223694526269 Slides: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15188864 Notes: 100+ attendees
4 Mar 2025	Exploring the Experimental Publishing Compendium: Tools, Practices, and Books to Promote the Publication of Experimental Scholarly Works, as part of the panel 'Economics and Experiments in Open Access Publishing'	Oxford Forum of Open Scholarship 2025 (OxFOS25)	Janneke Adema, with Martin Eve and Ronald Snijder	Event page: https://openaccess.ox.ac.uk/oxfos25 Slides: https://www.openreflections.org/?page_id=1709
3 Mar 2025	Experimental Book Archiving Workshop	Copim/WP6 & WP7 webinar	Experimental Publishing Group, WP7 (Archiving & Digital Preservation)	Report: https://doi.org/10.21428/785a6451.bc3b5a71 Participants: 15
3-13 Mar 2025	Introducing Copim at OxFOS25	Oxford Forum of Open Scholarship 2025 (OxFOS25)	Judith Fathallah	Event page: https://openaccess.ox.ac.uk/oxfos25 Poster: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14972895

25 Feb 2025	Avoiding the Seventy Year Itch: 'Transformative' Open Access via Diamond Funding Models	Researcher 2 Reader Conference (R2R)	Kira Hopkins, Rose Harris-Birtill	Event page: https://r2rconf.com/r2r-conference-programme/ Slides: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15188723
25 Feb 2025	Mapping OA Books in an African Context: project meeting		Copim, with SPARC Africa, Chinhoyi University of Technology, DOAB/OAPEN	Event page: N/A Slides: N/A
20 Feb 2025	Practical Applications of Open Infrastructure Tools for Scholarly Communication	OASPA Webinar	Vincent van Gerven Oei	Event page: https://www.oaspa.org/events/webinar-practical-applications-of-open-infrastructure-tools-for-scholarly-communication/ Slides: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15050568 Notes: 250+ registrations
17-19 Feb 2025	Thoth Open Archiving Network (TOAN) Update: Lessons Learned & New Directions	The 19th International Digital Curation Conference	Miranda Barnes	Event page: https://dcc.ac.uk/events/idcc25 Slides: [tbc]
Q7 (November 2024—January 2025)				
24 Jan 2025	The Future of OA Journals	Copim/WP2 & WP3 workshop	OBC, OtF, Open Library of Humanities	Event page: N/A Slides: N/A
21 Jan 2025	The Open Book Collective: current challenges for OA book publishing	The realities, challenges and future of open access publishing, University of York Open Research Webinar.	Kevin Sanders	Event page & slides: https://uoy.atlassian.net/wiki/spaces/YorkOpenResearch/pages/300352406/The+realities+challenges+and+future+of+open+access+publishing+Tuesday+21+January+2025 Recording: https://youtu.be/w09cy1a-Txo
16 Jan 2025	Experimental Publishing in Practice - Seminar 02: Hypothes.is	Copim/WP6 webinar	Speakers: Remi Kalir (Duke University) with Sonja Visser	Event page: https://compendium.copim.ac.uk/practice_seminars

			(Hypothes.is) and Janneke Adema (Open Humanities Press) Organisers: Post-Publishing strand at the CPC, WP6	Recording: https://archive.org/details/Experimental_Publishing_Seminar_02 Report on event: https://copim.pubpub.org/pub/practice-seminars-2
8 Jan 2025	Webinar for the F.O.R.M. Forum for Open Research in MENA	Copim webinar	OTF, Thoth, OBC, F.O.R.M	Event page: N/A Slides: N/A
9-10 Dec 2024	Open Monograph Publishing Workshop, hosted by Copim and Association of African Universities	2nd Global Summit on Diamond Open Access: Centering Social Justice in Scholarly Communication to Advance Research as a Public Good [University of Cape Town, South Africa]	Joe Deville, Judith Fathallah, Rupert Gatti, Vincent van Gerven Oei, Janneke Adema	Event page: https://doasummit.uct.ac.za/programme Slides and further information: https://openbookcollective.pubpub.org/pub/open-mongraph-publishing-workshop-at-the-2nd-global-summit-on-diamond-oa Notes: Organisations involved: African Minds, Association of African Universities, Coventry University, the Directory of Open Access Books/OAPEN, Lancaster University, Open Book Collective, Open Book Publishers, Public Knowledge Project, punctum books, Thoth Open Metadata, University of Cape Town Libraries, and University of Cape Town Press.
8-9 Dec 2024	Promoting Interactions and Engagement with Scholarly Research: Speculations on the Role of the Librarian in Advancing Experimental Publishing	DKIS Conference on Advancing Social Justice Through Curriculum Realignment: Centering Scholarly Communication in LIS Curricula [University of Cape Town, South Africa]	Janneke Adema	Event page: https://doasummit.uct.ac.za/dkis-conference-diamond-open-access Slides: [tbc]
6 Dec 2024	Open Book Hong Kong webinar	Copim webinar	OtF, OBC, Thoth, Open Book Hong Kong	Event page: N/A Slides: N/A

2-4 Dec 2024	Activities for Professionals International University and Academic Publishing Forum Workshop: Thoth Open Metadata	Guadalajara International Book Fair	Amanda Ramalho	Event page: https://www.fil.com.mx/ingles/prog/indice.asp Slides: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14259769
27 Nov 2024	Publishing Workshop: Accessibility, Archiving and Metadata		Open Book Publishers, Loughborough University Library, Lancaster University Library, Thoth Open Metadata, punctum books, publishers using Thoth: Open Press at the University of Sussex, University of London Press, Scottish Universities Press, LSE Press, Graz University Library Publishing, meson press, L'Harmattan Publishing House, University of Groningen Press, mediastudes.pres s, Mattering Press, TU Delft Open Publishing, Maastricht University	Slides: Accessibility: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14620187 Archiving: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14673216 Report on event: https://doi.org/10.21428/785a6451.a1803fe6
21 Nov 2024	Experimental Publishing in Practice - Seminar 01: Manifold	Copim/WP6 webinar	Speakers: Terence Smyre (Manifold) and Matthew Gold (CUNY) with author Whitney Trettien	Event page: https://compendium.copim.ac.uk/practice_seminars Report on event: https://copim.pubpub.org/pub/practiceseminars

			(University of Pennsylvania) Organisers: Post-Publishing strand at the CPC (Coventry University)	
20-21 Nov 2024	Cybersecurity and Censorship	UKSG (November conference)	Simon Bowie	Event page: https://www.uksg.org/events/novconf24/ Slides & edited transcript: https://opensauce.simonix.com/uksgnov2024/
14 Nov 2024 (3:20 – 4:00 PM EDT)	Open Access, Open Metadata, Open Archiving: Liberating Metadata Flows across the OA Landscape	Charleston Conference, 2024	Hannah Hillen, Livy Snyder, Lidia Uziel, Toby Steiner, Vincent W.J. van Gerven Oei	Event page: https://www.charleston-hub.com/the-charleston-conference/welcome/2024-preliminary-program/ Poster: https://zenodo.org/records/13960036
14 Nov 2024 (4:00-4:40 PM EDT)	Beyond the BPC: Collective Funding Model Experimentation and Challenges in Accelerating Sustainable OA Monographs	Charleston Conference, 2024	Tom Grady, Rebecca Seger (ITHAKA/JSTOR), Amy Harris, (MIT Press), Andrew Barker (Lancaster University Library)	Event page: https://www.charleston-hub.com/the-charleston-conference/welcome/2024-preliminary-program/ Slides: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14717134
13 Nov 2024	Whose Future Is It? Practical Strategies for Supporting Community-led Open Access Book Publishing	Charleston Conference, 2024	Livy Snyder	Event page: https://www.charleston-hub.com/the-charleston-conference/welcome/2024-preliminary-program/ Slides: N/A Notes: c. 70 participants. Co-organised by: punctum books, OBC (via Lidia Uziel, UCSB), CUNY, Queens College Graduate School of Library and Information Studies
13 Nov 2024	5 years of Copim. What has been done? What is still to do?	NAG Webinar	Joe Deville & Kira Hopkins	Slides & recording: https://nag.org.uk/development/copim/

6 Nov 2024	Thoth open metadata management and dissemination platform for open access books	EIFL Webinar	Toby Steiner	<p>Event page: https://eifl.net/resources/eifl-webinar-thoth-open-metadata-management-and-dissemination-platform-open-access-books</p> <p>Recording: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=C_s9xGbhrIM&feature=youtu.be</p> <p>Slides: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14044726</p>
Q6 (August 2024—October 2024)				
28 Oct 2024	Thoth Open Metadata - exploring library-facing extension workshop	Copim/Thoth workshop	Thoth, Manchester University Library, Loughborough U Library, Thoth Open Metadata, Penn State U Libraries, California Digital Library / COMET project	<p>Event page: N/A</p> <p>Slides: N/A</p>
24 Oct 2024	Getting out from the back of the sofa: Or, how can we achieve sustainable funding for Open Access books?	UKSG webinar	Tom Grady, Elaine Sykes	<p>Event page: https://www.uksg.org/events/webinar-getting-out-from-the-back-of-the-sofa/</p> <p>Slides: https://www.uksg.org/wp-content/uploads/2024/10/Tom-Grady-Elaine-Sykes-combined-UKSG-webinar-Oct-2024.pdf</p> <p>c. 350 registered attendees</p>
24 Oct 2024	Delivering Open Access for Books by Default: The role of community-led funding models and infrastructures	IOAP / OIPA Webinar	Joe Deville, Tom Grady, Toby Steiner	<p>Event page: https://ioapblog.blogspot.com/2024/09/ioap-and-oipa-webinar-ioap-and-oipa.html</p> <p>Slides: Deville: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14653011 Grady: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14673914</p>

				<p>Steiner: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13987019</p> <p>Notes: c. 150 registered attendees. c. 75 attendees on the day</p>
24 Oct 2024	The Open Book Collective and Collective Development Fund	OASPA Webinar: 'Sustainable Open Access Book Publishing in East Africa (Publishers' Forum)'	Judith Fathallah	<p>Event page:</p> <p>Slides: N/A</p> <p>Recording: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=YaK9r0iFiXE</p> <p>Notes: 26 people, 5 different countries. 48% are from Uganda, 25% are from Kenya and the rest from France, Ethiopia and Tanzania.</p> <p>20% of registrants from an academic library with publishing organisations making up 40% and the rest come from academic research backgrounds; non-profits and charities; service or technology organisations, funders, and governmental and non-governmental organisations amongst others</p>
23 Oct 2024	Introducing Copim's work to support open access publishing	Open access book publishing: Infrastructure solutions and reflections	Joe Deville	<p>Event page: https://www.eifl.net/resources/online-discussion-open-access-book-publishing-infrastructure</p> <p>Slides: in English: https://www.eifl.net/sites/default/files/resources/introducing_copim_english.pptx in Ukrainian: https://www.eifl.net/sites/default/files/resources/ua_introducing_copim_ukrainian_0.pptx</p> <p>Notes: 20 attendees</p> <p>A conversation series hosted by EIFL in collaboration with SUPRR (Supporting Ukrainian Publishing Resilience and Recovery) and the Ministry of Education and Science of Ukraine</p>

22 Oct 2024	Choosing Open Access for Books	Coventry Open Press Conversations: 'Everything you ever wanted to know about OA publishing (for books), but were afraid to ask (in 90 minutes)	Judith Fathallah	Event page: https://libcal.coventry.ac.uk/event/4284622 Slides: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14717434
16-20 Oct 2024	Copim & DOAB joint stand	Frankfurt Book Fair	Kevin Sanders, Kira Hopkins, Toby Steiner, Jordy Findanis	Event page: https://connect.buchmesse.de/newfront/exhibitor/thoth-open-metadata Slides: N/A
13 Oct 2024	Affects of open access: Platform building as affective method in scholarly publishing	Society for the Study of Affect: Promises, Impasses, Settling. Conference at Millersville University, Lancaster Pennsylvania	Joe Deville	Event page: https://affectsociety.com/pits/ Slides: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14652800
10 Oct 2024	Update on Copim and Open Book Futures	Open Research Scotland meeting October 2024	Simon Bowie	Event page: N/A Slides: N/A
01-02 Oct 2024	Copim — community-led infrastructures for OA books	JurOA conference 2024	Toby Steiner	Event page: https://openrewi.myeu.cloud/index.php/s/c22XjRDNykksSby Slides: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13869406
26 Sep 2024	National Libraries Network Meeting #4	Copim/WP7 meeting	Archiving & Digital Preservation Group (Loughborough University, Thoth)	Notes: Fourth official meeting of the informal National Libraries Network within OBF WP7.
25 Sep 2024	Copim's Open Book Futures project— an update and showcase of our work	Copim webinar/workshop	Copim WPs	Recording and slides: https://copim.pubpub.org/pub/obf-showcase-catchup Notes : c. 80 participants online, c. 170 registrations.

23-24 Sep 2024	Leveraging the power of open research information to foster open collaboration towards an equitable not-for-profit ecosystem for Open Access books	Barcelona declaration on Open Infrastructure Conference in Paris	Rupert Gatti	Event page: https://barcelona-declaration.org/conference_programme/ Slides: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13823880
20 Sep 2024	Represented Opening the Future and Copim	OA Book Transitions multi-stakeholder workshop	Tom Grady	Arranged by Information Power. Event page: https://www.informationpower.co.uk/open-access-transitions-for-book-publishers-spa-ops-4-0/ Slides: N/A
19 Sep 2024	Crisis in higher education and the future of Diamond open access	Copim & LSE Library & LSE Press event (online and in-person)	LSE Library, LSE Press, OBC, OtF	Slides and report: https://copim.pubpub.org/pub/catch-up-future-of-diamond Notes: c. 150 participants, and c. 280 registrations.
17 Sep 2024	Choosing Open Access for Books As a Precarious Scholar	OASPA 2024 Conference	Judith Fathallah	Event page: https://www.oaspa.org/news/oaspa-2024-conference-programme/ Slides: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14717795 Recording: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=pzSG7_VLvMs&list=PLIpJXV9MOz0MslBc1yVogeiMw2liHWoz6&index=9
17 Sep 2024	Precarity in scholar-led & marginalized open access publishing	OASPA 2024 Conference	Joe Deville	Event page: https://www.oaspa.org/news/oaspa-2024-conference-programme/ Slides: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14652580 Recording: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=pzSG7_VLvMs&list=PLIpJXV9MOz0MslBc1yVogeiMw2liHWoz6&index=9

16 Sep 2024	Can scaling small scale? Lessons learned from building community-led infrastructures for open access book publishing	OASPA 2024 Conference	Joe Deville. Contributors: Janneke Adema; Miranda Barnes; Toby Steiner; Tom Grady; Hannah Hillen; Kira Hopkins; Rebekka Kiesewetter; Kevin Sanders	Event page: https://www.oaspa.org/news/oaspa-2024-conference-programme/ Poster: https://zenodo.org/records/13694568
12 Sep 2024	Sustainable Community-Led Open Access Beyond the BPC	Association of Learned Society Publishers Annual Conference and Awards 2024	Joe Deville	Event page: https://alpsp.cventevents.com/event/2409AIC-home/websitePage:1f46e137-68df-4932-bb2f-7639736a7bb5 Slides: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14652536
11 Sep 2024	No open access without open infrastructure: 5 non-profit infrastructures for OA books	Open-Access-Tage 2024	Hannah Hillen	Event page: https://open-access-tage.de/open-access-tage-2024-koeln Poster: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12263353 Received an award at conference.
3 Sep 2024	Transparency through community-led open infrastructure: a pathway to trust	UK DARIAH Day	Miranda Barnes	Event page: https://www.dariah.eu/2024/07/25/uk-dariah-day/ Poster: https://zenodo.org/records/10608700
21 Aug 2024	Introduction to OA for Books: Challenges and Opportunities	UKSG webinar series "Introduction to OA"	Tom Grady Lucy Barnes Sam Nesbit (Head of Schol Comms @ Sussex Uni Library)	Event page: N/A Slides: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14673409
19-20 Aug 2024	Experimental Publishing as a Critical Praxis: Rethinking Distinctions between Research and Publishing	Supervising Artistic and Practice-based Research: Publishing for Urgency [University of Copenhagen,	Janneke Adema	Event page: https://pass.ku.dk/supervising-artistic-and-practice-based-research-publishing-for-urgency/

		Denmark: Art Hub Copenhagen]		Slides: [tbc] Notes: Organised by Maibritt Borgen, Royal Danish Academy of Fine Arts, School of Visual Arts; Mikkel Bogh, PASS – Center for Practice-based Art Studies, Rune Gade, and Holger Schulze.
16 Aug 2024	Towards a fairer, more sustainable future for open access books	Virginia Scholarly Communication Interest Group (VASCIG) Summer Meeting	Joe Deville	Event page: https://sites.google.com/richmond.edu/va-scholarly-communication/meetings Slides: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14652203
Q5 (May 2024—July 2024)				
19 Jul 2024	Can STS transform scholarly publishing?	EASST/4S Conference	Joe Deville	Event page: https://www.easst4s2024.net/programme/#13972.85946 Slides: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14651898
16-19 Jul 2024	Experimenting with academic knowledge production	11th quadrennial joint conference of EASST and 4S	Janneke Adema, Simon Bowie, Rebekka Kiesewetter, Julien McHardy	Event page: https://nomadit.co.uk/conference/easst-4s2024/p/15175 Slides: N/A
03 July 2024	Evaluating and Assessing Diamond Open Access Book Initiatives: Challenges and Opportunities	LIBER 2024	Kevin Sanders, Niels Stern, Giulia Trentacosti, Joe Deville	Event page: https://liberconference.eu/workshop-10-evaluating-and-assessing-diamond-open-access-book-initiatives-challenges-and-opportunities/ Report on event: https://openbookcollective.pubpub.org/pub/liber-2024
19 June 2024	The Open Book Collective and Thoth: Bringing publishers, libraries and service providers together to establish a shared sustainable open ecosystem for books	OTESSA conference	Judith Fathallah, Livy Snyder, Lidia Uziel, Paula Kennedy, Toby Steiner	Event page: https://otessa.github.io/2024/jun19.html#session-18.3-addressing-inequities-sustaining-positive-change Slides: N/A

5 June 2024	Thoth Archiving Network: How institutional repositories can become involved in preserving long-form scholarship	Open Repositories Conference	Miranda Barnes	Event page: https://www.conftool.net/or2024/index.php?page=browseSessions&form_date=2024-06-05&presentations=show Slides: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12579528
22 May 2024	An Overview of Copim & Open Access Revenue Models	Publishers Association of South Africa - Scholarly Committee, Open Access seminar	Tom Grady	Event page: N/A Slides: https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.12749998
15 May 2024	Posthumanities Practice: Performing Publishing Proactively	Wanting Better: The Practice of Publishing for Practice Research , University of Leeds	Janneke Adema	Event page: https://cepra.leeds.ac.uk/2024/02/26/wanting-better-the-practice-of-publishing-for-practice-research-15-5-24/ Slides : [tbc] Notes: Event at The Centre for Practice Research in the Arts (CePRA), with William Urricchio (MIT/Utrecht University), organised by Nick Thurston, Leeds University
9 May 2024	Making open access book funding work fairly	Gold Leaf Consulting Webinar	Tom Grady, Kira Hopkins, Kat Baier (CEU Press)	Event page: N/A Slides: https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.12749822
7 May 2024	Workshop with Ubiquity publishers	Copim Workshop/Webinar	OBC, Thoth	Event page: N/A Slides:N/A
1 May 2024	Bridging Altruism to Strategy in OA Book Publishing – How Libraries Can Close Funding Gaps to Support a Bibliodiverse Global Shared Collection	Copim Workshop/Webinar	OBC, University of Delaware Publishing, University of Arizona Libraries, University of Alberta, Iowa State University Digital Press, Lyrisis	Slides: Annie Johnson, "Towards an Open Access Strategy for Books" < https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.11202986 > Harrison W. Inefuku, "Open Access Book Publishing" < https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.11202885 >

				<p>Ellen Dubinsky, "OA at UA Libraries" <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11202827></p> <p>Joe Deville, "Bridging Altruism to Strategy in Open Access Book Publishing" <https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.11202754></p> <p>Sara Chomyc, "University of Alberta Library & Open Access Monographs" <https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.11202590></p>
1 May 2024	Experiments in Academic Book Publishing	Experiments in Radical Publishing. Sonic Screen Lab, London College of Communication, University of the Arts London	Janneke Adema	<p>Event page: https://www.eventbrite.co.uk/e/experiments-in-radical-publishing-tickets-884178350247</p> <p>Slides: [tbc]</p> <p>Notes: With Charlotte Crofts (UWE/Screenworks), Ashwani Sharma (UAL/darkmatter), and Mark Peter Wright (UAL/CRISAP).</p>
Q4 (February 2024—April 2024)				
30 Apr 2024	National Libraries Network Meeting #3	Copim/WP7 meeting/webinar	Archiving & Digital Preservation Group (Loughborough University, Thoth), British Library, [anonymous member], German National Library, Dutch National Library, National Library of Qatar, National Library of Scotland	Notes: Third official meeting of the informal National Libraries Network within OBF WP7.
30 Apr 2024	CEU Press: Opening the Future, webinar	Copim / OA Australasia Network Webinar	OtF, OA Australasia	Event page: https://ceu-edu.zoom.us/meeting/register/tJAlcuGorT0oGNKl3om9n6wapuuuYQpJ68Qg

			Network, CEU Press	Notes: 30 registered participants.
30 April 2024	Making open access book funding work fairly	Open Access Australasia Webinar	Tom Grady, Kira Hopkins, Kat Baier (CEU Press)	Event page: N/A Slides: https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.12749503
25 April 2024	How To Facilitate Horizontal Collaboration Between Community-Led Infrastructures for Equitable and Bibliodiverse Futures for Open Access Books?	OPERAS 2024 conference	Lucy Barnes, Rupert Gatti, Kevin Sanders, Niels Stern, Toby Steiner	Event page: https://operas-eu.org/news-and-events/calendar-2/programme/day-1-conference-programme/ Slides: N/A
18 Apr 2024	Practical workshop on evaluating collective funding models for open access books	Jisc Webinar	Tom Grady & Kira Hopkins (co-organisers & facilitators)	Event page: https://www.eventsforce.net/jiscevents/frontend/req/thome.csp?pageID=598003&eventID=2033 Slides: N/A
18 Apr 2024	"Opening the Future" – A Reliable Funding Model for Open Access Monographs: Introducing an Innovative Approach to Publishing OA Books Through Library Membership Funding	Copim workshop/webinar	OtF, Kennesaw State University	Event page: https://digitalcommons.kennesaw.edu/ato/2024al/thingsopen/presentations/5/
17 Apr 2024	Evaluating Evaluation Criteria for OA Book Publishers	Copim workshop/webinar	OBC, Project Muse, OpenEdition, African Platform for Open Scholarship, SciELO Books, DOAB, Opening the Future, JSTOR, Thoth, AG Universitätsverlag e, University of Georgia Press/AUPresses, Fulcrum	Report on event : https://katinamagazine.org/content/article/open-knowledge/2024/how-should-we-evaluate-open-access-book-publishing Notes: 20 participants

11 Apr 2024	Workshop do Thoth Latin American Publishers, abril de 2024	Copim webinar	Thoth, Editorial UNRN (Argentina), Editorial Flacso Ecuador, Editorial UR (Colombia) and EUNED (Costa Rica)	Report on event: https://doi.org/10.21428/785a6451.1a61edad
9 & 10 Apr 2024	Getting Out From the Back of the Sofa: Or, How to Achieve Sustainable Funding for Open Access Books	UKSG 2024	Tom Grady (WP3 Otf); Elaine Sykes (Lancaster)	Event page: https://www.uksg.org/uksg-annual-conference-2024-programme/ Slides: available from a later version delivered in October 2024: https://www.uksg.org/wp-content/uploads/2024/10/Tom-Grady-Elaine-Sykes-combined-UKSG-webinar-Oct-2024.pdf
8-10 Apr 2024	Copim community stand	UKSG 2024	Kevin Sanders, Tom Grady, Kira Hopkins, Simon Bowie	Event page: https://www.uksg.org/uksg-annual-conference-2024-programme/ Slides: N/A
4 Apr 2024	Introducing the OBC & Mattering Press	Creating and Developing an Open Access Journal: An experience sharing and networking event. Lancaster University	Joe Deville	Event page: https://portal.lancaster.ac.uk/intranet/events/creating-and-developing-an-open-access-journal-experience-sharing-and-networking-event Slides: N/A
1 Mar 2024	Choosing Open Access for Books: Myths and Truths Beyond the BPC (updated version)	Choosing Open Access For Books at UCLAN Library	Judith Fathallah	Event page: N/A Slides: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14620401
18 Mar 2024	Experimental Book Publishing: Tools, Practices, and Books to Promote the Publication of Experimental Scholarly Works	Northumbria University Open Research Week	Simon Bowie, Janneke Adema	Event page: N/A Slides: https://figshare.northumbria.ac.uk/articles/presentation/ORW_Experimental_Book_Publishing_Tools_Practices_and_Books_to_Promote_the_Publication_of_Experimental_Scholarly_Works_/25472479

27 Feb 2024	CEU Press Opening the Future webinar	Copim / CEU Press webinar	OtF, CEU Press	Event page: https://ceu-edu.zoom.us/meeting/register/tJwoc-ghpzgpEtW9Bz2Clu3hG2iMt0pe79cc?tk=pLr62LbLdebjuhr5nAvW1tF86K8QIFBc2boigkY1F1w.AG.lwGzdrvOLJcyiMWRqUox5JanaXdPOrRLDDxwHErPPasTGY_K7K6Pqp7DhibWH0Xdj-t09m0v0fbVEofr17lztJt7FMMyFejMjDqvcHRcmP7027Q.Wd2P34oFThlauUq7aaj-0w.01zB8lypD9U37H4O#/detail
19 Feb 2024 until 21 Feb 2024	Transparency through community-led open infrastructure: a pathway to trust	18th International Digital Curation Conference, Edinburgh	Miranda Barnes, Toby Steiner	Event page: https://dcc.ac.uk/events/idcc24 Slides: https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.10608699
14 Feb 2024	Open Access infrastructures and higher education futures	Lancaster Institute for Contemporary Arts Research Seminar	Joe Deville	Event page: N/A Slides: N/A
13 Feb 2024	Introducing the OBC to IReL members (Irish Library Consortium)	Copim webinar/meeting	IReL and OBC	Event page: N/A Slides: N/A
7 Feb-9 Feb 2024	Towards Sustainable Open Access Book Publishing in the African Context	Series of workshops at the University of Cape Town	OBC, Thoth, DOAB/OAPEN, University of Cape Town Library, University of Cape Town Press, African Platform for Open Scholarship, Association of African Universities, Lancaster University, punctum, Mattering Press	Event page & slides: https://doi.org/10.21428/41ca814e.c8fbbc53 Report on event: https://doi.org/10.21428/41ca814e.6fa8c7df Notes: 40 participants

6 Feb 2024	Introducing Opening the Future and CEU Press (Webinar 2)	CRKN Members Webinar	Tom Grady, Kira Hopkins, CEU Press	Event page: https://ceu-edu.zoom.us/meeting/register/tJAfceytrzwuHdz2epVQFZJa-A8fcHRCpoXs#/registration Slides: N/A Notes: 15 participants.
Q3 (November 2023—January 2024)				
29 Jan 2024	Introducing Opening the Future and CEU Press (Webinar 1)	CRKN Members Webinar	Tom Grady, Kira Hopkins, CEU Press	Event page: https://ceu-edu.zoom.us/meeting/register/tJAfceytrzwuHdz2epVQFZJa-A8fcHRCpoXs#/registration Slides: N/A Notes: 15 participants.
25 Jan 2024	Copim Connects SCONUL libraries: practical strategies to support equitable OA book publishing	Copim / SCONUL Webinar	OtF, SCONUL, Lancaster University, Coventry University, University of Sheffield, Salford University	Event page: https://www.sconul.ac.uk/event/copim-and-sconul-exploring-practical-problems-and-potential-strategies-to-fund-equitable-oa Recording: https://vimeo.com/906390958 Report on event: https://copim.pubpub.org/pub/vmatlpc7/release/1 Notes: 350 participants
23 Jan 2024	National Libraries Network Meeting #2	Copim / WP7 meeting	Archiving & Digital Preservation Group (Loughborough University, Thoth)	Notes: Second official meeting of the informal National Libraries Network within OBF WP7.
22 Jan 2024	Information Hub and Collective Development Fund scoping workshop		OBC, Punctum, White Horse Press, Mattering Press, African Minds, Westminster University Press,	Notes: 15 participants Report on event: https://doi.org/10.21428/41ca814e.f748da11

			University of London Press, Leuven University Press, DOAB/OAPEN, Thoth, OBP, meson press, mediastudies.presses	
15 Jan 2024	Experimental Publishing Pilots: Match-making workshop for applicants	Copim / Experimental Publishing workshop	authors and project teams (17 proposed pilot projects presenting), platforms (e.g. Electric Book Works, Manifold, PubPub, Scalar, Juncture) and presses (e.g. UCL, LSE, Westminster, UoL, Bristol UP, Coimbra, mediastudies.presses, Open Book Publishers)	Report on event: https://copim.pubpub.org/pub/matchmaking Notes: c.40 participants.
11 Jan 2024	Open Access and Global South Scholars: Needs, Experiences, Barriers		Lancaster University, Southern Women Academic Network	Report on event: https://doi.org/10.21428/41ca814e.b423d75c Notes: 10 participants
11 Jan 2024	Thoth Open Metadata: Open, community-led infrastructures for metadata management, dissemination & archiving	ENABLE! workshop	Toby Steiner	Event page: https://enable-oa.org/news/einladung-zum-enable-werkstattgesprach-am-11012024-thoth-open-metadata Slides: https://zenodo.org/records/10497884

				Notes: C. 60 participants
11 Jan 2024	Books contain Multitudes: Valuing Phone & Spear	Multimodal Appreciation Workshop #1	Julien McHardy	Event page: https://www2.hu-berlin.de/multimodalappreciation/2023/12/29/multimodal-appreciation-workshop-1-program/ Slides: N/A
12 Dec 2023	Open Book Collective: Collective Paths Toward an Open and Sustainable Ecosystem for Monographs	CNI Conference, Washington DC	Lidia Uziel, Livy Snyder	Event page: https://www.cni.org/topics/digital-libraries/open-book-collective-collective-paths-toward-an-open-and-sustainable-ecosystem-for-monographs Recording: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=obWzE2_uNk8 Slides: N/A Notes: Participants: c. 50 (in person)
8 Dec 2023	Closing the Knowledge Gap: Improving Open Access Knowledge Sharing between Publishers, Authors, and Libraries	The Charleston Virtual Conference	Livy Snyder	Event page: https://www.charleston-hub.com/the-charleston-conference/welcome/2023-charleston-conference/ Poster: https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.12751568 Notes: Participants: 60 (in person)
29 Nov 2023	Meet the Open Book Collective	Opening the Future and the Open Book Collective. Diamond Open Access for Books? Open Access Network, hosted at University of Konstanz	Joe Deville	Event page: https://open-access.network/en/fortbilden/workshops/informationsreihe-die-open-access-transformation-nachhaltig-gestalten-diamond-oa-als-alternative/information-event-on-november-29th-2023

				<p>Slides: DOI 10.5281/zenodo.10224941</p> <p>Notes: Participants: c. 50</p>
29 Nov 2023	Making Open Access Book Funding Work Fairly: Opening the Future Library Membership Scheme	<p>Opening the Future and the Open Book Collective. Diamond Open Access for Books?</p> <p>Open Access Network, hosted at University of Konstanz</p>	Tom Grady	<p>Event page: https://open-access.network/en/fortbilden/workshops/informationsreihe-die-open-access-transformation-nachhaltig-gestalten-diamond-oa-als-alternative/information-event-on-november-29th-2023</p> <p>Slides: DOI 10.5281/zenodo.10224675</p> <p>Notes: Participants: c. 50</p>
29 Nov 2023	Open Book Collective Development Fund Grant Scoping Workshop		Continental Platform, Digital Preservation Coalition, Invest in Open Infrastructures, Knowledge Futures, Language Science Press, OpenEdition, Public Knowledge Project, SPARC EU	<p>Report on event: https://doi.org/10.21428/41ca814e.f748da11</p> <p>Notes: Workshop to inform the OBC Development Fund Grant.</p>
28 Nov 2023	COPIM Connects Librarians: OA books options and advice for your authors (hosted online by ALN & COPIM)		Academic Libraries North (ALN) Network, Manchester Met University, University of Oxford, University of Sheffield,	Notes: With the imminent launch of the UKRI OA books policy in January, and the rise in activity surrounding OA book publishing more broadly, authors need sound guidance to navigate this rapidly developing area of publishing. This webinar, jointly organised by ALN and OA books experts from Copim, will support librarians in

			Open Book Publishers, Lancaster University	making authors aware of their open access options for books.
27 Nov 2023	A Community-led Future for OA Books: How can new OA infrastructures enable libraries to support 'scaling small' in scholarly publishing?	The Charleston Virtual Conference	Lidia Uziel, Livy Snyder, Dave Park, Toby Steiner	Event page: https://www.charleston-hub.com/the-charleston-conference/welcome/conference-agenda/ Slides: N/A Notes: Participants: 88 (online)
16 Nov 2023	Thoth Publishers' workshop		Thoth, punctum books, Open Book Publishers, Mattering Press, University of Westminster Press, LSE Press, Open Book Publishers, punctum books, SciELO Books, Loughborough University Library, Open Book Collective, Lancaster University, mediastudies.press, textem Verlag, ADOCS Verlag, Scottish Universities Press, meson press, Edinburgh Diamond, and Mattering Press	Report on workshop: https://copim.pubpub.org/pub/thoth-publishers-workshop-2023/release/1 Notes: 21 participants.
15 Nov 2023	Choosing Open Access for Books: Myths and Truths Beyond the BPC	Unveiling Open Access Monograph Publishing, at Exeter University	Judith Fathallah	Event page: https://www.eventbrite.co.uk/e/unveiling-open-

				access-monograph-publishing-tickets-747061369667 Slides: https://zenodo.org/records/10189397
13 Nov 2023	Looking to a more equitable future: the institutional repository as digital monograph archive for the small and scholar-led press	UKCoRR Members Day 2023	Miranda Barnes	Event page: https://blog.core.ac.uk/2023/11/16/ukcorr-members-day-core-panel-session/ Slides: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10123353
8 Nov 2023	Thoth Archiving Network: Supporting Small and Scholar-led Publishers with Repository-Led Preservation of OA Books	The 18th Munin Conference on Scholarly Publishing	Miranda Barnes, Gareth Cole, Toby Steiner	Event page: https://site.uit.no/muninconf/program/ Abstract: https://septentrio.uit.no/index.php/SCS/article/view/7140 Recording: https://uit.cloud.panopto.eu/Panopto/Pages/Viewer.aspx?id=8cee185c-08c8-4f6f-a052-b06600d6bd63&start=11155.054 Slides: 10.5281/zenodo.10089533
8 Nov 2023	Getting out from the back of the sofa: Sustainable funding for Open Access books	18th Munin Conference on Scholarly Publishing.	OtF, University of Tromso, SPARC Europe, University of Oslo, Bloomsbury Academic	Event page: https://site.uit.no/muninconf/program/ Abstract: https://septentrio.uit.no/index.php/SCS/article/view/7156 Slides: https://zenodo.org/records/10226504 Notes: 20 participants.
6 Nov 2023 until 1 Dec 2023	Copim information stand	The Charleston Conference	Livy Snyder	Event page: https://www.charleston-hub.com/the-charleston-conference/welcome/conference-agenda/

1 Nov 2023	The Times They Are A' Changing: How Can We Fund Open Access Books Equitably and Sustainably	Copim / Project MUSE webinar	OtF, Project MUSE, California Digital Library (CDL), Central European University Press	<p>Event page: https://jh.zoom.us/webinar/register/7516956723405/WN_HLiuPo3SSUeft2q1abtczA#/registration</p> <p>Recording: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=fqDv80x2F8Y</p> <p>Report on workshop: https://copim.pubpub.org/pub/5t35zs1t</p> <p>Notes: 432 participants registered</p>
Q2 (August 2023—October 2023)				
30 Oct 2023	Networks of libraries supporting open access book publishing	Open and Engaged 2023: Community Over Commercialisation, British Library	Rupert Gatti	<p>Event page: https://blogs.bl.uk/digital-scholarship/2023/09/open-and-engaged-2023.html</p> <p>Slides: 10.5281/zenodo.10225439</p> <p>Notes: https://bl.iro.bl.uk/concern/conference_items/48fba8b5-7a20-4ecb-bd44-e1643d65b577</p>
26 Oct 2023	Reflections on experimenting with book publishing in Copim and Open Book Futures	Utrecht University Library Open Textbooks project workshop	Simon Bowie	<p>Event page: N/A</p> <p>Slides: https://pureportal.coventry.ac.uk/en/activities/reflections-on-experimenting-with-book-publishing-in-copim-and-op</p>
26 Oct 2023	Introducing the Open Book Collective	Open Access Week: University of Bremen	Kevin Sanders	<p>Event page: https://m.suub.uni-bremen.de/ueber-uns/neues-aus-der-suub/themenwoche-open-access-vom-23-bis-27-oktober-2023/</p> <p>Slides: https://m.suub.uni-bremen.de/uploads/cms/files/Introducing_OBC_Bremen_KS_2023_10_26_1_2.pdf</p>

26 Oct 2023	Managing and Disseminating Open Metadata of Scholarly Monographs	Workshop on Open Citations & Open Scholarly Metadata 2023	Vincent W.J. van Gerven Oei	Event page: https://workshop-oc.github.io/#about Slides: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10032765
25 Oct 2023	OA Week webinar on Thoth Open Metadata	Open Access Week, University of Latvia Library	Toby Steiner	Event page: https://www.biblioteka.lu.lv/parmums/zinas/zina/t/80629/ Slides: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10039858
24 Oct 2023	Open Access Books: Panel Discussion	Open Access Week 2023 - University of Derby	Joe Deville	Event page: https://libcal.derby.ac.uk/calendar/events/UoDOpenAccessWeek23OABooks Recording: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=k4YiVSqfIRY Notes: 40 attendees
24 Oct 2023	Beyond BPCs: Towards fairer, more sustainable futures for Open Access books	Danish Network for Open Access, Open Access Week 2023 Webinars	Joe Deville	Event page: https://openaccess.dk/oaw2023/tuesday_oct_24_2 Slides: 10.5281/zenodo.10225591 . Recording: https://oer.ku.dk/media/t/0_4s4nbeko
24 Oct 2023	Advancing Community-Led Open Infrastructure	Boulder OA week event	Janneke Adema	Event page: https://www.colorado.edu/libraries/open-access-week Slides: N/A
23 Oct 2023	Scholars are doing it for themselves: The challenges and opportunities of open access scholar-led publishing	Open Access Week, Sheffield University	Toby Steiner	Event page: https://www.sheffield.ac.uk/openresearch/events/open-access-week-2023 Slides: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10033672

19 Oct 2023	Congratulations to UCT Press on its relaunch	Relaunch of University of Cape Town Press (UCT)		Event page: N/A Slides: N/A Notes: 50 attendees at event
10 Oct-11 Oct 2023	Thoth / OAPEN / OBC Cross-Initiative Outreach Workshop (Den Haag)	Copim workshop / meeting	OAPEN, Thoth, OBC	Report on event: https://doi.org/10.21428/785a6451.a2e47002
4 Oct 2023	Collective funding models for open access books #3: Supporting Critical OA Infrastructure	Copim / Jisc Webinar	Thoth, Jisc, OABN, OAPEN/DOAB, Thoth, University of Manchester	Event page: https://beta.jisc.ac.uk/events/collective-funding-models-for-open-access-books-oct-2023
4 Oct 2023	Open Infrastructures for Open Access books: Community-led Metadata Management, Dissemination & Archiving with Thoth	Jisc webinar: Collective funding models for open access books — the importance of community-led open infrastructures	Toby Steiner	Event page: https://beta.jisc.ac.uk/events/collective-funding-models-for-open-access-books-oct-2023 Slides: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8406752
29 Sep 2023	Die Zukunft von Open-Access-Büchern in der deutschen Open-Access-Landschaft: Strategische, ökonomische und wissenschaftspolitische Perspektiven	Open-Access-Tage 2023: "Visionen gestalten"	Toby Steiner	Event page: https://open-access-tage.de/open-access-tage-2023-berlin/programm/donnerstag-28092023 Slides: N/A
29 Sep 2023	Thoth Open Metadata Management and Distribution Service for OA Books	Open-Access-Tage 2023: "Visionen gestalten"	Toby Steiner	Event page: https://open-access-tage.de/open-access-tage-2023-berlin/programm/donnerstag-28092023 Poster: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8273948
27 Sep 2023	COPIM und Governance von wissenschaftsgeleiteten Publikationsinfrastrukturen	Satelliten-Konferenz „Wissenschaftsgeleitetes Open-Access-Publizieren“ zu	Toby Steiner	Event page: https://www.ibi.hu-berlin.de/de/forschung/infomanagement/events/oat23ibi

		den Open-Access-Tagen 2023		Slides: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8385346
27 Sep 2023	National Libraries Network Meeting #1	Copim workshop / meeting	Archiving & Digital Preservation Group (Loughborough University, Thoth), British Library, National Library of Scotland, German National Library	First official meeting of the informal National Libraries Network within OBF WP7.
20 Sep 2023	OASPA 2023 Conference on Open Scholarship	OASPA 2023 Conference	Toby Steiner	Event page: https://oaspa.org/2023-conference-program/ Poster: https://oaspa.org/wp-content/uploads/2023/09/Toby-Steiner-thoth-poster-OASPA2023-A1-Steiner.pdf
20 Sep 2023	Equity and sustainability in Diamond OA publishing	OASPA 2023 Conference	Judith Fathallah with Sharla Lair, Amanda Ramalho, Caroline Edwards and Rob Cookson	Event page: https://oaspa.org/2023-conference-program/ Slides: N/A
19 Sep 2023	Getting Out From The Back of the Sofa: Sustainable Funding for Open Access Books	OASPA 2023 Conference	Tom Grady & Lucy Barnes	Event page: https://oaspa.org/2023-conference-program/ Poster: https://oaspa.org/wp-content/uploads/2023/09/Tom-Grady-OASPA23-poster_final.pdf
6 Sep 2023	The Open Book Collective: An Infrastructure for Equity and Diversity	OAI13	Judith Fathallah	Event page: https://oai.events/etn-speaker/dr-judith-fathallah/ Slides: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8322034

				Recording: https://vimeo.com/showcase/10628629/video/862063618
2 Sep 2023	Open Metadata Management and Dissemination with Thoth	OSCAL2023	Vincent van Gerven Oei	Event page: https://cfp.openlabs.cc/oscal2023/talk/NNGYJH/ Slides: N/A
3 Aug 2023	Publishing from Collections Using Linked Open Data Source and Computational Publishing Pipelines	FSCI 2023 Enhancing the Global Impact of Open Scholarship	Simon Worthington, Simon Bowie, Janneke Adema	Event page: https://force11.org/fsci/post/course-list-with-abstracts-2023/ Slides: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10226312
Q1 (May 2023—July 2023)				
19 Jul 2023	Collective funding models for open access books #2: the Library perspective	Copim / Jisc Webinar	OtF, OBC, Jisc OABN Imperial College University of Essex St Andrews	Event page: https://beta.jisc.ac.uk/events/collective-funding-models-for-open-access-books-july-2023-
14 Jul 2023	Open Book Futures: Working together to Build Community-owned Infrastructures for OA books	COPIM – SciELO 25 Years Seminar	Lucy Barnes, Joe Deville, Rupert Gatti, Tom Grady, Toby Steiner	Event page: https://25.scielo.org/en/seminars/copim/ Slides: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8142775 Video: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=PfdUZyLkMBE Notes: c.60 participants
6 Jul 2023	Open Book Collective & Thoth Open Metadata posters	LIBER 2023	Francesca Corazza & Toby Steiner	Event page: https://wayback.archive-it.org/12503/20230725231049/https://liberconference.eu/wp-content/uploads/2023/06/LIBER_2023_conf_boo

				k_website_NEW.pdf
29 Jun 2023	Developing equitable OA for books: Building open infrastructure	'My heart is an open book': Open Access for longform research [Organised by the University of Sussex]	Lucy Barnes	Event page: https://www.eventbrite.co.uk/e/my-heart-is-an-open-book-open-access-for-longform-research-tickets-638641733617 Slides: https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.10185273
27 Jun 2023	The COPIM Project's Tools and Infrastructures to Support Open Access Monographs	Open Science Conference	Joe Deville, Tom Grady and Tobias Steiner	Event page: https://www.open-science-conference.eu/ Slides: N/A
21 Jun 2023	Collective funding models for open access books #1: the Publisher perspective	Copim / Jisc Webinar	OtF, OBC, Jisc, OABN, Liverpool University Press, MIT Press, White Horse Press	Event page: https://beta.jisc.ac.uk/events/collective-funding-models-for-open-access-books
21 Jun 2023	Another New Normal: How Can We Sustainably Fund Open Access Monographs	Academic Libraries North Conference 2023	Tom Grady and Joe Deville	Event page: https://docs.google.com/document/d/1k03ta43-t4CqwIBw5FtEDXwtbvXU1QaN/edit Slides: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10226654 Notes: c.50 UK-based librarians
13 Jun 2023	Experimenting with Living Books as a Posthumanities Practice	Communication in Culture and Society – Research at the crossroads of audience, public, and collaboration, Linköping University Research Retreat	Janneke Adema (with Nicholas Thoburn, Jonas & Cecilia Grönberg and Erica Engdahl)	Event page: N/A Slides: 10.5281/zenodo.10225905.
6 Jun 2023	'Promoting Bibliodiversity in Academic Publishing: Scaling Small and Experimental Post-Publishing'	Centre for the Study of the Networked Image (CSNI),	Janneke Adema	Event page: https://www.centrefortheStudyof.net/?p=7082

		London South Bank University		Slides: 10.5281/zenodo.10226038
2 Jun 2023	Scaling Small: The Open Book Collective Launch and Platform Practice	OTESSA 2023	Judith Fathallah	Event page: https://otessa.org/2023/ Slides: https://zenodo.org/records/10186301
25 May 2023	Sustainable futures for OA book publishing: Sheffield, St. Andrews and the Open Book Collective	National Acquisitions Group Seminar 2023	Judith Fathallah, Kyle Brady, Peter Barr	Event page: https://nag.org.uk/wp-content/uploads/2022/11/Abstracts-and-biosV1.pdf Slides: N/A
25 May 2023	Sustainable Funding for Open Access Monographs: Opening the Future and other collective funding models	National Acquisitions Group Seminar 2023	Tom Grady	Event page: https://nag.org.uk/development/nagcd13_copim/ Slides: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10226960
23 May 2023	The Open Book Collective: Equity, Diversity and Sustainability in Open Access Book Publishing	OASPA Webinar: Funding Open Access after the Transformation	Judith Fathallah (with Vivian Berghahn, Ámbar Tenorio-Fornés, Evgeniya Lupova-Henry)	Event page: https://oaspa.org/webinar-funding-open-access-after-the-transformation/ Slides: https://zenodo.org/record/7991155 Notes: 700+ participants registered
9 May 2023	Thoth: Open and Trusted Metadata for Open Access Books and Book Chapters	Library Publishing Coalition Panel	Rupert Gatti	Event page: https://librarypublishing.org/panel-may-9-1200/ Slides: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10225504
May 2023	Open Access infrastructures and higher education futures	Workshop at Lancaster University	Joe Deville and Judith Fathallah	Event page: N/A Slides: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10225658

9.5 Images

Figure 1. Photographs from *Crisis in higher education and the future of Diamond open access*, on *Thursday 19 Sept 2024, 17:00-18:30 (BST)*, at the *London School of Economics*. (photography by [Catriona Gray](#))

Figure 2. Images from UKSG 2025.

“It’s Nice, but is it sustainable? Rethinking sustainability for Diamond open access infrastructures and funding models”. See: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15189001>
 Photography by UKSG.

Graphics shared on social media to promote Copim stand and social event